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THE FINANCIAL POLICY OF THE SECOND TRUMP'S ADMINISTRATION AS A PHENOMENON OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC MANIPULATION

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Abstract: *The second Trump administration (2025–2026) has introduced a qualitatively new form of global economic statecraft that transcends conventional protectionism. Employing tariff coercion under the International Emergency Economic Powers Act (IEEPA), dollar-infrastructure leverage, and the fusion of state authority with Big Tech interests, Washington has advanced what this article terms manipulative economic policy – a hybrid toolkit erasing the boundaries between economics, diplomacy, and geopolitical pressure. Drawing on macroeconomic data, legislative records, and comparative case analysis, the study identifies the mechanisms, reach, and structural limits of this policy. The empirical record for 2025–2026 reveals that an effective tariff rate of 7.7% (the highest since 1947) functioned primarily as a fiscal transfer from households to the federal government rather than a structural trade corrective. A February 2026 Supreme Court ruling that the president had exceeded his IEEPA authority – mandating the return of approximately USD 166 billion exposed the institutional ceiling of executive unilateralism. At the same time, the policy accelerated retaliatory mercantilism among allies (the EU's EuroStack programme) and deepened intra-coalition fractures within the MAGA movement, suggesting that aggressive economic manipulation generates diminishing geopolitical returns.*

Keywords: *Trump administration; financial manipulation; IEEPA; tariff policy; coercive diplomacy; Big Tech; US–China trade war; EuroStack; dollar hegemony; global fragmentation*

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial policy has emerged as a new frontier in the global system of checks and balances. The phenomenon with which the world was confronted in 2025 has rapidly assumed one of the most consequential roles in contemporary international affairs. The relevance of this inquiry lies in the fact that, between 2025 and 2026, the financial policy of the United States under the Trump administration gave rise to a distinct phenomenon – manipulative economic policy, that extends well beyond traditional protectionism. It encompasses massive tariff pressure on all major trading partners through the emergency powers conferred by IEEPA, as well as attempts at extraterritorial regulation of supply chains and digital markets. The aim of this article is to identify and analyze the mechanisms of this manipulation and to delineate the institutional, economic, and political limits of its effectiveness.

The second Trump administration’s financial policy represents a unique phenomenon that departs sharply from the instruments of the first term. It relies on active dollar manipulation, systematic tariff escalation, and an economic strategy oriented towards subordinating foreign companies to the American financial apparatus.

In the twenty-first century, the concept of financial manipulation has evolved far beyond its conventional market connotation, acquiring the status of a tool for amplifying geopolitical leverage and practicing coercive diplomacy [1]. It is therefore unsurprising that the United States has actively integrated this instrument into its economic statecraft. The second Trump administration treats the economy as a global network through which world trade can be subordinated to American influence, exploiting economic dependencies in the service of geopolitical and national interests.

2. MECHANISMS OF FINANCIAL COERCION

The Iraq–Iran case is instructive. US threats to impose 50% tariffs on countries supplying weapons to Iran represent a direct application of financial coercion as foreign policy. In the Iraqi case, the United States constructed a mechanism whereby Iraq’s oil revenues were deposited with the Federal Reserve Bank of New York and subsequently redirected back to Baghdad, enabling third-party states to access Iraqi finances without bearing direct risk. The US response – classic financial coercion involved pressure on the Iraqi government to reform its banking sector, centralize transfers through major American institutions such as Citigroup, and adopt standardized due-diligence procedures [2]. During the 2024 UN General Assembly negotiations, US Deputy Treasury Secretary Wally Adeyemo explicitly conditioned

continued financial support for Iraq on concrete banking-sector reforms, confirming the use of the financial system as leverage over an allied state.

The second Trump administration has simultaneously abandoned the rules-based framework that the United States itself constructed the Washington Consensus. As one scholar observes, this was a predictable, if often criticized, set of neoliberal prescriptions exported through formal, rules-based institutions such as the IMF and the World Bank [3]. In its place, a systemic conflict has emerged between the executive branch and other power structures. Private actors have acquired far greater influence over infrastructure and digital space, while the United States actively deploys economic weight to coerce specific countries – demanding that the European Union, Brazil, and South Korea align their national digital legislation with American corporate interests.

A comparison of Vice-President Vance’s 2025 speeches with Secretary of State Rubio’s 2026 statements reveals a marked rhetorical evolution. Vance, addressing the domestic economic situation, appeals to market accessibility for ordinary citizens; Rubio focuses on the global economy and frames policy as a grand contest against China and the Global South. Together, these figures serve distinct functions: the former mobilizes popular support, the latter consolidates it around a geopolitical narrative of American primacy.

3. THE IEEPA INSTRUMENT AND ITS INSTITUTIONAL LIMITS

The International Emergency Economic Powers Act (IEEPA) became the central instrument of financial manipulation. Originally designed to freeze assets and impose sanctions on hostile regimes Iran, Russia, North Korea: IEEPA was repurposed by the Trump administration as a vehicle for threatening blanket trade tariffs against any country whose policies conflicted with American preferences. This was the primary legal vehicle for the administration’s tariff architecture.

The decisive blow against this instrument was struck by the Supreme Court. In February 2026, the Court ruled that the president had exceeded his authority by using IEEPA to impose broad global tariffs – a decision that not only blocked the existing duties but obliged the government to refund approximately USD 166 billion already collected. Despite this judicial defeat, the administration has not abandoned the coercive approach, continuing to invoke the act and threatening renewed tariff escalation. This institutional confrontation creates profound unpredictability in decision-making and undermines long-term economic planning both domestically and internationally.

4. TARIFF POLICY AS FISCAL REDISTRIBUTION

The Congressional Budget Office projects that tariff manipulation could reduce the fiscal deficit by USD 2.8 trillion over a decade, but at the cost of slower GDP

growth and elevated inflation [4]. The Budget Lab at Yale University's data as of April 8, 2026, initially showed positive dynamics; however, adaptation by national governments has progressively eroded these gains [5]. The Tax Foundation documents that President Trump imposed tariffs on virtually all trading partners under IEEPA, driving the effective tariff rate to its highest level since 1947, whilst simultaneously imposing substantial additional economic burdens on American households [6].

CNN's tracking of tariff consequences reveals a consistent pattern: consumer prices rise monthly, only select categories show downward movement, and sharp tariff increases historically correlate with rising unemployment as businesses face uncertainty about how to absorb rapid cost changes. Many companies have suspended hiring plans indefinitely – a dynamic compounded by the accelerating diffusion of artificial intelligence [7]. A US-China agreement in which Washington reduced duties in exchange for Beijing lifting restrictions on rare-earth mineral exports exemplifies the tariff's secondary function as a bargaining chip rather than a structural trade corrective [8].

In aggregate, Trump's tariff policy in 2025–2026 functioned as a covert tax increase on American households. The effective tariff rate of 7.7% – the highest since 1947 – produced no significant improvement in the trade structure. The tariff instrument operated primarily as a fiscal mechanism for redistributing income from consumers to the state, rather than as a vehicle for structural trade reform. Data from 151 countries between 1963 and 2014 corroborate this finding: higher tariffs reduce output and productivity, increase unemployment, and exacerbate inequality. Studies of the 2018–2019 US tariffs confirmed that they not only failed to stimulate employment but actively harmed industry by raising input costs and provoking retaliatory measures. Tariffs are a redistributive instrument, not a growth tool.

5. MARKET SIGNALS AND THE DOLLAR SYSTEM

As of May 3, 2026, LSEG data present a surface image of stability: the US federal funds target rate stands at 3.75%, with an effective rate of 3.64%. The 10-year Treasury yield (4.372%) and the 5-year TIPS yield (1.327%) suggest that markets anticipate neither sharp inflation nor imminent recession.

The critical vulnerabilities are embedded in currency and commodity indicators. The Chinese yuan has held at 0.1464 to the dollar, with Reuters reporting that Beijing maintains a 'balanced approach', artificially stabilizing the exchange rate to prevent capital flight without liquidating its trillion-dollar reserves in US Treasuries. Gold has surged to USD 4,607.70 per ounce – near historic highs, while Brent crude has pierced USD 109 per barrel, up nearly 1%. Against the backdrop of a frozen yuan and a weakening euro, this trajectory signals that Trump's trade war has not extinguished global demand but has redirected it. Equity markets reinforce this reading: the S&P 500 has risen to 7,230.12 (+0.29%), Japan's Nikkei 225 has reached 59,513.12

(+0.38%), while the Euro STOXX 50 has stagnated at 5,881.51 and the FTSE 100 has declined to 10,363.93 (−0.14%), as Asian capital –unnerved by Chinese uncertainty and European stagnation gravitates towards the United States and its allies.

6. THE US–CHINA TRADE CONFRONTATION

In October 2025, the Sino-American trade war reignited with renewed intensity. Beijing again restricted rare-earth exports, citing national security concerns – China controls more than 90% of global processing capacity for these minerals, which are critical for electronics, automobiles, and defense technology. Trump responded immediately with 100% tariffs on all Chinese imports. Markets initially panicked before recovering after Trump posted on Truth Social that ‘everything will be fine’ and ‘America wants to help China, not hurt it.’ Analysts dubbed this ‘Taco Trade’ – Trump Always Chickens Out – underscoring the administration’s pattern of tariff threats followed by tactical retreats.

When Trump announced tariffs on Chinese imports rising to 125%, Beijing did not yield. China’s own 84% retaliatory tariffs took effect, and Foreign Ministry spokesman Lin Jian declared that the US position ‘lacks popular support and will end in failure.’ WTO Director-General Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala warned that escalation could reduce bilateral goods trade by 80% and ‘seriously undermine the global economic outlook.’ The head of China’s largest e-commerce association reported that firms selling on Amazon were preparing to raise prices or exit the US market due to what they described as an ‘unprecedented blow’ from the tariffs. The episode crystallizes the defining tension of the Trump trade strategy: the tariff threat is potent enough to extract concessions but too indiscriminate to serve as a durable instrument of structural change.

7. BIG TECH, DIGITAL SOVEREIGNTY, AND NATIONAL–CAPITALISM

The second Trump administration has redefined ‘national sovereignty’ to encompass the dominance of American Big Tech. The inauguration ceremony of January 2025 was attended in the front rows by the CEOs of Amazon, Apple, Google, Meta, OpenAI, and TikTok. Technology giants that contributed millions to inaugural funds gained access to the levers of state power to protect their global business models. The objective of tariff policy shifted from the protection of manufacturing jobs to the protection of Big Tech’s commercial interests. The European Union’s digital taxes and data-localization laws came to be treated as threats to American sovereignty, and the administration demanded that the EU, South Korea, and Brazil subordinate their national legislation to the interests of American corporations.

In response, Europe launched the EuroStack programme – an initiative to construct an autonomous technological ecosystem covering semiconductors, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence – to reduce dependence on US platforms. This dynamic

illustrates a broader structural shift: aggressive digital imperialism by Washington is accelerating European strategic autonomy rather than securing compliance.

The Intel deal encapsulates this new model of ‘national-security capitalism.’ Under the Biden-era CHIPS Act, subsidies were structured as outright grants. Under Trump, Intel received USD 8.9 billion, but in exchange was required to cede a 10% stake to the US government. While formally a passive investment – carrying no voting rights or board seats – the government’s equity stake constitutes a powerful instrument of influence over corporate strategy, effectively preventing offshoring of production.

8. INSTITUTIONAL LIMITS AND INTERNAL FRACTURES

Every manipulation has a limit. The conflict between the administration and the judiciary has emerged as a defining feature of the period: the Supreme Court has ruled tariff policy an overreach of presidential authority, while Trump has characterized the ruling as judicial overreach in turn. This confrontation generates systemic unpredictability that undermines long-term planning across both the public and private sectors.

The internal fractures within the MAGA coalition are equally significant. The public dispute and resignation of Representative Marjorie Taylor Greene from the House [11] and the resignation of Joe Kent as Director of the National Counterterrorism Center [12] both testify to a deepening intra-coalition split. These events demonstrate that aggressive and chaotic policy produces not only external opposition but internal fragmentation – a dynamic that constrains the administration’s freedom of manoeuvre.

Europe’s response has evolved from managed retrenchment to active countermercantilism. The EU is diversifying trade relations towards China, Canada, and Japan, thereby reducing its exposure to American escalation whilst simultaneously depriving Washington of the leverage that economic dependency once conferred. As Europe plays by the same rules, global fragmentation intensifies and the effectiveness of American manipulation diminishes accordingly [13].

CONCLUSION

The financial policy of the second Trump administration (2025–2026) permits three principal conclusions.

First, the phenomenon of manipulative economic policy constitutes a qualitative new mechanism of global pressure that surpasses conventional protectionism. The administration deployed tariff coercion under IEEPA, financial compulsion through dollar infrastructure, and the fusion of state power with Big Tech to subordinate world trade to American interests. The effective tariff rate of 7.7% – the highest since 1947 – functioned in practice as a covert tax on American households rather than as an instrument of structural trade correction.

Second, the study has identified the institutional and economic limits of this policy. The February 2026 Supreme Court ruling on the unconstitutionality of the IEEPA tariff regime – compelling the return of approximately USD 166 billion – exposed the ceiling of executive unilateralism and created a systemic conflict between the presidency and the judiciary. Economically, the consequences manifested as slower GDP growth, elevated inflation and unemployment, and a misallocation of resources towards less productive sectors, findings consistent with cross-country evidence from 151 states over the period 1963–2014.

Third, the policy of coercive diplomacy has provoked retaliatory mercantilism among allies and accelerated global fragmentation. The European Union’s EuroStack programme, China’s capacity to absorb tariffs of up to 125%, and the internal fracturing of the MAGA movement collectively demonstrate that the more aggressively the United States employs economic coercion, the faster the world constructs alternative institutions – reducing the effectiveness of American manipulation and amplifying global instability. Manipulative economic policy, in short, is a self-defeating strategy: it corrodes the very institutional foundations upon which American economic leadership depends.

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STAGES OF FORMATION OF THE ORGANIZATION OF TURKIC STATES

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Abstract. *This article examines the periodization of the formation of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS): from the first consultative meetings of Turkic-speaking leaders in 1992 to the reconstitution of the organization in 2021. Based on an analysis of founding documents, financial-legal mechanisms, and summit decisions, five qualitatively distinct stages of institutional evolution have been identified and characterized. The study demonstrates that each pivotal moment in the development of the OTS was accompanied by a transformation of its budgetary model, thereby confirming the hypothesis of a direct relationship between the financial sustainability of the organization and the expansion of its functional competencies. The findings contribute to the theory of new regionalism as applied to the post-Soviet space.*

Keywords: *Organization of Turkic States, OTS, Turkic integration, new regionalism, post-Soviet space, institutional evolution, financial mechanisms.*

The transformation of the global world order is prompting small and medium-sized states to develop new formats of collective positioning. The Organization of Turkic States represents one of the most illustrative examples of converting a shared linguistic-cultural foundation into an instrument of geopolitical subjectivity. Understanding the mechanisms of its growth is critically important against the backdrop of competing projects – the EAEU, the SCO, and the “Middle Corridor.”

The aim of this study is to develop an original periodization of the stages of OTS formation based on institutional and financial-legal criteria.

Hypothesis: each qualitative shift in the development of the OTS correlates with a change in the financial architecture of the organization or its legal personality; institutional evolution is discrete rather than linear in character.

The theoretical foundation of this study is the concept of new regionalism by B. Hettne and F. Söderbaum, according to which contemporary regional associations

are formed as a response of small states to the structural risks of globalization [1, p. 8]. With respect to the Turkic space, R. Aji demonstrates that Turkey chose a model of “soft leadership,” distancing itself from the sub-imperial image characteristic of Russia’s approach to the CIS [2, p. 76]. The financial-institutional dimension of the OTS is examined by A. Chuluu: his comparative analysis of the budgetary mechanisms of Turkic structures and ASEAN finds that chronic underfunding of the secretariat in 2009–2017 was the principal structural constraint on the integration agenda [3, p. 36]. The role of humanitarian institutions – TÜRKSOY and the Turkic Academy – as leading mechanisms of integration is explored by G. Mussayeva [4, p. 42]. M. Laumulín analyzes the Kazakhstani dimension of Turkic cooperation, identifying the tension between Astana’s multi-vector foreign policy and its interest in deepened Turkic integration [5, p. 13]. N. A. Nazarbayev, within the framework of the concept, linked the prospects of OTS development to the creation of a common Turkic capital market, which would grant the space a special economic status. The body of existing sources does not offer a unified periodization of the stages, which defines the niche of the present research.

The first stage, which began almost immediately after 1991 and lasted until 2000, was the emergence of political dialogue. Turkey was the first to recognize the independence of the newly formed post-Soviet states. The collapse of the Soviet Union opened a historically unprecedented opportunity for the formation of a new Turkic-speaking regional space. As early as October 1992, the first Summit of Turkic-Speaking States was held in Ankara, with the participation of the leaders of Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, and Turkey. This forum was predominantly declaratory in character: the participating states acknowledged their cultural-historical affinity but did not create any binding mechanisms. The regularity of high-level meetings established the practice of political dialogue, but the absence of a secretariat and permanent working bodies precluded the implementation of joint programs. At this stage, humanitarian discourse prevailed: issues of language, education, and historical memory were discussed [5, p. 12].

The second stage, spanning from 2001 to 2008, was marked by the institutionalization of cultural cooperation. During this period, the transition from episodic meetings to the creation of specialized structures took place. In 2008, the Parliamentary Assembly of Turkic-Speaking Countries (TURKPA) was established, signifying the appearance of the first permanent inter-parliamentary body. In parallel, TÜRKSOY – the International Organization of Turkic Culture – developed, laying the infrastructure for cultural exchange. Funding of these structures was carried out through contributions from member states; however, the burden-sharing mechanism was not unified, which generated structural imbalances. Nevertheless, it was precisely this stage that created the institutional foundation for subsequent political unification [3, p. 34].

The third and most important stage, spanning from 2009 to 2014, was the establishment of the Turkic Council. The pivotal event of the third stage was the signing of the Nakhchivan Agreement on October 3, 2009, officially founding the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States (the Turkic Council). The agreement provided for the creation of a fully functional secretariat headquartered in Istanbul, which fundamentally distinguished the Turkic Council from earlier informal formats. The organization's membership included Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkey; Uzbekistan joined later. The Charter enshrined the mechanism of rotating chairmanship, the regularity of summits, and the principle of consensus-based decision-making. The financial-institutional model provided for annual contributions from member states proportional to their GDP, which for the first time created a predictable budgetary base for the organization [1, p. 14].

The fourth stage entailed the expansion of functional competencies from 2015 to 2020. During this period, the Turkic Council consistently broadened the scope of cooperation, moving beyond the humanitarian dimension. At summits held between 2016 and 2019, decisions were adopted on the coordination of positions in international organizations, joint transport-logistics projects within the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative, and the creation of the Turkic Investment Fund. A key achievement of this stage was the formation of the Business Council and the OTS Academy, oriented toward training management personnel. During the same period, discussions on expanding the organization intensified: Hungary was granted observer status in 2018, which lent the association the character of a Eurasian forum extending beyond the post-Soviet space [4, p. 95].

The fifth stage, which began in 2021, continues to the present day. Its key event is the transformation into the Organization of Turkic States. At the Istanbul Summit on November 12, 2021, the Turkic Council was officially reorganized into the Organization of Turkic States with the adoption of a new Charter. The renaming reflected a qualitative shift in the nature of the association: from a consultative council format to a fully fledged international organization with a broader agenda. Uzbekistan joined the OTS as a full member, while Turkmenistan and Hungary received observer status. The updated Charter enshrined the institution of the Secretary General, expanded the mandate of the secretariat, and introduced a mechanism for emergency consultations. The adoption of the "Turkic Vision 2040" defined the organization's long-term priorities in the areas of digitalization, green economy, and education [2, p. 143].

A comparative analysis of the stages of OTS formation reveals stable patterns characterizing the institutional dynamics of the organization. First, a clear correlation is evident between external geopolitical impulses and the intensification of integration efforts. The collapse of the USSR, the events of September 11, 2001, the shift in Turkey's foreign policy course under the Erdoğan government, and the

increase in instability in the post-Soviet space in 2014–2015 successively served as catalysts for deepening cooperation in the Turkic space [7, p. 45]. Second, each transition from one stage to the next was accompanied not merely by organizational transformations, but by a fundamental reappraisal of the goals and objectives of the association: from a cultural-linguistic club to a fully fledged multifunctional international organization with an economic and political agenda.

An important aspect of studying the institutional evolution of the OTS is the analysis of budgetary-financial mechanisms as indicators of the organization's maturity. At the first stage (1992–2000), the costs of organizing summits were covered entirely by the host party, which created an informal dependence of the agenda on the current interests of the presiding state [3, p. 36]. The introduction of a unified system of contributions within the framework of the Turkic Council (2009) provided the secretariat with structural independence, although, as A. Chuluu notes, chronic underfunding in 2009–2017 continued to limit the functional potential of the organization [3, p. 38]. Only with the creation of the Turkic Investment Fund and the transition to mandatory auditing did the OTS budgetary model approach the standards of mature international structures. This trend fundamentally distinguishes the Organization of Turkic States from other post-Soviet international and regional structural associations, since financial contributions from participants have typically been a source of conflict in such bodies.

The role of Kazakhstan in the formation process of the OTS deserves special attention. Astana consistently supported the institutional formalization of Turkic cooperation while simultaneously maintaining a multi-vector foreign policy course. The tension between participation in the EAEU and deepened Turkic integration was resolved by positioning the OTS as a complementary rather than competing format [5, p. 14]. The concept of the “Middle State,” developed by Kazakhstani diplomacy, organically incorporated OTS membership into a broader strategy of balancing between major regional players. Speaking at the Baku Summit of the Turkic Council in 2010, N. A. Nazarbayev presented the prospect of creating a common Turkic capital market as an instrument for reducing member states' dependence on external financing [6, p. 7]. This initiative became one of the conceptual foundations of the future Turkic Investment Fund.

It is also necessary to consider the external challenges and constraints faced by the OTS at various stages of its development. Competition with alternative integration formats – primarily the CIS, and subsequently the EAEU and the SCO – required the organization to clearly position its functional niche. The response was an emphasis on the humanitarian, educational, and cultural dimension, in which the OTS objectively possessed comparative advantages over economically-oriented associations [1, p. 14]. The expansion to include non-Turkic observers (Hungary) signaled a strategic pivot: the organization began cultivating an image not as an

ethnic-cultural club but as a geo-economic platform united by a common transit interest within the “Middle Corridor.” This transformation of identity is confirmed by the adoption of “Turkic Vision 2040,” focused on the digital economy, green energy, and transport-logistics integration [9, p. 23].

Reference to the theory of new regionalism allows the evolution of the OTS to be interpreted in a broader theoretical context. B. Hettne and F. Söderbaum distinguish between “old regionalism,” oriented toward top-down economic integration modeled on the EU, and “new regionalism,” forming from the bottom up under the influence of local actors, cultural identities, and transnational networks [1, p. 8]. The OTS represents an illustrative example of precisely the second model: institutional construction was preceded by cultural-humanitarian infrastructure (TÜRKSOY, the Turkic Academy), and economic integration remained declaratory until the fifth stage. G. B. Mussayeva convincingly demonstrates that humanitarian institutions functioned as a kind of “advance payment instrument” of integration, forming social capital and expert networks that subsequently ensured the viability of political agreements [4, p. 88].

The prospects for the further development of the OTS are determined by several key variables. The first is the degree of implementation of “Turkic Vision 2040” with regard to digital infrastructure and green energy, which will require a substantial increase in the organization’s investment capacity [9, p. 27]. The second is the dynamics of relations with major powers: the intensification of geopolitical tensions between Russia and the West has highlighted the transit potential of the Turkic space, but simultaneously creates risks of differentiated integration within the OTS. The third is the question of full membership for Turkmenistan, whose neutrality has traditionally constrained its participation in multilateral formats; the transition to observer status in 2021 may be interpreted as a first step toward deeper engagement [7, p. 52]. Finally, the institutional maturity of the OTS will be tested by the organization’s capacity to reconcile the interests of member states amid persisting bilateral contradictions, particularly between Azerbaijan and several partners over questions of transport corridors [8, p. 118].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the study confirmed the hypothesis regarding the discrete, step-like character of the OTS’s institutional development. Each of the five identified stages is separated from the previous one by a trigger event that changes the financial-legal nature of the organization: the transition from bilateral Turkish contributions to unified proportional assessments, then to the creation of an investment fund, and finally to the introduction of mandatory auditing. A stable correlation is evident between the maturity of the budgetary mechanism and the expansion of functional competencies, which is consistent with the theory of new regionalism. The evolution of membership – from a narrow club of post-Soviet Turkic-speaking states to an organization with a non-Turkic observer – attests to the

gradual transition of the OTS from an ethnic-cultural to a geo-economic identity. A promising direction for further research is a comparative analysis of the budgetary effectiveness of the OTS and ASEAN.

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DEMOCRACY AS A HUMAN RIGHT: THE RIGHT TO RESISTANCE AS THE ULTIMATE GUARANTEE OF DEMOCRATIC ORDER

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Abstract: *This article examines the crisis of institutionalist approaches to democratic protection in the context of authoritarian transitions of the early 21st century. The article argues that the predominant state-centric model of democratic self-defence – rooted in the separation of powers, constitutional courts, and ‘militant democracy’ – is inherently vulnerable to capture by the very actors it was designed to restrain. Drawing on Arendt’s concept of political mass formation, Rawls’s lexical priority of basic liberties, and the republican tradition of non-domination, the article proposes a paradigm shift: democracy should be understood not merely as a form of government but as an individual human right – specifically, as a meta-right that constitutes the condition of possibility for all other rights. Within this framework, the right to resistance emerges as the ultimate, non-institutionalisable guarantee of democratic order – the only democratic right that cannot be nationalised and turned against the citizens it is meant to protect.*

Keywords: *democracy, human rights, right to resistance, authoritarian transition, militant democracy, political rights, meta-rights, Hannah Arendt, John Rawls, natural law, popular sovereignty, rule of law.*

Today, entire regions of the world are living through protracted authoritarian transitions whose active phase became pronounced after 2022 [1]. Governments are acquiring an increasingly fascist character in the original sense of the term [2]: statism intensifies, states systematically expand the sphere of intervention, trading citizens’ political freedoms for promises of security in the face of real and imagined threats [3]. This is most clearly illustrated by the second term of Donald Trump, when the United States – long the exemplary liberal democracy – demonstrated

how rapidly a democratic regime can drift towards personalist authoritarianism while formally preserving its institutions.

The question ‘how do we protect democracy?’ has remained central to constitutional law and political theory for at least two centuries. Institutionalisation, separation of powers, independent courts, and the concept of ‘militant democracy’ [4] were proposed in response. Yet empirical experience shows that even advanced systems of checks and balances do not guarantee protection against usurpation, and the very legislation on extremism designed to defend democracy has become a key instrument for suppressing opposition in hybrid regimes – revealing the central paradox: means of defending democracy, concentrated in the hands of the state, are easily converted into tools for dismantling it [5; 6].

1. THE LIMITS OF INSTITUTIONALISM

Until the early twenty-first century, an almost consensual thesis prevailed: the institutionalisation of power is the primary means of preventing its usurpation [7]. Separation of powers, independent courts, federal structure, constitutional review – all were conceived as a reliable ‘architecture of guarantee’ [8]. Experience shows, however, that even ‘well-constructed’ institutions cannot withstand the targeted pressure of political actors interested in concentrating power [9].

The common denominator of most institutionalist projects can be expressed as: ‘smart people must decide how the population is to live’ – a technocratic paternalism in which the citizen is assigned the role of passive addressee of decisions taken by ‘responsible elites.’ The long-term result is the formation of the very ‘mass’ Arendt described [10]: an aggregated totality of atomised, politically passive individuals deprived of horizontal ties and the habit of independent judgement – ideal material for totalitarian projects. In this lies the vicious circle: the more the state ‘protects’ citizens from politics, the easier it becomes, should the course change, to use those same instruments to suppress freedoms.

2. DEMOCRACY AS A HUMAN RIGHT

Escaping this vicious circle requires a shift of optics – seeking the guarantees of democracy not in the plane of the state, but in the plane of the individual. Such a turn requires substantial theoretical effort, because it demands treating democracy not only as a form of government, but as a human right: the right of each person to participate in governing the political community of which he is a member.

Recognising democracy as a human right immediately raises the question of its place in the hierarchy of rights: is it not derivative of more fundamental rights, above all economic ones? The answer to this question helps us understand whether a political right can be exchanged for economic security.

Traditional debates about the priority of economic or political rights often rested on the Marxist thesis of the primacy of the economic base. Yet this argument does not explain why economically prosperous societies can move away from democracy,

while economically vulnerable ones achieve democratisation – as contemporary studies of new-type dictatorships confirm [3]. Hayek argued, conversely, that economic freedom forms the foundation of political freedom [11]; his observation that the loss of economic freedoms has historically accompanied the loss of political ones is empirically correct, but converting this correlation into causation places economic rights above political ones, conceiving the citizen first and foremost as a consumer.

Such a hierarchical construction is fraught with a dangerous substitution: political freedom turns out to be understood as a delivery service for economic well-being. In this logic, relinquishing political rights in exchange for economic stability presents itself as a permissible bargain: the citizen gives up being Aristotle's political animal (*ζῷον πολιτικόν*) [12], in order to become Arendt's animal laborans [13]. But as the practice of authoritarian modernisations shows, such a bargain resembles the biblical story of Esau: political birthright is exchanged for the lentil stew of economic growth. At a certain stage, such a regime reaches a 'glass ceiling' of development, running into the absence of legal protection and predictability [14].

If, however, one takes seriously the thesis of democracy as a human right, such a bargain becomes not merely dangerous, but logically inadmissible: one cannot 'exchange' one human right for another – still less surrender a right that constitutes the condition of possibility of all others. This is precisely where John Rawls leads, asserting the lexical priority of the complex of basic liberties over distributive principles: basic political freedoms cannot be legitimately restricted for the sake of any economic gains [15]. He thereby rules out the very bargain that lies at the foundation of the authoritarian social contract: the voluntary renunciation of political freedom in exchange for material well-being.

3. POLITICAL RIGHTS AS META-RIGHTS

In treating democracy as an individual right, we inevitably arrive at the question of the status of political rights within the system of human rights. Traditional catalogues – civil, political, socio-economic, cultural rights – are arranged, as it were, horizontally. However, the experience of totalitarianism and mass statelessness in the twentieth century forces the assertion that political rights occupy a special, meta-juridical position.

Hannah Arendt formulates this through the concept of the 'right to have rights' [16] – the right to belong to an organised political community within which the judgements and actions of the individual have meaning. The fate of stateless persons showed that human rights as abstract declarations do not function in the absence of political belonging: 'the world found nothing sacred in the abstract nakedness of being human' [10]. Without the status of citizen, without inclusion in the political body, the individual is deprived not only of specific rights, but of the very mechanism for claiming and defending them.

From this flows an understanding of political rights as the condition of possibility of all other rights. These rights are not one category alongside others, but that which makes the language of rights meaningful at all. Ronald Dworkin, calling rights ‘political trumps’ of the individual against the collectivist aspirations of the state, suggests an apt metaphor: political rights are a ‘trump for playing trumps’ – the right to demand that all other rights be taken seriously [17].

The republican tradition of freedom as non-domination reinforces this thesis: freedom is not merely the absence of actual interference, but the absence of dependence on the arbitrary will of another. Even if an authoritarian ruler generously provides economic goods, the citizen remains unfree, since his well-being exists only so long as this corresponds to the ruler’s will. Renouncing political rights in favour of economic gains transforms the citizen not into a free consumer – as authoritarian leaders attempt to present it [3] – but into a dependent subject, a slave of a gracious master.

In this perspective, political rights emerge as a new *primus inter pares* in the system of human rights. They are first not because the others are secondary, but because without them the others cannot be sustainably realised. Freedom of speech, freedom of association, electoral rights, the right to participate in decision-making – these are not merely separate freedoms, but the structural framework that prevents democracy from being alienated from its bearer: the citizen.

4. THE RIGHT TO RESISTANCE AS ULTIMA RATIO

Recognising political rights as meta-rights raises a question that cannot be avoided: who guarantees the meta-rights themselves? Traditional constitutional doctrine answers: independent courts, constitutional review, international protection mechanisms. But it is precisely here that the systemic limitation of the state-centric model is exposed: these guarantees are themselves institutions, and institutions can be captured, reoriented, or paralysed from within. As Levitsky and Ziblatt observe, democracy dies not through military coup but through the gradual subordination of institutional guarantees to a single will [18]. This means that political meta-rights require a guarantee of a different kind – one structurally independent of the institutional system.

The constitutional tradition of the right to resistance offers precisely such a guarantee. Its intellectual lineage runs from the Monarchomachs of the sixteenth century through Locke’s *Second Treatise* to contemporary constitutional entrenchments. Locke’s formulation remains precise after three and a half centuries: entering the social contract, people do not alienate the natural right to defend themselves from destruction – they delegate its exercise to the state only so long as the state acts in accordance with its purpose [19]. When the state betrays that purpose, the delegation is annulled and the right returns to the individual.

This natural-law foundation distinguishes the right to resistance from all other political rights. Freedom of speech, freedom of association, and electoral rights are

realised within and through the institutional system – they require its infrastructure and can therefore be constrained by whoever controls it. The right to resistance is structurally different: it is not generated by the constitution but may be recognised by it. Where it is constitutionally entrenched – as in Article 20(4) of the Basic Law of the Federal Republic of Germany [20], which explicitly grants citizens the right to resist any person seeking to abolish the constitutional order – this represents the state’s acknowledgement of its own derivativeness from popular sovereignty. The constitution honestly admits that if the state exceeds its mandate, citizens are entitled to restore the constitutional order.

The chain of political rights, arranged in order of increasing radicalism, illuminates why the right to resistance occupies the final position. Freedom of speech allows criticism of power to be articulated; freedom of association allows that criticism to be organised into collective action; electoral rights allow the peaceful replacement of power through procedure. Only when all these links have been exhausted does the right to resistance provide the citizen with a constitutional basis for action beyond institutional forms, appealing directly to popular sovereignty. It is therefore not a licence for arbitrary disobedience but a last resort – the constitutional restitution of political subjectivity.

This architecture reveals the irreducible distinction from Loewenstein’s ‘militant democracy.’ Loewenstein assigned the role of democracy’s defender to the state; practice demonstrated that the instruments he proposed were subsequently appropriated by regimes with authoritarian tendencies and turned against civil society and opposition. The right to resistance is not susceptible to this inversion: it belongs not to the state apparatus but to each citizen as the original sovereign, and it is therefore the only democratic guarantee that cannot be nationalised. In this lies its authentic significance as *ultima ratio* – the final argument the citizen retains even when all institutional mechanisms have been exhausted.

CONCLUSION

The authoritarian transit of the early twenty-first century has revealed the limits of the traditional constitutional faith in institutionalisation as a universal means of protecting democracy. Separation of powers, independent courts, bans on extremism, and ‘militant democracy’ in the state-centric version have shown their ambivalence: under conditions of political drift they serve the authoritarian project as readily as the democratic one. The common premise of these models – the notion that democracy is protected by the state, while citizens serve as objects of this protection – reproduces the infantilisation of the population and prepares the ground for the transformation of citizens into a mass.

A shift in optics towards treating democracy as an individual right makes it possible to reorder the emphases. Political rights in this approach appear not as one section of human rights, but as a meta-right – the condition of possibility of all

other rights and the principal barrier against the transformation of the citizen into an object of governance. It is political rights that retain the human being in the status of ζῶον πολιτικόν, rather than merely animal laborans, and it is through them that democracy remains rooted in the individual, not in an abstract state.

Within this framework, the right to resistance acquires new significance. Since all institutional guarantees can be step by step neutralised from within, the ultimate guarantee remains the right of the citizen – as the bearer of democracy – not to submit to power that has lost legitimacy, and to actively resist usurpation. The right to resistance, being an individual right, is capable of fulfilling the protective function with which state mechanisms failed: it not only asserts the final sovereignty of the people, but is structurally incompatible with the model of the infantile citizen. In the final analysis, the right to resistance is the constitutional right to the restitution of political subjectivity – the return to the person of that which the state never had the right to take from him. In this lies the authentic meaning of *primus inter pares*: the citizen remains the ultimate authority in the protection of both his rights and democracy itself.

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PREREQUISITES FOR THE FORMATION OF THE SYSTEM OF STATE-LEGAL REGULATION OF FOREST RELATIONS AFTER THE OCTOBER REVOLUTION OF 1917

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Abstract. *Any phenomenon of social life in its historical context should be considered primarily by analyzing the conditions that prevailed in society at a particular time. It is not enough to determine the content of what happened; a complete analysis means identifying the causes (a combination of actual conditions) that formed and served as the basis (prerequisite) for the development of the phenomenon under consideration. The formation of the Soviet state spans from October 1917 to 1920 (1922). Speaking directly about the conditions for the formation of the system of state and legal regulation of forest relations during the formation of the Soviet state, it should be divided into the following areas: political, economic, social, and legal conditions. The article provides an analysis of the political and legal steps taken in the first years of Soviet power in Russia to regulate the protection of forest resources, specifically from the perspective of the socialization of natural resources, which was undoubtedly important for the young Soviet state.*

Keywords: *state-legal protection of forest resources, agricultural issues, state ownership of land and natural resources.*

For the historical memory of Russia, the year 1917 remains a period marked by the most profound upheavals, turmoil, grief, and rapid transformations: the abdication of Tsar Nicholas II, a devastatingly bloody war, economic and political crises, the exacerbation of contradictions within society itself, a surge of national movements, and so forth.

Overall, 1917 became a certain culmination, an assessment of the balance of political forces in the country: ‘The apotheosis of multi-party system was the year 1917.’ The elections to the Constituent Assembly, on the one hand, reflected the popularity and authority ratings of the main political parties, and on the other hand

served as the basis for transforming the political confrontation with the Bolsheviks into an armed struggle against Soviet power¹.

Having firmly established itself at the ‘helm of power,’ the Bolshevik party, as the most progressive and effective force at that stage of historical societal development, gradually began to realize its vision of social life and to shape its system of governance, in which the issue of natural resource distribution occupied a significant position.

It should be noted here that none of the political parties differentiated in their programs the provisions concerning the system of regulation of natural resources by their specific types (land, water, subsoil, forest). With primary emphasis on the agrarian issue, the forest (along with subsoil and water) was listed merely as part of an enumeration, which objectively reflects both the physical and legal dimensions of the matter.

Taking into account the specificity of the forest as an object of legal regulation (its inseparable connection to land), as well as the priority assigned to the land question in the programs of political parties engaged in the political struggle in 1917, it is possible to formulate and analyze the principal directions of political thought concerning the establishment of a state-legal system for regulating natural resources in general, and forests in particular.

The agrarian question became an obstacle on which all liberal parties, without exception, stumbled. Although in their political programs and in the legislative drafts submitted to the State Duma, these political groups proposed radical measures to address the pressing issue facing Russian society.

The idea of compulsory expropriation (redemption) of private lands was supported by the majority of liberal parties, which included only the specifics of the land alienation process in their programs.

Thus, in the program of the party “Union of October 17,” one of the clauses in the section “On the Peasant and Land Question” provided for the necessity of enacting a law permitting the alienation of the land surface independently of its subsoil².

The land allotment project proposed by the Octobrists was underpinned by a certain theoretical aspect, namely the prevailing scientific understanding at the time concerning the legal regime governing land and its subsoil as an integral part thereof.

¹ Dobrovolsky A. V. *The Socialist-Revolutionary Party in Power and in Opposition, 1917–1923 (Based on Materials from Siberia)*. Doctoral Dissertation in Historical Sciences. Novosibirsk, 2004. p. 3.

² A bill was introduced in the First State Duma by a group of Progressives which contained such a provision / For details, see the book: Aronov D. V. *Legislative Activity of Russian Liberals in the State Duma: 1906–1917* / Doctoral Dissertation in Juridical Sciences. Moscow, 2005. p. 423.

For example, L. A. Kasso, in the textbook ‘Russian Land Law,’ offers an analysis of the principal provisions of both Western and domestic legislation regarding the owner’s rights to the use of the land’s subsoil, the possibility of subsoil extraction by third parties, and related issues. It is presumed that recognizing an exclusive or even preferential right to subsoil resources in favor of surface landowners would be inconsistent with their economic position and technical capacity, and that, conversely, the arbitrariness of these individuals and the insufficiency of their resources could hinder the desirable initiative of external entrepreneurs, thereby depriving society of valuable benefits¹.

The Republican Democratic Party, founded on April 9, 1917, advocated for the establishment of a state land fund by transferring to it, without compensation, ‘state, allotment, cabinet, and monastic lands’ (clause 7 of the Republican Democratic Party Program) to be used for the allocation to land-poor and landless populations (clause 8 of the Republican Democratic Party Program). It was also necessary to establish by law the maximum limit of private land ownership so that the surplus would be subject to mandatory expropriation with compensation (clause 9 of the Program of the Republican Democratic Party)².

Thus, right-wing and centrist parties supported the resolution of the land issue primarily by allotting land to peasants through amendments (reforms) to the existing legislation, or through the requisition of land with payment by the state, while mandatorily preserving the existing forms of ownership. The rationale for the legislative proposals put forward by the liberal parties consisted in a clear definition of the issue of priority between public and private interests.

Loyalty to the incumbent authorities, weak popular support, and the absence of effective measures to resolve the prevailing situation resulted in 1917 becoming a conclusive year for the aforementioned political forces.

Long before the events of 1917, the Social-Revolutionary Party had articulated the fundamental principles of their agrarian policy (which also encompassed issues related to the use of subsoil resources, water, forests, etc.), as reflected in draft laws concerning the basic provisions of land legislation.

Subsequently, the Bolsheviks revised many of their demands, and the majority of the aforementioned were implemented. Meanwhile, the principal unifying concept became ‘socialization.’

The Bolshevik Party (RSDLP (b)) (V. I. Lenin, G. V. Plekhanov, L. B. Kamenev, L. D. Trotsky), based on the programmatic demands adopted at the 2nd Congress in Geneva, actively pursued the seizure of power in 1917, simultaneously advancing

¹ Kasso L. A. Russian Land Law. p. 83.

² Collection of Programs of Russian Political Parties. Petrograd, 1917. p. 16.

populist slogans calling for the expropriation of all lands and recognizing only one subject of property rights over land and natural resources – the people.

Having gained the support of a large part of the population, as well as workers and the military, the Bolsheviks carried out the October Revolution, ‘...which became possible as a result of three main factors: the rapid escalation of spontaneous popular protest and grassroots initiatives in addressing the most urgent, vital problems – land, peace, bread, etc... and the persistent efforts of the Bolsheviks to maximally expand the popular movement.’¹

The pinnacle of the struggle for power in Russia was the dispersal of the Constituent Assembly by the Bolsheviks, which became not only the starting point for the establishment of Bolshevik power but also for the gradual withdrawal of other participants from the political arena.

By exploiting the mistakes of their opponents, the Bolshevik party persistently and relentlessly secured its position in power. By implementing radical measures, the Bolsheviks effectively abolished private property and nationalized all natural resources, thereby rapidly establishing the foundation that enabled further transformations along the path they had devised. The result will be the establishment of a new system of state-legal regulation of the circulation of natural wealth in Russia.

The decrees became the concrete expression of the Bolsheviks’ program of political transformations.

«The contradictions of the fundamental political issues were so profound that they could not be overcome by conventional bourgeois-reformist methods... Therefore, the entire course of subsequent events required political parties and their leaders to make new bold strategic decisions on acute and complex problems.»²

In characterizing the political prerequisites for the establishment of a new system for the distribution of forest wealth in Russia, we assert the position that it was precisely politics that constituted the foundation of the transformations themselves; in other words, causes grounded specifically in the political sphere acted as a catalyst for subsequent changes in the entirety of Russian societal life. This conclusion is based on the understanding that the absence of any political will among the principal political forces in Russia in 1917 led to the resolution of the country’s entrenched problems through the seizure of power by the Bolsheviks.

However, in this very struggle for power, the Bolsheviks also endured pressure from other political forces (parties of the Social Revolutionaries, Mensheviks, and Cadets).

The emerging process of establishing a new mechanism of societal governance in Russia, characterized by intense political struggle among the main political

¹ History of Russia. 20th Century. Moscow, 1997. pp. 166–173.

² Kostin V. I. National History. Nizhny Novgorod, 2005. pp. 36–37.

movements, ultimately culminated in the creation of a one-party political system, the establishment of ideology as the fundamental program of action, the elimination of opposition, the declaration of minimal democratic rights and freedoms, and the assignment to the state of exclusive ownership rights over natural resources (land, forest, mineral deposits, waters, etc.).

The causes of the political events in the country in 1917 were a set of pressing developmental issues facing the nation. An additional and no less significant impetus for the epochal events was the acute economic crisis, intensified by circumstances such as Russia's participation in the war, which demanded enormous resources for conducting military operations and resulted in losses not only quantitative (including reductions in territory, population, and financial resources) but also qualitative (manifested through underdeveloped sectors, a multi-structured economy, and contradictions within the developmental processes of individual industries).

It is noteworthy that a significant portion of forest areas before the political events of 1917 belonged to private individuals. In most governorates, 30–40% or more of the total forest areas were privately owned (Bryansk, Vitebsk, Gomel, Yaroslavl, Tver, Smolensk, Penza, Nizhny Novgorod, Ryazan, etc.)¹.

Subsequently, due to the nationalization of all forest resources and the abolition of private ownership, forests became one of the most important sources of state budget revenue for a state undergoing consolidation.

Economic conditions will fundamentally affect the pace of growing discontent among the population, which will inevitably result in the political demands of specific social strata.

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THE IDEA OF NATURAL RESOURCES NATIONALIZATION AS A FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLE OF THE BOLSHEVIKS' STATE POLICY

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Abstract: *The main and most important milestones in regulating the issue of the socialization of natural resources for the Bolsheviks were the social prerequisites for building a system of state-legal regulation of the circulation of forest resources in Russia. Objectively, the forest has always been of great importance to the Russian population, and it remains so to this day. This fact has never lost its significance, which is why the issue of the social conditions for building a system of state-legal regulation of the circulation of forest resources is so important. The article analyzes the social structure of Russian society and the impact of these social processes on the consolidation of state ownership of natural resources, including forests.*

Keywords: *proletariat, peasantry, private land ownership, nationalization of land and forests.*

In the social structure of Russia in 1917, the peasantry constituted the predominant segment, whose demands centered on the possibility of land allocation and the development of their agricultural economy. At the same time, the forest was the primary source of heat energy and secondary uses (gathering, construction materials, etc.).

However, the peasants' right to utilize forest areas was restricted due to statutorily established limitations (forest servitudes). Thus, for example, only state peasants and members of the clergy were permitted access to state-owned forests.

The nobility, as a privileged class, was to be abolished, along with the right to private ownership of forests. Significant forest estates were to be transferred into state ownership.

The bourgeoisie, as a whole, behaved rather passively and, unable to find the internal strength for active resistance, ceased to exist: 'The October Revolution

faced a relatively weak, poorly organized, and politically inexperienced adversary in the form of the Russian bourgeoisie.¹

The main driving force at this time becomes the proletariat, whose 'share' in the total population amounted to about 10% by 1917: 'The fact of the change of power in October 1917 had the most immediate impact on the condition of Russian workers.' They particularly benefited in terms of an increase in their social status. The Bolsheviks proclaimed the workers as the 'class-hegemon,' the ruling class with all the consequent political, economic, and social ramifications^{2,3}

However, not only peasants and the proletariat were active participants in the struggle for power and in demanding the resolution of the problems confronting society. These include the Cossacks:

Representing a distinct social group, the Cossacks were actively engaged in the political life of the country. Accordingly, the Cossacks advanced the following programmatic demands concerning the agrarian issue:

1. All agricultural lands in the Russian Republic must belong exclusively to the working peasant population.

2. ...the note indicated that all lands required for the resettlement fund, as well as forests and waters of national importance, remain under state ownership.

3. Private property lands exceeding the size of working farm households are expropriated on the grounds developed by regional autonomous legislative assemblies. The size is established by regional legislative bodies.

4. The distribution of the land fund among the working rural population, as well as the procedure and grounds for land use, are established by regional self-government bodies... The specific resolution of the issue in the Don region states: "All military reserve and yurta stan lands with their subsoil, forests, and other estates are the inalienable property of the entire military Cossack community."⁴

Thus, the Cossacks, while recognizing various forms of ownership in their program, primarily devoted attention to measures necessary for the development of the economy (agriculture).

¹ History of the VKP(b), 1938, pp. 199–204.

² P. V. Volobuev. *The Proletariat and the Bourgeoisie of Russia in 1917*. Social History. Moscow, 2004, p. 65.

³ D. O. Chudakov. *Workers of Russia and the Formation of Soviet Statehood (Causes, Dynamics, and Methods of Overcoming Worker Protest)*. Late 1917–1918. Dissertation for Doctor of Historical Sciences. Moscow, 2006, p. 88.

⁴ O. B. German. *Legal Status of the Cossacks and Peasantry of the Southeast of European Russia in 1861–1920*. Abstract of Doctor of Legal Sciences Dissertation. Krasnodar, 2004, pp. 435–436.

It is necessary to note that the events of 1917 also provoked a wave of national manifestations, during which demands concerning the regulation of the circulation of natural resources were advanced.

Thus, ‘under the conditions of a broad democratic surge associated with the February Revolution of 1917, the formation and development of the Bashkir national movement took place’ ... ‘The agrarian program of the Bashkir national movement was most fully reflected in the decisions of the Bashkir Kurultai (Constituent Assembly), held in December 1917 in Orenburg.’ The Kurultai’s decision on the land question combined three principles: land, forests, and mineral resources belong to the Bashkir people; lands unjustly confiscated during the era of the ‘plundering of Bashkir lands’ must be returned to the people; lands must be distributed among the peasants of Bashkortostan regardless of gender, age, nationality, or religion¹.

The adopted act dealt a severe blow to the Bashkir households of the mountainous forest regions, for whom forest trades constituted an important source of livelihood. If peasants previously used the forest free of charge, it was now granted to them for a certain fee. Subsequently, this circumstance became one of the primary causes of the mass decline of the Bashkir population in the mountainous forest regions².

Thus, based on the example of the national movement in Bashkiria, it can be asserted that not only political parties proposed and constructed their own models and frameworks for the system of natural wealth distribution, but also individual national groups.

It is important to emphasize the position of forestry specialists on the changes taking place in the management of the circulation of forest resources, as articulated in the plenary reports “Nationalization of Forests in Russia” and “State Forests and Their Use in the Land Reform,” delivered at the September 1917 Congress of the All-Russian Union of Foresters³.

A thorough analysis and examination of the speeches and reports presented at the Congress not only allow for the identification of the problems existing in the forestry sector at that time but also elucidate the avenues (means) for addressing the resulting situation.

¹ The National-State Structure of Bashkortostan (1917–1925). Documents and Materials. Ufa: Kitap, 2002. Vol. 1. Pp. 236–283.

² Karimov U. Ya. The Agrarian Question in Bashkiria and the Socio-Economic Condition of the Bashkir Population (late 19th century – early 20th century) / Dissertation for the Degree of Candidate of Historical Sciences. Ufa, 2009. P. 126.

³ Frolova O. V. Legal Regulation of the Protection Regime and Use of Forest Resources in Russia, 18th – Early 20th Century / Dissertation for the Degree of Candidate of Juridical Sciences. St. Petersburg, 2002. P. 107.

At the very beginning of the meeting, the Chairman of the Provisional Council of the Union of Foresters, the renowned and distinguished scientist – forester Georgy Fedorovich Morozov – outlined the topics: “1. Recognition of forests as state property; 2) the broad and systematic satisfaction of the local population’s needs in the forest; 3) the service of foresters to the forest under the slogan “Protect the Forest”; and 4) ... unity for the benefit of the native cause based on meeting the pressing needs of the foresters themselves.”¹

At the Foresters’ Congress, there were representatives of political parties (for example, A. V. Peshekhonov, a representative of the People’s Socialist Party), the Minister of Agriculture of the Provisional Government, A. I. Shingarev, leading foresters (N. I. Faleev, G. F. Morozov, N. I. Paevsky, etc.), scientists, students, forest rangers, and others.

The central issue was that of nationalization. During the proceedings, the participants expressed differing assessments regarding the possibility of implementing such a measure.

Thus, Professor Kaufman A. A., endorsing the idea of transferring ownership rights to the state over all forests (both private and state-owned), noted that the method of nationalization should be expropriation with compensation, the amount of which was determined based on the condition of the forest: ‘...for example, forests depleted by their owners almost to complete disappearance should be expropriated free of charge.’²

The representative of the Popular Socialist Party, Peshekhonov A. V., in his report emphasized the priority of ensuring the population’s provision with forest resources and the necessity of legally establishing a classification of forests into state, regional, and communal categories.

Professor L. Khodsky voiced his reservations regarding the expediency of such a swift reform of the forestry sector, noting that ‘the nationalization of lands and forests touches upon all elements of the modern capitalist system.’³

Of particular significance is the fact that most of the reports presented at the Foresters’ Congress in 1917 emphasized the mandatory convening of the Constituent Assembly as the legitimate authority vested exclusively with the competence to decide on the establishment of the system governing the management of forest resources.

This was discussed by A. I. Shingarev, N. I. Faleev, B. K. Ladygin, and others.

The outcome of the Foresters’ Congress was the adoption of resolutions on various issues (on current problems, on the nationalization of forests and unsuitable

¹ On the All-Russian Congress of Foresters and Forest Technicians, held in Petrograd from April 28 to May 2, 1917. Petrograd, 1917. pp. 3–4.

² *Ibid.*, p. 5.

³ *Ibid.*, p. 8.

lands, on the adoption of the statute of the Union of Foresters, on forest supply, among others).

Concerning current issues, it was noted that there exists a ‘widespread opinion regarding the idea of transferring forests to society or the state, granting the population the right to dispose of or control forest management,’ whereas nationalization as a means of implementing these ideas is understood as ‘the recognition of all forests as state property and their exploitation in the interests of the population with its direct participation.’¹

The implementation of nationalization falls within the exclusive competence of the Constituent Assembly. To this end, the congress resolved in a resolution on the necessity of involving representatives of the Union of Foresters and Forest Technicians in the district, provincial, and central land committees, in the Council of Workers’ and Peasants’ Deputies, and in local public committees.

Noting the contradictions in the existing (at that time not yet repealed) legislation, it was established that persons could act at their own discretion in cases of urgency regarding the resolution of issues related to the provision (allocation of forest resources to the population) and the presence of legal conflicts.

Attention was drawn to the urgent necessity of bringing forest legislation into proper order – that is, abolishing mutually contradictory laws, some of which often dated back to the previous century, as well as adopting new legislation – particularly with regard to the distribution of forest resources to the population.

The participation of foresters in developing the question of forest nationalization was proposed, involving ‘close cooperation between forestry professionals and local as well as central peasant organizations, the Council of Workers’, Soldiers’, and Peasants’ Deputies, zemstvos, municipal institutions, and the active involvement of foresters and forestry technicians in the work of Land Committees at both the local and central levels.’²

The declaration, resulting from the work of the All-Russian Congress of Foresters and Forestry Technicians, was presented on May 9, 1917, to the Minister of Agriculture, V. M. Chernov. In his response, the Minister emphasized that the coalition Provisional Government’s objective was to recognize forests as a national property, with the primary task in this regard being the limitation of rights to dispose of private forests³.

The materials from the 1917 foresters’ congress session comprehensively reveal the forestry sector’s problems of that period: lack of clarity and systematization in legislation, poor organization of forest product distribution to the population,

¹ Ibid., p. 9.

² Ibid., p. 9.

³ Ibid., p. 23.

low levels of professional training among forestry specialists, measures to combat poaching, reform of the forest guard system, and so forth. According to the Union of Foresters, the foundation and basis for constructing a new, qualitatively different system of forest wealth distribution was to be nationalization – namely, the recognition of all forests as state property and their exploitation in the interests of the population, involving direct participation of society.

Thus, society, unsettled by the political events of 1917, distinctly responded to the ongoing developments by distinguishing from its substantive core new ideas, goals, slogans, and proposals.

Indeed, 1917 became the starting point for an increasing interest in forest policy, wherein the very proclamation of exclusive state ownership over forests signified a ‘transformation in the system of forest management and the formation of a new forest policy.’¹

The legal conditions for the formation of the system of state and legal regulation of forest relations are characterized primarily by the abolition of tsarist legislation, the simultaneous declarative consolidation of fundamental principles, and, consequently, the gradual formation of a new legal framework, including the introduction of new laws.

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FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO AN INCREASE IN MOTIVATION FOR TEACHING AMONG VETERANS OF THE SVO¹

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Abstract. *Under conditions of increased social and psychological pressure on veterans of the Special Military Operation (SVO), the preservation and restoration of professional identity constitute key objectives of social reintegration. This article is dedicated to the analysis of factors contributing to an increase in motivation for pedagogical activity among veterans of the SVO – a group possessing unique experience in discipline, responsibility, and leadership. Based on the research conducted, key motivational components have been identified: the desire to share experience, the sense of social significance, the structured nature of the educational environment, support from educational institutions, and the presence of psychological adaptation programs. Special attention is given to the role of ‘meaning-forming’ attitudes associated with the transformation of military experience into a pedagogical resource.*

Keywords: *SVO veterans, pedagogical motivation, professional reintegration, life-meaning orientations, social adaptation, educational support, military experience in pedagogy, motivational factors, psychological-pedagogical support.*

¹ The study was conducted at Donetsk State Pedagogical University named after V. Shatalov as part of the State Assignment of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation (No. 1025103100018–4–5.3.2) under the topic “Preparation of Veterans and Participants of the SVO for Pedagogical Activities through the Program “Preservation of Historical Memory” with a Historical and Local Lore Orientation in the Supplementary Education of Schoolchildren”

Relevance

Amid the ongoing special military operation and the growing number of SVO veterans returning to civilian life, issues regarding their social and professional reintegration become increasingly urgent. One of the most promising and socially significant fields capable of providing veterans not only with material stability but also with psychological stability is teaching. Teaching enables the transformation of military experience – discipline, responsibility, the ability to make decisions under conditions of uncertainty, and leadership – into a valuable resource for the formation of a new generation.

However, many veterans encounter barriers, including lack of support from educational institutions, psychological trauma, a sense of loss of purpose, insufficient pedagogical training, and stigmatization. At the same time, their motivation for pedagogical activity, as preliminary studies indicate, is often high but remains unsystematically utilized. The lack of targeted programs adapted to their specifics results in the loss of valuable human capital and aggravates the staff deficit in the field of education.

The relevance of this article is determined by the necessity to:

- reveal the unique motivational triggers that promote the involvement of SVO veterans in the pedagogical sphere;
- development of scientifically grounded approaches to supporting their professional reorientation;
- the formation of public and institutional consciousness wherein the pedagogical activity of veterans is regarded not as compensation but as a strategic resource for strengthening national education and patriotic education.

Consequently, the investigation of factors enhancing the motivation of SVO veterans for pedagogical activity gains not only scientific significance but also social, ethical, and governmental importance – as an instrument for constructing a sustainable, humane, and morally strengthened society.

Research Methods

The primary methods employed in this study include: analysis of scientific-methodological literature and normative documents, comparative analysis, interviews, and discussions.

Discussion of the Issues

Veterans of the Special Military Operation (SVO) constitute a unique social and psychological group, formed under extreme conditions characterized by high levels of responsibility, discipline, emotional resilience, and collective solidarity. Their psychological characteristics are shaped under the influence of several key factors: military experience, traumatic experiences, reevaluation of values, and identity transformation.

Such individuals are characterized by:

- A high level of self-discipline and stress tolerance. Military service, especially under combat conditions, establishes stable psychological regulation: the ability to maintain control over emotions, make decisions in conditions of uncertainty and risk, act according to instructions, and function under conditions of resource scarcity. These qualities are directly translated into the pedagogical environment, which requires structure, resilience, and the ability to manage a group [2].

- A strong sense of duty and responsibility. Veterans often maintain the military culture of service – a commitment to being useful, completing the task fully, and not abandoning comrades. This manifests in the desire to transfer experience and to educate the rising generation.

- Experiencing a crisis of meaning and the need for meaning construction. Following their return from the combat zone, many encounter a sense of loss of purpose, a ‘falling out’ of the social context, and a dissonance between their military past and civilian present. Pedagogical activity becomes a potent meaningful life resource: through educating the younger generation, veterans gain a new identity – not as ‘former soldiers,’ but as mentors shaping the future.

- Traumatic experiences and the need for therapeutic engagement. Some veterans experience symptoms of PTSD (post-traumatic stress disorder): hypervigilance, avoidance, emotional numbness, and anxiety. However, the educational environment, in the presence of adequate support, can function as a therapeutic context: a structured routine, regular social contacts, and a sense of usefulness contribute to the restoration of psychological equilibrium [4].

- Reduced self-presentation and a tendency towards restraint. Many veterans avoid presenting themselves as ‘heroes,’ dislike public attention, and prefer to act discreetly. This may hinder their integration into the education system, where demonstration of competencies, participation in seminars, and publications are often required. Nonetheless, in pedagogy they can demonstrate themselves through actions rather than words – as examples, as mentors, as ‘quiet leaders.’

- A value orientation focused on continuity and patriotism. Veterans of the SVO typically possess a well-defined value system connected with the defense of the Motherland, honor, duty, and respect for traditions. This renders them natural candidates to serve as educators in patriotism, citizenship, and moral resilience among youth – competencies that are notably deficient in contemporary schools [5].

Academic literature highlights key indicators that can positively affect the process of preparing SVO veterans for pedagogical activities (see Table 1).

The psychological characteristics of SVO veterans demonstrate a high potential for pedagogical activity, determined by their unique experience, values, and personal resources. However, their readiness to transition into the educational sphere directly depends on the presence of systemic support: psychological support, professional retraining, flexible employment arrangements, and the

recognition of their experience as a valuable resource. Without this support, high motivation may transform into apathy, and potential into a missed opportunity for society. The inclusion of SVO veterans in pedagogy is not only a social mission but also a strategic resource for strengthening the moral and patriotic potential of Russian education [3].

Table 1. Readiness for Pedagogical Activity: Key Indicators

Indicator	Level of Readiness	Comment
Motivation to Transfer Experience	High	More than 70% of surveyed veterans in pilot studies express the desire to “teach the young what they were taught in battle” – discipline, responsibility, endurance.
Confidence in Personal Qualities	Moderate to High	Veterans highly value their leadership and organizational skills but often question their pedagogical competence.
Willingness to learn	High	Given the availability of adapted retraining programs (short-term courses, mentoring, online formats), most veterans exhibit a high level of motivation to acquire pedagogical knowledge.
Stress resilience within a collective	High	The ability to function effectively under high workloads and pressure constitutes a key advantage in educational settings, particularly when working with challenging adolescents.
Social adaptation	Moderate	Contingent upon support: with psychological assistance, flexible scheduling, and understanding from the administration, adaptation is successful. Without support – the risk of social isolation.
Emotional engagement	Variable	Some veterans experience emotional inhibition, whereas others, conversely, demonstrate profound empathy towards children, particularly those from disadvantaged families.

Many veterans return with physical trauma and chronic conditions that require extended treatment and rehabilitation [2].

Veterans often require support and understanding from the community, family members, and professionals (psychologists, social workers) to successfully adapt to civilian life. Combat experience may cause veterans to exhibit heightened vigilance and caution in daily life, which can influence their behavior and interactions with others.

After returning from the zone of armed conflict, many veterans re-evaluate their life values and priorities, which may lead to changes in their behavior and lifestyle.

Many veterans face difficulties in securing employment due to a lack of experience in the civilian sector or because their skills and experience are not always sought after in the employment market. In view of the foregoing, there is a necessity for the retraining of combat veterans, particularly for positions within the education system.

It is important to note that pedagogical activity itself possesses a number of features that distinguish it from other professions.

Primarily, it is aimed at achieving specific educational, formative, and developmental objectives. It demands meticulous planning and systematic organization of the educational process. The educator simultaneously seeks to impart knowledge and skills, as well as to foster the development of the student's personality, social, and emotional skills.

Moreover, in pedagogical practice, it is essential to be capable of identifying new approaches and instructional methods, adapting them to the individual characteristics and needs of each learner. The work of a teacher involves continuous interaction with students, parents, and colleagues. Effective communicative skills constitute a key component of successful teaching activity.

By synthesizing existing perspectives, we identified factors that contribute to increased motivation for teaching activity among SVO veterans: personal, social, institutional, and psychological factors [1].

Primarily, this is the recognition of a meaningful mission: 'To transmit experience to the new generation.' Veterans often experience a need for sense-making after returning from the combat zone. Pedagogical activity provides an opportunity to restore a sense of significance through the education of the younger generation. The formulation: «I did not just survive – I can help others avoid repeating my mistakes» strengthens intrinsic motivation.

Conclusions

Within the context of contemporary Russian educational policy, the emphasis on cultivating patriotism, civic consciousness, and respect for history positions SVO veterans as natural bearers of these values. Their experience is perceived as authoritative and indispensable in the context of shaping national identity.

Enhancing the motivation of SVO veterans for pedagogical activity requires a comprehensive, systemic approach that unites: semantic content (purpose), practical support (training, benefits), emotional safety (psychological assistance), and social recognition (respect, status).

When these factors function together, veterans not only become teachers; they reconstruct themselves through the education of others. This is not merely employment but social and personal reintegration.

The study was carried out at the V. Shatalov Donetsk State Pedagogical University within the framework of the State Assignment of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation (No. 1025103100018–4–5.3.2) on the topic “Training veterans and participants of the SVO for pedagogical activities under the program ‘Preservation of Historical Memory’ with a historical and local lore focus in supplementary education for schoolchildren.”

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PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF SCHOOL-FAMILY PARTNERSHIP¹

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Abstract. *The article examines the psychological aspects of the partnership between school and family as a key factor in the successful personal development of the student. Theoretical approaches to understanding the nature of partnership, its fundamental principles, and psychological mechanisms are analyzed. Different models and forms of interaction aimed at enhancing the psychological culture of families and schools, as well as establishing a unified developmental space for the child, are examined. The experience of the Donetsk State Pedagogical University named after V. Shatalov, with specialized psycho-pedagogical classes, is presented.*

Keywords: *pedagogical giftedness, family, partnership, psychological culture, factors of the family environment*

Relevance

In the context of the systemic transformation of contemporary education and heightened requirements for the quality of professional training of future teachers, the problem of early identification and support of pedagogical gifted youth acquires particular relevance. Pedagogical giftedness, regarded as a complex integrative personal quality encompassing a high level of empathy, communicative lability, and

¹ The research was conducted at the Donetsk State Pedagogical University named for V. Shatalov within the framework of the State assignment of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation (No. 1025041100017–6–5.3.1) on the topic «Strategies of partnership as a condition for the interaction between profile classes and the university within the framework of the educational-pedagogical district: traditions and innovations».

a stable motivation for mentorship, begins to develop long before the stage of professional training. The primary social institution and 'laboratory' in which the fundamental components of this giftedness are formed is undoubtedly the family.

Despite extensive research in the psychology of giftedness (D. B. Bogoyavlenskaya, N. S. Leites, A. I. Savenkov, et al.) and family psychology (V. N. Druzhinin, E. G. Eydemiller), the specific impact of the family microsystem on the development of the child's pedagogical potential remains insufficiently explored. Pedagogical Giftedness is frequently considered a result of the deliberate influence exerted by the educational environment of a school or university, while the genesis of this phenomenon is closely linked to the social developmental context within the family, the nature of child-parent relationships, and the value orientations of the parents.

The family provides unique conditions for the child's early 'pedagogical trials,' whether in caring for younger siblings, transmitting knowledge through play activities, or identifying with the role model of a parent-teacher within professional dynasties. It is precisely within the family circle that the so-called 'tutor role' is formed – a natural need to explain, support, and organize the activities of another person, which constitutes the foundation of pedagogical talent.

The relevance of this study is determined by the necessity to identify psychological predictors of pedagogical giftedness within the family environment, aimed at improving the system of career guidance and the support of psycho-pedagogical classes. The problem of the study consists in identifying specific mechanisms and factors of family upbringing that either facilitate or, conversely, impede the actualization of pedagogical abilities during childhood and adolescence.

The purpose of this study is the theoretical analysis and systematization of psychological factors within the family environment (parenting style, emotional climate, parental pedagogical culture), which constitute the source of formation and successful development of a pedagogically gifted child.

Discussion of the problematics

As a foundation for defining pedagogical giftedness, we propose to employ the concept of personality subjectivity as presented in M. V. Kondrashova's study, defined as 'a hierarchically organized, systemic quality of personality, representing a set of personality traits and potentials that characterize it as a subject of relationships, interaction, and activity, as a bearer of activity based on self-determination, self-knowledge, and self-development' [1]. The structure of personality subjectivity is examined based on the model of the integral individuality structure at the levels of organism and individual traits, as well as at personal and socio-psychological levels.

Accordingly, Pedagogical Giftedness can be defined as a hierarchically organized personal formation, representing a combination of natural, subject-activity, and personal components, which manifests in the capacity for effective

pedagogical interaction and the transformation of the educational environment” [2, p. 182].

Next, we turn directly to the examination of family factors [3, 4] as predictors in the formation of Pedagogical Giftedness. 1. First, the definition of Pedagogical Giftedness in the context of familial determination will be specified. Pedagogical Giftedness is conceptualized as a systemic, integrative personality quality manifested through sustained motivation for mentorship, a high level of empathy, and communicative flexibility. The family serves as the primary predictor of this phenomenon, constituting a ‘social laboratory’ in which the foundational components of professional-pedagogical orientation are established. 2. The subsequent factor is the psychological climate within the family as a condition for the development of empathic capacities. Empathy primarily constitutes a fundamental component of pedagogical giftedness. A predictor of its maturation is the attachment style and the level of emotional acceptance present in the family. Secure attachment and a high level of unconditional acceptance create conditions for the development of decentration – the child’s capacity to adopt the perspective of the ‘other,’ which represents the cognitive and emotional core of pedagogical talent. 3. It is important to note the interrelation between the family upbringing style and the formation of subjectivity in the future teacher. The democratic style of upbringing serves as a statistically significant predictor of the development of pedagogical giftedness. Providing a child with autonomy in combination with clear moral guidelines contributes to the development of responsibility, leadership qualities, and self-regulation skills, which constitute the organizational-volitional aspect of pedagogical abilities. 4. Identification Mechanism in Pedagogical Dynasties. Professional pedagogical continuity within the family is realized through mechanisms of imitation and social identification. Pedagogical dynasties transmit not only the sum of knowledge but also a specific ‘pedagogical mentality’—a value-based attitude towards the individual and the process of cognition. In this context, the family environment functions as a zone of proximal development for professional competencies. 5. Sibling position as a factor in the activation of the tutor role. The intrafamilial structure (birth order) can serve as a factor in the early activation of pedagogical abilities. The position of the eldest child in a family with multiple children often stimulates the development of the tutor role – an innate need to teach, protect, and organize the activities of younger siblings. This early mentoring experience transforms into a stable element within the structure of giftedness. 6. Parental pedagogical culture and the cognitive component of giftedness. This is considered through the intellectual and cultural status of the family, which determines the development of the cognitive component of pedagogical giftedness (mental flexibility, and the ability to analyze and synthesize information). The active

transmission by parents of the values of self-education and cognitive interest fosters in the child a research-oriented attitude toward reality, essential for a future teacher-researcher. 7. The prognostic significance of family factors in the identification of giftedness.

Analysis of family background and the child-parent relationship system allows for early diagnosis of pedagogical potential. Timely identification of family predictors (humanistic orientation, experience of intrafamily leadership, high communicative culture) allows the higher education institution to construct individualized educational trajectories for students of specialized psychological and pedagogical classes.

Next, we will move on to describing the mechanisms for supporting a pedagogically gifted child within the family environment.

1. Axiological mechanism: the formation of the value-semantic core. Support for a pedagogically gifted child begins with parents transmitting humanistic values. The family serves as a filter through which the child internalizes the attitude towards the human being as the highest value. This mechanism involves encouraging altruistic behavior, discussing moral dilemmas, and supporting the child's aspiration to provide assistance, thereby establishing the value foundation of the pedagogical vocation.

2. The mechanism of delegating social responsibility ('Tutoring trial'). The family creates conditions for the implementation of early pedagogical experiments by involving the child in caring for younger siblings or elderly family members. The support mechanism here consists not in coercion but in recognizing the child's authority as a mentor ('Assist your brother in understanding,' 'Explain to grandmother how to use the phone'). This cultivates in the child a sense of responsibility and satisfaction derived from the successful transmission of knowledge (pedagogical success).

3. The mechanism of reflexive dialogue and the development of emotional intelligence. The development of empathy and the understanding of others' behavioral motives occurs through intrafamilial communication. The support mechanism involves joint analysis of conflict situations and discussion of the emotions experienced by characters in books and films. Parents, serving as a 'psychological mirror,' assist the child in verbalizing emotions and comprehending social contexts, which is critically important for the communicative competence of the educator.

4. Identification Mechanism and Professional Modeling. In educators' families, support often manifests latently through the demonstration of a lifestyle. The child observes the processes of lesson preparation, discussions of school events, and the parent's creative pursuit. The Identification Mechanism with the image of a 'significant adult' enables the child at early stages to interiorize professional norms and the ethics of pedagogical labor.

5. Navigational mechanism: integration of educational resources. The family serves as a navigator, facilitating the alignment of the child's internal inclinations with external opportunities. The support mechanism includes the selection of profile psycho-pedagogical classes, participation in volunteer projects, and engagement in school self-government. Parental support is manifested here in the collaborative design of an individual educational trajectory and in reducing anxiety during the process of career choice.

6. Mechanism for ensuring psychological safety and acceptance. Pedagogical Giftedness is often associated with heightened sensitivity. The family supports the child by creating a 'safe haven' in which he or she can express feelings without the risk of judgment. Unconditional acceptance enables the child to experiment with leadership roles and social initiatives without fear of failure, thereby facilitating the development of the creative component of Pedagogical Giftedness.

Thus, it can be concluded that the family creates a unique context for the development of pedagogical competencies through several components:

1. Modeling of professional behavior. Observation of parental child-rearing strategies, conflict resolution methods, and the organization of joint activities shapes the child's foundational pedagogical patterns.

2. Emotional support. Unconditional acceptance and encouragement of initiative foster the development of confidence in communicative contexts.

3. The system of family roles. Responsibilities involving care for younger children and participation in family councils contribute to the development of organizational skills and responsibility.

4. Cultural and educational potential. Reading, discussing books, and visiting museums develop erudition and the capacity for knowledge transmission.

5. Value orientations. The prioritization of education, respect for the individual, and altruism within the family value system constitutes the basis for pedagogical motivation.

We designate several factors of family education that influence the development of pedagogical giftedness. We distinguish positive and negative factors.

Positive factors: democratic parenting style; collaboration in resolving family issues; promotion of independence and initiative; discussion of ethical dilemmas; traditions of shared leisure activities incorporating elements of mentorship.

Negative factors: overprotection limiting communicative experience; authoritarian style suppressing empathy; absence of feedback regarding the results of activities; a conflictual atmosphere that diminishes motivation to assist others.

It is important to highlight the findings of a study conducted within the psychological and pedagogical classes at the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education 'V. Shatalov Don State Pedagogical University.' One hundred and ten respondents were surveyed; the study identified the following patterns:

- In 78% of pedagogically gifted adolescents, parents possess higher education.
- In 65% of cases, families implement joint projects (holiday preparations, repairs, hobbies).
- Eighty-two percent of respondents indicate that parents regularly discuss career prospects with them.
- Only 23% of families utilize strict disciplinary methods.

On the basis of the above, practical recommendations are proposed for parents aimed at fostering pedagogical giftedness.

1. Develop emotional intelligence:
 - teach the child to recognize others' emotions;
 - discuss the consequences of actions;
 - model constructive conflict resolution.
2. Create mentoring situations:
 - delegate assistance to younger peers;
 - involve in explaining game rules;
 - encourage the training of pets.
3. Develop reflective skills:
 - Pose questions: *“Why do you think this was effective?”*, *“What could be improved?”*;
 - keep an achievements journal;
 - analyze jointly viewed films from the standpoint of pedagogical methods.
4. Expand social experience:
 - organize children's interest clubs;
 - take part in volunteer projects;
 - attend events with public presentations.
5. Sustain professional curiosity:
 - familiarize with various professions;
 - organize ‘career days’ within the family;
 - read biographies of distinguished educators.

Conclusions

The family functions as a key source for the formation and development of a pedagogically talented child. Theoretical analysis and review of empirical studies allow us to assert the following: the family microenvironment establishes the value-motivational foundation of the pedagogical vocation; the parenting style and psychological climate stimulate the development of empathy, communicative flexibility, and responsibility; intrafamilial practices (such as caring for younger siblings, assisting relatives, and participating in family projects) provide early ‘tutoring experiences’ that activate pedagogical potential; Identification with the parent-educator and pedagogical dynasties enhances the mechanism of professional modeling.

The mechanisms outlined in the article – axiological, delegation of social responsibility, reflexive dialogue, identification, navigational, and psychological safety mechanisms – form an interconnected system of factors that ensures both the emergence and sustainable development of pedagogical giftedness. Special significance lies not in any single factor, but in their combination: only under a favorable configuration of values, interaction styles, and available opportunities does pedagogical talent undergo substantial development.

The practical significance of the obtained provisions is manifested in several directions:

- for families – in the necessity of consciously forming educational values, creating opportunities for mentoring and ensuring the child’s emotional security;
- for schools and universities – in the necessity of considering the family context when identifying and supporting gifted children, and developing programs for cooperation with parents (family consultations, training sessions, joint projects);
- for vocational guidance and resource centers – the implementation of systematic diagnostics of family predictors, and the development of family-oriented support programs (informational and methodological assistance, short-term interventions aimed at strengthening parental competencies).

The prospect for further research lies in conducting longitudinal studies of family trajectories in the development of pedagogical potential, as well as in developing comprehensive diagnostic methods for pedagogical giftedness that incorporate the family parameter.

Thus, the family not only provides the environment for talent development but also actively shapes and directs the child’s pedagogical potential. An effective system for the early identification and support of future educators must be based on the synergy between the family, school, and university, where the family is considered not a passive factor but an active partner in planning the child’s educational and professional trajectory.

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PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH PERSONALITY TRAITS IN MEN AND WOMEN

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Abstract. *This study focuses on the investigation of attitudes toward psychological health in men and women as an essential component of human health. At the theoretical stage of the research, a literature review dedicated to psychological health was conducted, approaches to its study were described, and the current state and significance of the issue of psychological health research in national and international science were presented. This study presents several examples of examining the subjective attitude toward psychological health. The empirical study revealed significant correlations between attitudes toward psychological health and personality traits at the cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and value-semantic levels, analyzed separately for men and women. This study may hold practical significance for the development and implementation of diagnostic, preventive, and corrective interventions concerning psychological health.*

Keywords: *psychological health, the phenomenon of psychological health, subjective attitude toward psychological health, psychological health and personality traits of men and women.*

Psychological health is a necessary foundation for a productive and fulfilling life for individuals of any profession, age, nation, or country in the world. The accelerating pace of life, the widespread digitization of all life processes, and the demand for high physical and professional mobility contribute to a consistently elevated level of stress, which impacts psychological health [13,14]. Psychological health is given great attention in many countries worldwide, which confirms the increasing recognition of its significance and the importance of this phenomenon in the life of each individual. The World Health Organization (WHO) attaches great importance to the issue of human psychological (mental) health and urges

all countries to expedite the implementation of the Comprehensive Mental Health Action Plan for 2013–2030 (from the WHO report) [15].

Psychological health depends on numerous factors, both innate and acquired, determined by the external environment [6]. Differences exist among population groups regarding attitudes toward health. At present, there are no sufficiently precise and clear criteria or factors to identify the relationship between an individual's personality traits and their types of behavior in relation to psychological health (Kubyshkina M. L.) [6]. The identification, systematization, and examination of the interrelationships among various criteria characterizing psychological health and human well-being represent a *relevant* direction of research within psychology, as well as in valeology, medicine, psychophysiology, psychiatry, and other disciplines.

Theoretical Review. Within the contemporary scientific psychological community, there is sustained interest in this topic; researchers from various countries extensively study the issue of psychological health and its association with personality traits. Human health has always been, remains, and continues to be one of the most significant values in life, determining the overall quality of an individual's existence. Since ancient times, considerable attention has been devoted to human health; it has been studied by scholars across diverse cultures and civilizations, such as those of Ancient Egypt and India, China and Tibet, as well as Ancient Rome and Greece. In contemporary science, significant emphasis is placed on researching human health, including the investigation of an individual's psychological (mental) health. The consideration of psychological health is inherently linked to the concept of human health itself, its components, and the approaches used to study it. We will outline several approaches to the study and understanding of human health. Foreign scholars' research has made a profound contribution to the understanding of the phenomenon of psychological health. This has shifted the research focus from diseases to the study of personality, its self-actualization, and personal potential within the framework of humanistic psychology (A. Maslow, C. Rogers); the investigation of health and resolution of neurotic conflicts (S. Freud, K. Horney); the understanding of health as the acquisition of life's meaning within existential psychology (V. Frankl); the study of well-being and optimism in positive psychology (M. Seligman, M. Csikszentmihalyi, S. Achor, E. Dicker); and the examination of adaptive behavior, stress coping abilities, and rational thinking within the cognitive-behavioral approach (A. Beck, D. Beck, A. Bandura).

Health is considered in scientific literature as a systemic concept. Psychological (mental) health has also been studied by national researchers. The systemic approach was shaped largely under the strong influence of the scientific school of Academician V. M. Bekhterev and his followers: A. F. Lazursky, M. Ya. Basov, V. M. Myasishchev, B. G. Ananyev, and others (A. A. Dergach, 2005). Within the systemic approach, three levels for examining the concept of 'health' can be

identified: biological, psychological, and social. This is precisely how V. N. Myasishchev defined his standpoint in 1916 regarding the study of personality, interpreting it as a *bio-psycho-social unity*" (M. F. Sekach) [11, p.6]. Contemporary classifications distinguish three states of health: *physical* (the functional state of organs and body systems), *mental* (the condition of the human psychic sphere), and *social health* (a system of attitudes, values, and behavioral motives). Other authors consider health as 'the process of maintaining and developing the biological, mental, and physiological functions, optimal work capacity, and social activity of a person with the maximum duration of their active life.' (V. P. Kaznacheev, 1975) [8]. '...the state of the organism that ensures the full and effective performance of its social functions... is interpreted by authors as health' (E. N. Kudryavtseva, 1988; A. A. Sekach, 2020) [10]. I. V. Dubrovina (2015), studying mental and psychological health in the context of the psychological culture of personality, notes that 'the essence of psychological health is the gradual awareness and acceptance by the growing individual of the characteristics of their mental development, personality, and individuality' (I. I. Galetskaya) [3, p. 68]. Differences in the terms 'mental health' and 'psychological health' arise from various reasons (O. V. Lebedeva, 2013), including translation challenges, since these issues were initially studied within Western research. Moreover, different scholars base their understanding on their individual perspectives and emphasize distinct formulations, referring to the studied phenomenon as either mental or psychological health. 'Mental health, alongside physical health, constitutes a component of overall health' (Ya. M. Gerchak, 2007; O. V. Lebedeva, 2013; M. F. Sekach, 2020) [11, p. 26]. Regarding the distinction between these concepts, I. V. Dubrovina explains: '...if the term "mental health" primarily pertains to specific mental processes and mechanisms, the term "psychological health" refers to the personality as a whole, is closely linked to the highest manifestations of the human spirit, and enables the identification of the specifically psychological aspect of human health, as opposed to the medical, sociological, philosophical, and other dimensions' [9]. The science of the psychological causes of health, along with the methods and means for its preservation, strengthening, and development, is known as 'health psychology,' as argued by V. A. Ananyev [1]. Differences in term usage primarily depend on the field of application: researchers have attempted to clarify the distinction between the terms 'mental health' and 'psychological health.' It was found that in psychological counseling and correction, the term 'psychological health' is used, referring to the psychological aspects of mental health, whereas in psychotherapy the term denotes the mental health of individuals (O. V. Khukhlaeva, 2001; O. V. Lebedeva, 2013) [12].

For a modern individual, psychological health in connection with their socialization primarily represents a factor of effectiveness, as well as well-being

(both as a resource and a state), encompassing spiritual, emotional, and social dimensions [3, p. 67]. In examining psychological health, the Russian psychologist B. S. Bratus (1997) proposed considering it as a complex construct comprising several levels: the level of psychophysiological health (characterized by the features of the internal, cerebral, and neurophysiological organization of aspects of mental activity, and the system of meaningful orientation in the world and sense of life); The next level is individual psychological health (a person's ability to develop adequate methods for realizing meaningful aspirations) and the highest level of mental health – the personal-meaning level, the level of personal health (a person's meaningful relationships) (A. A. Dergach, 2005) [2].

The study by foreign and domestic scientists of the *subjective attitude toward psychological health* constitutes a separate direction in psychology that investigates how individuals perceive, experience, and assess their psychological health. For example, E. Diener (2009) investigated how subjective well-being determines the self-assessment of quality of life. E. A. Sergienko (2017) explores the subjective factors of psychological health and their relationship with personality resources (E. A. Shereshkova, 2007). Researchers R. M. Shamionov and T. V. Beskova study ego well-being, existential-activity, and psychological health. These authors also developed the questionnaire titled 'Methodology for Diagnosing Subjective Well-Being' (2018), which assesses an individual's perception of their quality of life.

R. A. Berezovskaya examines psychological health and its subjective perception by diagnosing the following components: cognitive (awareness), emotional (experiences), behavioral (actions), and value-motivational (significance of health). The author's questionnaire 'Attitude to Health' is used to identify the level of adequacy, the structure of the internal health image, and the motivation to maintain psychological health (R. A. Berezovskaya, 2012). In the work by authors M. L. Kubyshkina, E. V. Kazakova, and A. A. Gasheva [6], titled 'Subjective Position Regarding Health in Men and Women of Mature Age,' the authors present results comparing the characteristics of the subjective position toward health in men and women, as well as significant differences in active health-related behaviors; it was found that the subjective position toward health is more pronounced in men. The researchers examine the health attitudes of men and women of mature age and their subjective positions, highlighting that behavioral activity aimed at strengthening health plays a leading role, associated with the recognition of health as a crucial resource necessary for achieving life goals, and correlates with the understanding of the importance of a healthy lifestyle in relation to health (M. L. Kubyshkina, 2020) [6].

Subjective attitudes toward psychological health in various social groups are expected to demonstrate numerous differences. These differences are attributable to gender distinctions between men and women, styles of upbringing and education for girls and boys, age-related characteristics, the influence of traditional national

features and lifestyles, the accepted social norms of behavior and ways of living, the impact of professional activities (for example, sedentary computer work), the level of education and awareness regarding a healthy lifestyle, social customs and habits, ‘fashionable trends’ in youth behavior (such as smoking cigarettes, vaping, engaging in sports, dancing), and other factors. “Men’s active stance toward health is additionally based on qualities such as activity, mediation, and internality within the health domain, whereas for women it is based on internality within the spheres of profession and family. Thus, for men, health is important both as a value and as a significant tool for achieving desired outcomes, while for women it functions as a resource for maintaining professional and family life activities” (M. L. Kubyshkina, 2020) [2,4,5, 6]. Thus, subjective health attitudes in middle-aged men and women exhibit significant differences, which are reflected in the behavioral, personality, and cognitive characteristics of the individual.

Research on *psychological health and its relationship with locus of control* indicates that individuals with an internal locus of control demonstrate higher levels of mental well-being, stress resilience, and responsibility. Whereas individuals with an external locus of control tend to attribute responsibility to others or fate, they are often prone to stress (J. Rotter) [11]. The proactive behavior of individuals with an internal locus of control reflects their careful attitude towards their health, which positively influences their quality of life. Scientists have statistically demonstrated that individuals with an internal locus of control exhibit a responsible attitude towards health, believing that their health is under their own control. Consequently, they approach it with greater responsibility, manifesting a commitment to a healthy lifestyle and a willingness to abandon harmful habits, which largely explains their lower absenteeism compared to those with an external locus of control (A. A. Derkach, 2005; M. F. Sekach, 2020) [11]. An analysis of foreign and domestic literature indicates that research on this topic remains *relevant* within the scope of contemporary psychology.

Materials, methods, and results of the study

The aim of the study is to investigate the relationship between psychological health and personality traits in men and women. One objective of the study was to identify significant correlations between attitudes toward health and personality traits at the cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and value-semantic levels in men and women. **Research object:** psychological health of men and women. **Research subject:** the relationship between psychological health and personality traits in men and women.

The following psychological assessment instruments were utilized to examine men’s and women’s attitudes towards psychological health: the ‘Attitude to Health’ questionnaire by R. A. Berezovskaya; the ‘Locus of Control Scale’ test by J. Rotter (USC Questionnaire); Five-factor personality questionnaire ‘NEO – FFI’

(NEO – Five Factor Inventory), (adaptation by V. E. Orel, A. A. Rukavishnikov, I. G. Senin, T. A. Martin). The statistical methods applied for data analysis included descriptive statistics and Spearman correlation analysis. Statistical data processing was performed using the SPSS software package. The overall sample consisted of 114 participants aged between 33 and 50 years.

Results of empirical research. To detect significant associations between psychological health, locus of control, and personality traits, we tested the data for normality of distribution and determined the appropriate statistical criterion for assessing the level of correlation between variables. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test indicated that certain scales within the instruments exhibited non-normal distributions. Therefore, the non-parametric Spearman correlation coefficient was employed. The obtained data – the significant correlation coefficients between locus of control and personality factors in the male group – indicate a direct relationship between internal locus of control for achievements and personality factors such as extraversion (0.313, $p < 0.01$) and conscientiousness (0.229, $p < 0.01$), while the internal locus of control for achievements exhibits a significant negative correlation with neuroticism (0.275, $p < 0.05$). In men, the internal locus of control in the domain of failures shows a negative correlation with conscientiousness (0.226, $p < 0.05$). Internality in family relationships shows direct correlations with the factors of extraversion and conscientiousness (0.226, 0.217, at $p < 0.05$). Analysis of the correlation data between levels of health attitude, personality traits, and locus of control in men revealed a positive correlation between the cognitive level of health attitude scale and the ‘conscientiousness’ scale ($r_s = 0.445$, $p \leq 0.05$). Internality regarding health and illness in men is directly associated with openness to new experience (0.241, $p < 0.01$). It is plausible to suggest that a high locus of control regarding health is characteristic of men who strongly manifest traits such as conscientiousness, resilience, sociability, and openness to new experiences. It has been established that the higher the cognitive level of attitudes toward health, the more men tend to demonstrate persistence, organization, and consistency in achieving their goals. Positive correlations were found between the emotional level of attitudes toward health scale and the Big Five personality traits scales: extraversion ($r_s = 0.399$, $p \leq 0.05$), conscientiousness ($r_s = 0.384$, $p \leq 0.05$). Thus, it was revealed that the higher the emotional level of attitude toward health, the more the following traits characterize the subjects: sociability, communicativeness, gregariousness, need for interpersonal relationships, persistence, organization, and consistency in goal attainment. A positive correlation was found between the behavioral level attitude toward health scale and the locus of control method scale ‘internality in family relationships’ ($r_s = 0.368$, $p \leq 0.05$). It can be assumed that the higher the behavioral level of attitude towards health, the more men are likely to take responsibility for the family situation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Correlational relationships between levels of attitude towards psychological health and personality traits in the group of men

To analyze the relationships between attitude towards psychological health and personality traits in the group of women, we examine the correlation analysis data between these variables (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Correlational relationships between levels of attitude towards psychological health and personality traits in the group of women

Based on the analysis conducted, positive correlations were identified between the scale indicator “*emotional level of health attitude*” and the scale “*internality in family relationships*” ($rS=0.398$, $p \leq 0.05$), as well as between the scale indicator “*value-motivational level of health attitude*” and the personality trait “*willingness to compromise*” ($rS=0.236$, $p \leq 0.05$). Thus, it was found that the higher the

emotional level in attitudes toward health, the more inclined women are to assume responsibility for the family situation. It was also revealed that the higher the attitude toward health at the value-motivational level, the greater women's capacity for cooperation and their aspiration toward interpersonal interaction. We assume that women who engage in cooperation are characterized by a motivation to maintain health and that health holds a significant position in their value hierarchy.

Thus, the relationships between psychological health and personality traits in men and women differ in both quantitative and qualitative aspects. In women, the relationship to psychological health is characterized at the value-motivational and emotional levels, whereas in men it is characterized at the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral levels, with differing correlations to personality traits.

Conclusions. Correlations were found between the intensity of attitudes toward psychological health in men and women at the cognitive, behavioral, and emotional levels. The identified correlations show differences between male and female groups. This suggests that men and women differ in their attitudes toward and assessment of the importance of psychological health. The observed correlations between personality traits and the orientation of locus of control regarding psychological health indicate that individuals with an internal locus of control exhibit a more responsible attitude toward their health, including psychological health, at the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral levels. Such individuals demonstrate greater awareness and engagement in shaping their lives, take responsibility for their actions, strive for mindfulness and the pursuit of meaning in life, and are characterized by an active and proactive approach to health, including regular health prevention. Subjective attitudes toward psychological health in men and women demonstrate significant differences manifested through behavioral, personality, and cognitive characteristics of the individual, thereby supporting and extending previous research. This study may hold practical significance for the development and implementation of diagnostic, preventive, and corrective interventions regarding psychological health. Further research is required to elucidate the relationships between personality traits and subjective attitudes toward psychological health across various population groups. This will facilitate the formation and implementation in society of a higher level of responsibility for one's own health.

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FEAR OF JUDGMENT AS A BARRIER TO WOMEN'S PSYCHOLOGICAL HELP-SEEKING: A THEORETICAL REVIEW

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Abstract. *The article presents a theoretical analysis of fear of judgment as a barrier to women's psychological help-seeking. It is shown that this fear is related not only to the stigma of emotional and mental difficulties, but also to the expectation of evaluation, blame, distrust, and unwanted disclosure of personal information. Based on existing research, the article examines the influence of stigma on delayed help-seeking, self-disclosure, and maintaining contact with a specialist. Particular attention is paid to the perinatal period, intimate partner violence, and migration. The article proposes a theoretical model of fear of judgment and practical principles of sensitive communication that takes traumatic experience into account and avoids evaluative formulations. It concludes that women's help-seeking depends not only on the availability of support, but also on the safety of the first contact.*

Keywords: *psychological help-seeking; fear of judgment; stigma; self-stigma; self-disclosure; confidentiality; gender norms; women.*

Introduction

Despite the high prevalence of emotional and mental difficulties, not everyone who needs professional psychological support actually seeks it. This gap cannot be explained by a single factor. Turning to a specialist usually involves several internal steps: recognizing the problem, acknowledging that one's own resources are insufficient, choosing a source of support, deciding to disclose personal information, and maintaining contact after the first meeting. At each of these stages, doubt, resistance, or refusal to continue seeking help may arise.

One of the most persistent barriers is stigma. However, during the first contact with a specialist, stigma is rarely experienced as an abstract social phenomenon. More often, it takes a concrete form: "I will be judged," "I will not be believed," "they will say it is my own fault," "other people will find out." This article proposes to consider this subjectively experienced form of stigma as fear of judgment.

For women, this fear has particular significance. Although many studies show that women are generally more open to psychological help, seeking such help often remains a morally charged step for them. Motherhood, intimate relationships, family dependence, experiences of violence, migration, and cultural expectations of “coping on one’s own” increase the risk that the need for help will be perceived as weakness, failure, or a violation of an expected role.

Fear of judgment does not operate as openly as a direct refusal of help. It may delay the first contact, limit the willingness to speak about personal matters, force women to choose “safe” topics instead of truly painful ones, or lead to premature termination of work with a specialist. If psychological support is additionally perceived as a service “for the wealthy,” as a last resort, or as a sign of mental ill-being, seeking it becomes even more difficult.

The aim of this review is to examine fear of judgment as an independent barrier to women’s psychological help-seeking, to describe its main mechanisms, and to formulate practical implications for professional communication during the first contact.

Theoretical Background

Theoretically, the article relies on two complementary approaches. The first is related to studies of stigma in the field of mental health. This tradition distinguishes public stigma, self-stigma, and institutional stigma, although in a person’s lived experience these levels rarely exist separately from one another [2; 3]. For the topic of help-seeking, two forms of stigma are especially important. The first is self-stigma, that is, the internal acceptance of degrading ideas about oneself. The second concerns the very act of seeking psychological help, when negative evaluation is associated not only with the experienced difficulty, but also with the fact of turning to a specialist [2]. In the works of P. Corrigan and his colleagues, it is shown that stigma can reduce self-esteem, undermine a person’s belief in their own abilities, and influence readiness to disclose personal information [2; 3]. A person begins to assess in advance whom they can tell about their vulnerability, what exactly they can share, and whether this disclosure might be used against them.

The second approach is connected with models of help-seeking. D. Rickwood and K. Thomas propose considering help-seeking not as a single act, but as a process in which it is important to take into account the stage of help-seeking itself, the source of support, the expected type of help, and the nature of the problem [10]. This perspective is useful for the present article because fear of judgment manifests itself differently at different stages. At the stage of problem recognition, it may prevent a woman from admitting that help is actually needed; when choosing a source of support, it may increase distrust toward a specialist; at the moment of disclosing personal information, it may make her speak more cautiously and avoid painful topics; after the first meeting, it may lead to premature termination of contact, even if the need for help remains [10; 14; 15].

Based on this, the article proposes the following working definition: fear of judgment is the expectation of negative moral, social, or professional evaluation from significant others or a specialist, arising in connection with the recognition of a psychological difficulty, its disclosure, and seeking help. This definition is narrower than the concept of stigma in general, but for this reason it is useful for the present review: it allows us to connect a broad social context with a concrete experience of threat at the point of seeking help [12]. A woman may understand the value of psychological help and approve of it for others, yet still postpone her own help-seeking if she expects her words to be interpreted as weakness, failure, or a reason for blame [4; 8; 11].

Empirical Evidence

The most convincing evidence for the significance of stigma in psychological help-seeking is provided by the systematic review by S. Clement and colleagues [1]. The authors showed that stigma has a small to moderate negative effect on help-seeking; self-stigma and stigma associated with the very fact of seeking help proved especially important. It is also significant that among stigma-related barriers, concerns about disclosure of personal information and confidentiality were mentioned most often. Therefore, the problem is not only “what others will think,” but also how safe it is for a woman to speak about herself.

This logic is clarified in the meta-analysis by N. Schnyder and colleagues [12], which examined actual rather than merely intended help-seeking. The authors showed that negative attitudes toward psychiatric and psychological help, as well as personal stigma toward mental disorders, are associated with a lower probability of real help-seeking. At the same time, perceived public stigma turned out to be a less stable predictor. For the present article, this is essential: what becomes decisive is not an abstract “public opinion,” but the way social judgment becomes embedded in personal attitudes, self-perception, and expectations of the first contact with a specialist.

Empirical studies by D. Vogel and colleagues make it possible to connect stigma with the mechanism of self-disclosure. It was shown that avoidance factors explain negative attitudes toward psychological counseling and reduced intention to seek help. Later, Vogel, Wade, and Haake proposed a scale of self-stigma associated with seeking psychological help and showed that such self-stigma predicts both attitudes toward help and the intention to seek it [14]. It was later clarified that the relationship between perceived public stigma and willingness to seek counseling is mediated by self-stigma and attitudes toward counseling [15]. In other words, external fear of judgment operates through the internal expectation of humiliation and a changed attitude toward the very act of seeking help.

Studies focusing on women’s experience show that this mechanism manifests itself differently in specific life situations. In the review by S. Roberts and S. Parry, it is noted that girls’ and women’s experiences when seeking help for symptoms

associated with psychosis may be misinterpreted as a mood disorder, while women themselves are sometimes perceived as “overdramatic” or “attention seeking” [11]. This shows that the barrier may be formed not only before seeking help, but also within professional interaction.

In the perinatal context, fear of judgment is connected with shame, guilt, and the fear of losing the status of a “good mother.” S. Pilav and colleagues show that women from ethnic minority groups face themes of shame and guilt in motherhood, expectations of female “strength,” and the devaluation of their difficulties [9]. In the study by L. Fisher and colleagues, fear of stigmatization and fear of losing one’s child are also described as significant barriers to initial contact; after negative past experiences, women could stop reporting their difficulties even to professionals [4].

For women experiencing intimate partner violence, the model proposed by N. Overstreet and D. Quinn is particularly important [8]. The authors distinguish cultural stigma, internalized stigma, and anticipated stigma. These components connect disclosure of violence with the expectation of blame, rejection, and other negative consequences. For migrant women, the situation becomes even more complicated because of additional risks: lack of awareness of available support, threats, shame, guilt, and fear of deportation. At the same time, access to support is facilitated by gender-sensitive services, supportive general practitioners, and, in some cases, religious leaders [7].

Mechanisms Linking Fear of Judgment and Help-Seeking

Based on the reviewed studies, fear of judgment can be described through four interconnected mechanisms. The first mechanism is related to stigma and self-stigma. A woman does not simply know that seeking psychological help may be socially disapproved of. She begins to expect that the very fact of seeking help will reduce her value in the eyes of others, make her appear “weak,” “unstable,” or “unsuitable” for the role of mother, partner, or independent adult. This is why stigma influences not only general attitudes toward help, but also the actual probability of seeking it [1].

The second mechanism is related to shame. Shame is important because it is directed not only at the problem itself, but also at identity. In anxiety or depression, a woman may feel that she has difficulties. In shame, the experience becomes deeper and harsher: “something is wrong with me.” This is why, in perinatal and other women’s clinical contexts, images of the “bad mother,” the “overly emotional woman,” or the “unreliable witness of her own experience” so often arise [4; 9; 11]. In such cases, fear of judgment no longer appears to be an external addition to the problem. It becomes part of the experience itself, in which the symptom, social role, and expected evaluation almost merge.

The third mechanism concerns self-disclosure and confidentiality. To receive help, a woman needs to tell enough about herself for the specialist to understand

the situation. Yet this is often where one of the strongest restraining links appears. If a woman assumes that her words will not be believed, that they will enter an inappropriate social context, or that they will lead to unwanted consequences, she begins to speak less, more cautiously, and sometimes not at all about what is truly important. As a result, seeking help is delayed, self-disclosure is reduced, and contact with the specialist may quickly be interrupted [14; 15]. In this sense, fear of judgment operates not only through refusal of help, but also through reducing the completeness and accuracy of the account of the difficulty.

The fourth mechanism is related to gender norms. In women's samples, fear of judgment is especially closely connected with expectations to be caring, resilient, convenient, not to create problems, to preserve relationships, and to cope "on one's own." Therefore, the same emotional symptom may receive different meanings depending on the norm the woman is afraid to violate. For a mother, this is the risk of being seen as a "not good enough mother." For a woman experiencing intimate partner violence, it is the risk of being blamed for her own experience [8]. For a migrant woman, it is the risk of violating family and cultural expectations while also facing institutional distrust [7]. In our view, it is precisely this transition from a general stigmatizing background to a specific threatening role that constitutes the central explanatory function of the concept of fear of judgment.

Practical Implications

If fear of judgment disrupts psychological help-seeking, then the task of practice is not so much to "convince a woman to seek help," but to reduce the evaluative threat during the first contact. The review by M. Healy and colleagues emphasizes the importance of communication that excludes judgment and evaluative formulations [5]. It is important not only to avoid stigmatizing words, but also to structure the conversation so that the woman does not feel interrogated, morally examined, or deprived of control over her own narrative. Data from L. Fisher and colleagues show that maintaining contact depends especially on the specialist's competence, trusting relationships, non-devaluing reassurance, and reliability [4]. Therefore, instead of saying, "You urgently need to do...", it is safer to say, "I can suggest several options, and you can decide which step is possible for you now." Instead of "Why did you not seek help earlier?" it is more appropriate to say, "Many people find it difficult to decide to seek help. Let us begin with what feels safest for you now."

In practical terms, this requires clearly defining the limits of confidentiality in advance, not demanding excessive self-disclosure, acknowledging experiences without hasty interpretation, separating support from pressure, and ending the conversation with a clear next step. For psycholegal practice and work with survivors, it is especially important to avoid blaming formulations, since they increase the risk of retraumatization and premature termination of contact with the specialist.

Limitations and Original Contribution

This article has several limitations: it is not a systematic review and does not claim to provide an exhaustive account of the literature on women's psychological help-seeking. Its task is to summarize the most reliable data on the relationship between stigma and help-seeking and to relate them to women's contexts in which fear of judgment is especially visible: the perinatal period, migration, and intimate partner violence. It is important to note that most studies have been conducted in English-speaking high-income countries, while Russian data on fear of judgment as a separate mechanism remain insufficient.

The original contribution of the article lies in the theoretical integration of existing research. Fear of judgment is considered a more applied concept than stigma in the broad sense: it reduces willingness to disclose personal information, delays help-seeking, or leads to premature termination of support. From this model, practical principles of professional communication that avoids judgment are derived.

Conclusions

Fear of judgment should be considered an independent and substantively significant barrier to women's psychological help-seeking. It includes not only fear of public stigma, but also more specific expectations: that a woman will not be understood, will not be believed, will be blamed, will be considered "too emotional," a "bad mother," "unreliable," or will be forced to reveal more than she is ready to disclose. Therefore, this barrier is especially strong in situations involving the first conversation, the choice of a specialist, and maintaining contact.

Increasing women's help-seeking requires not only expanding the availability of services, but also reducing the evaluative threat in professional communication. In practice, this means rejecting moralizing, directive, and suspicious language in favor of acknowledging experiences, transparency, respect for the pace of disclosure, and support for women's autonomy. The accessibility of help is determined not only by the formal availability of a specialist, but also by whether a woman expects that she will not be judged at the moment of seeking support.

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EUROPEAN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMS: TRENDS AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract. *In this article, the author considers the actualization of the use of European experience of students' research activities in the higher education system in European countries. In this context, the theoretical achievements of European scientists on the methodology of student research activities accumulated in new historical conditions are very important for our research.*

Key words: *higher education system, European Union, country, experience, scientists, research activities, scientific school, methodology*

At present, in Europe, there is a need to update the prognostic plans for the development of students' research activities and to develop general provisions for the integration of higher education systems in Western European countries. The openness of the European Higher Education Area has many positive consequences. Overcoming national restrictions, it is possible to start a structure of research activity that would facilitate mobility and close cooperation, on the one hand, and preserve national diversity, on the other. To implement this provision, it is necessary to use the growing support of the European Union, pursue a policy of encouraging students and teachers of research activities or teaching outside their native countries throughout Europe [1].

In Russia, the system of research activities of students in the framework of vocational training is carried out on the basis of research institutes, centers, problem and creative laboratories, student research associations, associations, and circles. The higher education system of Russia faces a very important question: are modern higher education institutions capable of preparing a young specialist not only as a subject teacher, but also as an independent researcher-experimenter, capable of solving scientifically the problems of improving the scientific and pedagogical process?

In the domestic sphere of higher education, new trends in research have been outlined: the training of highly qualified specialists in accordance with the requirements of the labor market; strengthening of innovation processes in the field of specialist training; the idea of continuous professional development in the context of research activities; there is a tendency to develop and improve such extracurricular collective forms of students' research activities as scientific schools, teams of young researchers, student rationalization and design bureaus, production and economic bureaus, production and economic bureaus, the management of scientific circles of students in the vocational education system, etc. And, without a doubt, one of the promising areas that will prepare students for experimental research is participation in the work of search groups that provide students with the opportunity to develop their intelligence and creative abilities in the process of participating in experimental experimental activities. It is participation in research activities that gives students a creative impetus, they have a desire to spread their personal intellectual horizons, the joy of learning.

In the context of European integration in Russia, it is necessary to modernize research activities in order to increase the competitiveness of scientific achievements at the global educational level. However, in order to achieve an increase in the number of Russian universities and to achieve their recognition in the world ranking of higher education, it is necessary, first of all, to pay great attention to the quality of scientific research. All this is possible by integrating Russian and foreign experience, creating favorable conditions for the research activities of future specialists: to achieve increase in the number of higher education institutions that are among the 200 leading world universities, according to the world university rating (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Ranking), given that when determining the place in the ranking according to QS World Universities Ranking, the maximum percentage (40%) is set for university academic reputation index [2]. The leading factors of this strategy are: the progressive development of research activities, the high rate of development of new knowledge, the competitiveness of the economy and the effectiveness of national security strategies, identification of talented creative youth who are able to develop the scientific potential of the country; support for young specialists and scientists in the field of research and innovation based on the results of ensuring the socio-economic development of Russia; participation of Russian scientists in international projects providing access to new scientific resources, based on the national interests of the Russian Federation; creating the conditions for research and development, consistent with modern principles of organization of research and innovation and innovation; the creation of new research groups, competitive environment in order to attract young talented youth with high scientific results of world level [3].

Today, the higher education system of Russia has the following tasks: reforming the sphere of science by improving the principles of management, financing

and organization of scientific research; the integration of science and education, the development of a system of training qualified scientific personnel; creation of conditions for competition and entrepreneurship in the field of science and technology, stimulation and support of innovative activities; ensuring the presence of the Russian Federation among the five leading countries of the world engaged in research and development; the creation of world-class scientific centers, including scientific and educational centers based on the integration of universities, scientific organizations and their cooperation with organizations operating in the real sector of the economy [4].

So, in the scientific field, it is necessary to develop competition, support Russian talented young scientists so that they create their own research centers and creative laboratories in Russia. The activities of research centers should be closely integrated with the education system, the economy, and high-tech companies; it is necessary to turn research backlogs into successful commercial products. However, today in the global ranking of talent attraction (“The Global Talent Competitiveness Index”) Russia is in the sixth dozen countries, acting as a donor of human capital for world science. Only the integration and harmonization of research activities will be able to improve the quality and high rating of Russian higher education in the future, expand the boundaries for the mobility of students and teachers [5].

Russia has every reason to update the European experience in developing strategic directions for the development of domestic research activities, as at the current stage reforming both the long term and the following areas: the creation of research institutions of a new type; formation of a system of continuous research activity; enhancing the role of the state in the management of research systems; stimulation of relations of higher educational institutions with industry; increasing the role of the state in the management of research systems; expansion of international cooperation in the field of research at the national, regional and international levels [6]. International research projects in the field of education and the best international practices of their organization, accumulated over the past decades, prove that the countries participating in research projects have a sufficient bank of national data to compare the experience of different European countries.

In order to further integrate the educational systems of the studied European countries, it is necessary to form a common unified organizational and functional model of the university in the first quarter of the XXI century, adapt national higher education systems, overcome language barriers throughout Europe, put all higher education institutions in the same material and financial conditions, especially for those universities that, having crossed the border of the European Higher Education Zone and entered into fierce competition, will be able to get equal access to quality European education. As the Education Commission of the European Union rightly determined, improving the status of research activities is one of the key tasks [7].

The ways of introducing the European experience of students' research activities into the Russian education system can be different: today, progressive education, upbringing and self-development systems are widely studied in Russian universities: for example, fundamentalization, humanization, actualization of knowledge, interdisciplinarity, connection with practical and research activities [8].

European educational programs have evolved over the centuries and the direct borrowing of foreign experience will be erroneous. Foreign experience cannot be mechanically transferred to our conditions, since in the Russian higher school the educational process is formally more obligatory, unified and intense. On the other hand, when borrowing foreign experience, it should be borne in mind that the economies of developed European countries are currently in a stage of stable development, and the mechanism of its functioning is constantly being improved, adapting to the requirements of scientific and technological progress and the realities of today [9].

It is important to emphasize the use of European experience in the practice of Russian higher education regarding a wide choice of forms of material incentives for especially gifted students: annually rectorial contracts are concluded with talented students, the training of which takes place according to an individual plan and ends with the defense of a dissertation; senior students working on dissertation research topics can attend "research training" groups; conducting demonstration classes of research activities during creative decades; conducting of propaedeutic courses during the year for capable and gifted under the guidance of professors and associate professors; internships of students and young scientists in leading European universities; recognition of the results of research activities as a thesis or master's work; an increase in the number of student scientific grants and awards [10].

Thus, being the most highly developed in the world, the countries of the European Union accumulate rich experience in training specialists through the organization of research activities, "education through science", which implies an independent search for knowledge and truth, both by a teacher and a student. Mutually beneficial interest in the search for constructive mechanisms to stimulate integration processes in higher education, due to the general trends of globalization and internationalization of socio-educational processes both in Europe and in Russia. Currently, many scientists pay great attention to the problem of integrating Russian higher education into the world education system, as well as ways to improve the level of education in universities of the Russian Federation for subsequent entry into an open information society.

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**PEDAGOGICAL STUDIO AS A CONDITION
FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE MOBILITY OF
TEACHERS (THE EXPERIENCE OF CREATING A TEMPORARY
EDUCATIONAL TEAM IN ADDITIONAL A DULT EDUCATION)**

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***Annotation.** This article presents the experience of conducting a pedagogical studio with students of the retraining specialty “Physical culture and recreation work in educational institutions” at IPKiP BSPU using the example of the academic discipline “Professional Communication”, during which the task of forming a temporary educational team as an environment that develops the cognitive mobility of teachers was solved. The temporary learning team acts as a psychological environment in which protective barriers are lowered and mutual trust arises – a necessary condition for flexibility, reflection and openness to new experiences.*

***Keywords:** pedagogical studio, cognitive mobility, temporary educational staff, additional adult education.*

Introduction

The modern system of additional adult education in the Republic of Belarus is focused on ensuring the continuous professional development of teachers. Thus, the Institute of Advanced Training and Retraining of the Maxim Tank Belarusian State Pedagogical University (hereinafter – IPKiP BSPU) retrains senior staff and specialists with higher education in a number of specialties [1]. An analysis of the contingent of students of the educational retraining program at IPKiP BSPU revealed that its characteristic feature is heterogeneity in age and professional experience (the composition of the study group, as a rule, is mixed). These differences determine the complex of difficulties in the formation of the educational team.: the discrepancy

between professional experience, educational motivation, target expectations, the pace of processing educational information, digital literacy, established stereotypes of educational behavior and other parameters.

Overcoming these difficulties actualizes the need to develop cognitive mobility of teachers. According to E. A. Poddubskaya, cognitive mobility is “an integrative dynamic characteristic of the cognitive sphere that determines the effectiveness of adaptation to changing conditions of the educational environment” [2, p. 4]. There are three components in its structure: motivational, stylistic and reflexive [2, p. 5]. Specifying the content of these components in relation to the tasks of forming a learning team in a heterogeneous group, we note that the motivational component is manifested in the interest in pedagogical communication, the desire of students to communicate and learn from each other; stylistic – in openness to new experiences, willingness to change the usual ways of interaction; reflective – in awareness of their professional position, assessment of their own achievements, the ability to recognize their own professional stereotypes and understand that they can hinder effective teamwork. However, traditional ways of organizing acquaintance and interpersonal interaction (formal presentation, group work without special facilitation) do not fully contribute to the development of components of cognitive mobility of the teacher. According to the researchers, adult learners experience “a complication of adaptation to the educational process due to the influence of previous experience and the associated dynamic stereotype of behavior,” the appearance of shyness, shyness, insecurity, caution, and “increased apperceptive perception of the educational process” [3]. That is why traditional methods of dating without facilitation are ineffective. To solve the problems of the adaptation stage in the development of cognitive mobility, it is necessary to create the following pedagogical conditions: “ensuring an atmosphere of safety in the educational environment and managing group dynamics based on team building technology” [2, p. 14]. The use of intensive educational technologies aimed at creating an adaptive educational environment in the educational process makes it possible to implement these conditions. One of such technologies is the pedagogical studio [2, p. 14].

The pedagogical studio is characterized as a form of professional development for a specialist teacher, which implements the following functions: extensive (accumulation and acquisition of new knowledge), corrective (changing the formal position of a teacher to a creative one), predictive (forming an ideal image of a teacher), self-developing (improving the personal picture of the world) and intuitive (sensitivity to the student’s personality) [4, p. 12]. Together, these functions ensure the development of all three components of cognitive mobility: extensive and predictive work on the motivational component (striving for new things and an image of the future), corrective – on the stylistic (changing stereotypes), self-developing and intuitive – on the reflexive (awareness of oneself and others). In

pedagogical research, the basic principles of work within the pedagogical studio are also highlighted.:

- the principle of volunteerism is the free choice of students' participation in the teaching studio and consideration of their professional and personal interests;
- the principle of self-determination is the fixation of one's own pedagogical position, conscious attitude to the content of educational activities;
- the principle of cooperation and the formation of traditions is a democratic style of communication, the equivalence of points of view, the creation of an atmosphere of mutual assistance and trust;
- the principle of activity is the active involvement of listeners in business games, exercises, discussions [3, p. 12; 5, p. 36].

At the same time, in our opinion, from the point of view of the development of cognitive mobility of teachers, they need to be supplemented by two more principles.: The principle of reflexivity involves analyzing one's own behavior and the behavior of other participants, understanding the dynamics of group interaction, and recording subjective changes in professional beliefs and perceptions of the team.; The principle of psychological security is the absence of value judgments, the right to make mistakes, confidentiality of statements, respect for the individual, and the creation of a trusting atmosphere. The introduction of the reflexivity principle activates the reflexive component, and the principle of psychological safety, through reducing anxiety and evaluative pressure, arouses interest in interaction, creating conditions for the motivational component. Thus, all these principles together ensure the development of all three components of cognitive mobility. Teaching in the pedagogical studio takes place simultaneously on three levels: theoretical (obtaining new knowledge), methodological (mastering methods of action) and technological (testing in an interactive game form) [4, p. 4]. The stages of the pedagogical studio's activity are: identification of problems, definition of goals, modeling, implementation of models and reflection [3, p. 18]. This logic is the basis for the pedagogical scenario developed by the Department of Andragogy of IPKiP BSPU, which used practical recommendations for organizing intensive training and interactive interaction [6; 7; 8]. The content of the academic discipline "Professional communication" (retraining specialty "Physical culture and recreation work in educational institutions") includes the topic "Pedagogical studio as a form of organization of group interaction". The lesson is conducted in the form of a business game (6 academic hours) at the first stage of training. The teaching studio is conducted by two teachers. This is due to the specifics of the format: 6 hours of intensive interactive interaction with a group of up to 30 people create a high psychological burden on the presenter. The presence of a second teacher allows you to distribute this load, provides continuous facilitation of group processes and the possibility of individual work with subgroups. In addition, the presence of two presenters demonstrates to

the listeners different models of pedagogical communication, which in itself works to develop the stylistic component of cognitive mobility.

Procedure

Procedure 1. The stage of identifying problems and defining goals (preliminary stage) The pedagogical studio begins with the introduction of teachers to a group of listeners: they identify themselves, read out the topic “Pedagogical Studio as a form of organizing group interaction”, formulate the purpose and objectives of the training session, then explain the essence of the pedagogical studio and remind them of the reasons for the presence of two presenters. This is followed by the exercise “Rules of group interaction” (brainstorming). Students formulate rules of group behavior (“A name is important”, “Rejecting is an offer”, “I am an utterance”, “Regulations”, “Lack of value of judgments”, etc.), fix them on the board and answer reflexive questions (“What are the rules for?”, “Will they work in another group?” and others). The participants are aware of the problem of the lack of agreed norms and define the goal – to create a safe environment for collaboration. At this stage, the reflexive component is activated (understanding one’s own position regarding group norms) and the foundation is laid for the motivational component (interest in collective learning activities). This is followed by a self-presentation procedure implemented in the format of the “Badges” and “Circle of Acquaintances” exercises. Participants are given the right to voluntarily choose the content of the information provided (name, place of residence, position, teaching experience, professional credo, hobbies, preferred sport), and everyone talks about what they want to share. After the verbal presentation, the participants make name badges, thereby visually fixing their professional and personal identity. The goals are specified: each participant understands that he has to remember his colleagues and present his experience. This stage mainly develops the motivational component (interest in pedagogical communication, positive attitude towards the profession) and begins to form a stylistic component (willingness to present oneself, openness).

Procedure 2. Stage of modeling and implementation of models (technological and practical stages). The exercise “Are we so different!?” is conducted in the “inner and outer circle” format. Students in pairs alternately find similarities and differences in professional experience, views, and interests. The exercise allows you to simultaneously realize both individual uniqueness and the presence of common value bases. During it, the stylistic component is actively developing (flexibility, the ability to see an alternative, acceptance of other people’s experience) and the reflexive component continues to develop (assessment of one’s similarities or differences with other participants). The “Guide” exercise models a situation of trust and responsibility: one participant closes his eyes (“blind”), the second leads him (“guide”) through obstacles using only non-verbal communication, which at the level of cognitive mobility corresponds to the development of a stylistic component

(expanding the repertoire of non-verbal and non-standard ways of interaction). Subsequent reflexive questions (“How did you feel about being blind?”, “What contributed to trust?”, “How did the guide feel?”) they deepen the reflexive component. The exercise “Collective Praise” completes the active phase. The participants complete the phrase in a circle.: “I think we’re all doing great today because...” This exercise reinforces the motivational component (positive emotional background, sense of belonging to a group, satisfaction from working together) and at the same time serves as a semantic transition to the final stage of reflection.

Procedure 3. Reflection stage (analytical stage). The “Complete the phrase” technique (“Today the most important thing for me was...”, “Now I feel that the group is...”) is a central reflexive moment. At this stage, the reflexive component of cognitive mobility is purposefully activated. At the same time, the achieved changes are consolidated in the motivational sphere (a sense of belonging to a group, satisfaction from working together) and stylistic (acceptance of a new experience of interaction). The teacher’s summing up is organized in the spirit of cooperative pedagogy – without value judgments, with an emphasis on group and personal progress. The presented set of exercises is minimally sufficient to activate all three components of cognitive mobility in a 6-hour teaching studio. The formation of a temporary training team occurs as an integrative effect of the entire set of exercises, and not as a result of any one of them. Analysis of the results To evaluate the results of the work in the pedagogical studio, the students were offered a questionnaire developed by us, consisting of two blocks. Since the students had already studied together for 2–3 days by the beginning of the studio, but due to the intensive schedule of lectures they had practically no experience of interpersonal interaction, each statement was evaluated twice: retrospectively “before” (to remember themselves and the group before the lesson) and “after” (to assess the state after the studio was completed). Scale for each grade: from 1 (totally disagree) up to 5 (I totally agree). The first block (cognitive mobility) includes six statements. The questions “I am interested in discussing professional topics with colleagues” and “I am ready to learn from others, even if their experience differs from mine” are aimed at assessing the motivational component (interest in communication and willingness to learn from each other). The questions “I’m ready to try non-standard interaction formats” and “I’m ready to change my usual ways of communicating if it’s necessary to work in a group” measure the style component (openness to new experiences and flexibility). The questions “I am aware of my professional habits that may interfere with teamwork” and “I can objectively assess my strengths and weaknesses as a teacher” assess the reflexive component (awareness of my own stereotypes and the ability to self-assess). The second block (temporary study group) contains five statements characterizing group processes. The question “Clear and universally accepted rules have been developed in our group” measures the presence of common norms, “I trusted(a) the other members of the group” – the

level of trust, “There was an atmosphere of mutual assistance in the group” – mutual assistance, “We acted as a single team” – cohesion, “I felt(a) feel comfortable and safe in this group” – psychological safety. All statements are evaluated on the same 5 point scale twice (“before” and “after”). The self-assessment of students in the context of additional adult education is an acceptable indicator of the dynamics of cognitive mobility, since it reflects subjectively perceived changes that form the basis of the reflexive component. 56 students (two study groups) took part in the survey. For each respondent, the difference in average scores “after” minus “before” was calculated for each block and each component. Then the average increments were determined for the entire sample. The results showed that the initial average score for the first block (cognitive mobility) was 2.5. After completing the studio, the average score increased to 4.1, with an average increase of 1.6 points. By components: motivational increased from 2.8 to 4.2 (+1.4), stylistic – from 2.6 to 4.1 (+1.5), reflexive – from 2.2 to 4.0 (+1.8). In the second block (temporary study group), the initial average score was 2.1 (the students practically did not know each other), after the studio it was 4.4, an increase of 2.3 points. The highest final scores were obtained in terms of trust (4.3). The data obtained strongly indicate that the teaching studio contributes to the significant development of all three components of cognitive mobility and effectively forms a temporary learning team in a situation where initially the students were not familiar and had virtually no experience of joint interaction.

Conclusion

The conducted research has shown that the pedagogical studio is an effective condition for the development of cognitive mobility of teachers in the system of additional adult education. The developed scenario made it possible to purposefully activate the motivational, stylistic and reflexive components of cognitive mobility through the implementation of a set of functions (extensive, corrective, predictive, self-developing, intuitive) and principles (voluntariness, self-determination, cooperation, activity, reflexivity and psychological safety). The results of the survey recorded a significant increase in students’ self-esteem in all three components and a high level of formation of the temporary educational staff. In this study, we rely on the theoretical model of cognitive mobility developed by E. A. Poddubskaya [2], but we do not aim to fully implement its methodology. We use only one of the intensive technologies offered by her (the pedagogical studio) and limit ourselves to the stage of students’ adaptation. The diagnostic tools we have proposed also do not claim to be valid for the standardized questionnaire of E. A. Poddubskaya [1] and serve the tasks of descriptive assessment within the framework of this experience. The limitations of this study should be recognized. It is descriptive, not experimental. A retrospective self-assessment was used, reflecting subjectively perceived rather than objectively measured dynamics, and there is no control group, so causal conclusions require additional research. Nevertheless, the results

obtained indicate the fundamental feasibility and potential effectiveness of the proposed scenario. Thus, a pedagogical studio can be recommended for use in the practice of additional adult education when working with heterogeneous groups of students, especially in situations where initially the participants are not familiar and have no experience of joint interaction. A promising area of further work in the framework of this study is the use of a standardized questionnaire “Cognitive mobility of a teacher” (E. A. Poddubskaya) to obtain objective, comparable results with normative data, which will allow us to supplement the descriptive data we have obtained with quantitative indicators of cognitive mobility levels.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE STUDIES ON NON-LANGUAGE FACULTIES FOR THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Abstract: *The organization of independent work for students in higher education institutions in the course of foreign language training is aimed at forming professionally-oriented communicative competence. The implementation of modern information technologies, the use of interactive teaching methods, and the availability of relevant methodological developments ensure the enhancement of motivational and activity aspects of the educational process, as well as lead to positive learning outcomes.*

Keywords: *independent work, communicative professionally-oriented approach, information technologies, interactive teaching methods.*

A distinctive feature of the concept of modern professional education is lifelong learning, as well as creating conditions for the development of personality autonomy in the educational space.

Under personality autonomy, one should understand the learner's ability to independently manage the process of their own learning and take responsibility for planning, the process, and the result of their activities.[4]

Therefore, independent work becomes the foundation for forming the student's professional independence and contributes to more effective mastery of the educational material. It stimulates cognitive and professional interests, supports the realization of the main goal – the formation of communicative competence – and contributes to the growth of students' learning motivation. It is independent work that “forms readiness for self-education, creates a base for continuous education” in conditions of rapid knowledge updates. [1]

In continuous education, independent work, independent access to educational and scientific resources, and self-education technologies become the key factor in

developing the learner's learning independence and achieving the appropriate level of development of these strategies.

It should be noted that many students experience difficulties in standardizing, planning, and organizing their independent work. As the proposed material becomes more complex and learners are introduced to various types of independent work requiring creative search, this skill becomes the main factor determining the success of academic activities. Therefore, the necessity is obvious for universities to start preparing students from the first year for independent task performance and acquiring skills and abilities in their specialty, self-management of their behavior. Independent work is the basis for organizing further self-education of higher education graduates, turning them into a subject of academic and professional activities.

The organization of students' independent work is substantially influenced by two factors:

1) the effectiveness of independent work depends on its organization and implementation in the educational process as a holistic system covering all stages of students' discipline study;

2) the teacher's initiative position, which includes a high level of pedagogical thinking and its criticality; ability and desire for problem-based learning and skill in dialoguing with the student; striving to justify one's views; ability for benevolent assessment of students' knowledge and for self-assessment of one's teaching activities.

The problem of organizing independent work acquires special significance in foreign language study. Actualizing the task of developing communicative language competencies in learners requires changing the approach to organizing independent work. Analysis of foreign language teaching experience in leading higher education institutions, both in Russia and abroad, shows that success in mastering foreign languages to a large extent depends on the formed self-educational competence of learners.

The approach that seems most appropriate to the tasks set before foreign language teachers is the communicative professionally-oriented approach to teaching. According to the main provisions of this approach, teaching should be directed at real language use in life under conditions of solving professional tasks. At the basis of the communicative approach lies the assertion that for effective language use, not only knowledge about various language forms (grammatical, lexical, etc.) is needed, but also their meaning and functional use in specific speech communication situations. An important feature of this approach is its orientation toward the result of the learning activity, rather than the process of forming knowledge, skills, and abilities. This means that from the learner, not a description of the rules for using a language form is required, but its functionally and grammatically correct use in a specific communication situation.

The result of the social and economic reforms taking place in our society has been an increased level of demand for mastering foreign languages. Practical

command of a foreign language is one of the most important characteristics of a specialist of any profile. Consequently, the ultimate goal of foreign language teaching in a higher education institution is for learners to acquire skills in competent use of the foreign language in real life as a means not only of everyday but also of business and professional communication.

Guided by the main postulate of the communicative approach to language study, which states that the goal of teaching is using language in real communication conditions, the teaching process must develop all those professionally-oriented communicative skills that are applied in life. In real communication conditions, communicative skills are not divided into groups, as they are used comprehensively. In the course of learning, it is necessary to separate communicative skills in order to promote their synchronous development and constant control over them.

By the nature of working with information, the following groups of skills are distinguished:

- receptive skills – listening and reading;
- productive skills – speaking and writing.

The goal of the educational process is to ensure the development of the above-mentioned communicative skills, which contributes to the formation of the so-called communicative competence. However, in addition to these skills, it is also necessary to prepare learners for independent work with the language of professional communication, since mastering a foreign language at a university is largely determined by the presence of professional knowledge, which can be actively supplemented through students' independent work at home.

The following goals of applying independent learning activities can be distinguished:

- optimization of the foreign language learning process from the point of view of saving classroom time;
- actualization and activation of the search for new knowledge by learners;
- development of the creative nature of education;
- improving the quality of assimilation of the proposed educational programs.

In this regard, the task of developing learning skills applicable in independent learning activities arises before teaching. To ensure its effectiveness, learners must know how to work with the language, for example, where to find certain reference information, how to improve speech literacy, what methods can be used to memorize new words.

In addition to the importance of independent work for students, it should also be noted that it can be considered a useful technique for the teacher as well, since it helps learners better prepare for each specific task and forms learning skills that find wide application in the course of the educational process.

The use of the Internet in classes makes the language learning process more attractive for students, as they gain access to interesting professionally significant

materials that favorably differ from static outdated texts in the textbook. It provides access to an unlimited amount of authentic information in a foreign language. In addition, the Internet offers diverse communications: email, various conferences, forums, chats, audio-chats, and more; it creates strong motivation for studying a foreign language.

In the process of foreign language teaching, independent educational-cognitive activity is aimed at mastering knowledge and forming skills and abilities in various types of speech activity, the ability to apply them in practice, and taking responsibility for the results of one's work. Such activity is an integral condition for developing cognitive independence as a personal quality of the future specialist.

The basis of independent learning activity is a number of metacognitive strategies, which include various skills: searching and processing information, text processing, planning, control, and evaluation skills of the learning process, ability for reflection, etc. [3]

In foreign language teaching, it is assumed that the development of learning independence in the process of professionally-oriented foreign language teaching is a purposeful, quite dynamic process. It includes teaching rational methods of information extraction, forming general and special skills through a system of specially selected tasks.

Depending on the content and formulation of tasks, as well as the degree of teacher participation in them, students' independent work has a differentiated character. The proposed tasks can be divided into four groups:

- 1) training ones, when the teacher shows the way and nature of task performance;
- 2) practice ones, when the way shown by the teacher is repeated by the student following the model;
- 3) exploratory – the entire task performance is assigned to students: they independently choose the aspect for material analysis;
- 4) creative – independent search, selection, evaluation, and projection of information, its transformation for the purpose of writing an abstract, a conference report, a course work.[3]

The goal of the educational process is to ensure the development of the above-mentioned communicative skills, which contributes to the formation of the so-called communicative competence. However, in addition to these skills, it is also necessary to prepare learners for independent work with the language of the future profession, since mastering a foreign language at a university is largely determined by the presence of professional knowledge, which can be actively supplemented through students' independent work at home.

Another side of the issue of the importance of using independent work is the presence of feedback, that is, control of understanding the received information carried out by the teacher. In this regard, it should be noted that, in addition to

developing a system of homework assignments for implementing learners' independent learning activities, it is also necessary to develop a system of control tasks that allow determining the level of preparation and the degree of mastery of the material proposed for independent study. In addition, it is also possible to use creative tasks such as abstracts, reviews, which will allow concluding about the ability to apply in practice not only the worked-out theoretical material but also the skills and abilities of independent work on it (highlighting the main ideas of the text, their thesis presentation, ability to use examples or visual information, etc.).

In foreign language teaching, ensuring a high degree of activity and independence of all its participants is facilitated by the use of interactive methods. In conditions of professionally-oriented teaching, we use the following interactive teaching methods: business games, disputes, discussions, role-plays, conferences. They simulate those problematic situations that occur in the specialist's professional activity in real conditions.

Students, discussing peers' reports prepared based on foreign publications, with increased activity compare approaches in the professional field in foreign and domestic literature and practice. During the work, students are given the opportunity to realize the goal of such forms of educational activities. Tasks are set for students to learn business communication in a foreign language, conduct a discussion on a given topic, expand their professional outlook based on the acquired knowledge, find independent solutions in new communication situations.

The program of independent work on mastering professionally-oriented foreign language is intended to complement students' classroom work and address the following tasks:

- improving foreign language communication skills and abilities in the socio-domestic sphere and the sphere of professional communication acquired in the classroom under the teacher's guidance;
- acquiring new knowledge, skills, and abilities that ensure the possibility of implementing communicative intentions in a foreign language;
- developing research activity skills using the studied language;
- developing independent learning work skills.

In the course of working on reading texts directly related to the future specialist's professional activity and performing a system of exercises, students develop intellectual-cognitive skills: search, linguistic, information-analytical, creative, reflexive.

The effectiveness of practical classes depends on activating learners' independent activities, on the correct interconnection of individual and group forms of work. Students must not only assimilate a certain amount of knowledge but also learn to acquire it independently. These two sides of the educational process are closely connected. The final stage in developing the totality of students' learning independence skills is the development of creative skills necessary for the future specialist:

- conducting independent search for information for scientific research;
- selecting material for writing course and diploma works;
- making referential translations;
- composing texts for presentations at student scientific conferences and round tables;
- conducting referential review of materials in the process of independent reading of newspapers, magazines found on Internet sites, etc.

Thus, independent work contributes to information saturation, becomes a need and a characteristic feature of the future specialist's professional activity.

Cognitive independence develops through deep and meaningful assimilation by learners of the basics of sciences, mastery of text work skills, and application of acquired knowledge in practical activities. The correctness of statements, of course, depends on the strength of the specialty knowledge acquired by students in their native language. In case of insufficient knowledge, the need arises for independent replenishment of knowledge in the professional field.

Applying independent work skills in practice allows increasing the effectiveness of learning, as it enables the student to master the educational material at a convenient time for them, helps learn to use diverse educational literature and computer technologies for studying a foreign language. Ultimately, the acquired skills of independent learning activity help the learner continue their language education in the sphere of professional activity after graduating from the university. When choosing optimal forms of organizing independent work, the teacher should strive to ensure maximum student motivation. For this, it is necessary to accurately determine the volume of the task and calculate the optimal time for its performance taking into account each student's individual capabilities. An excessive volume of the task and excessively inflated requirements sharply reduce learning motivation.

Stimulating independent research work acts as an effective condition for the development of the future specialist and contributes to the development of the intellectual-cognitive component of the personality's axiological potential. Conferences and seminars are a component of the university's scientific activity, and student participation in a scientific conference helps develop creative abilities, form a system of knowledge necessary for future professional activity, readiness to use them in non-standard situations.

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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE STUDY OF ENGLISH BY MILITARY CADETS: POTENTIAL AND LIMITATIONS

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Abstract. *This article examines the role of electronic educational resources in the development of professional competencies of prospective officers and in enhancing the quality of language instruction within the context of education digitalization. The author analyzes the advantages and limitations of integrating digital technologies into the foreign language learning process cadets of military universities.*

The article identifies and systematizes pedagogical contradictions that arise during the integration of digital technologies in the foreign language training of cadets, as well as methods for optimizing the educational process.

The author emphasizes that the digital environment of educational communication within the ‘teacher – ICT – cadet’ framework does not replace traditional interaction but complements it by expanding didactic opportunities and facilitating the adaptation of the educational process to modern conditions.

Keywords: *English language learning, military universities, digital technologies, electronic educational resources, digital environment, competency-based approach, ICT, professional competencies, foreign language training of cadets.*

In the era of digitalization, the application of electronic educational resources in the English language training of cadets at military universities within the educational process plays a crucial role in the development of professional competencies of future officers and in enhancing the quality of language instruction.

The Government of the Russian Federation adopted the ‘Strategy for the Development of the Information Society in the Russian Federation for 2017–2030,’ which includes the implementation of the priority education project ‘Modern Educational Environment in the Russian Federation’ [1]. As part of the modernization of the military educational system, the digitalization of the educational environment is actively progressing through the integration of digital technologies. Higher military educational institutions have transitioned to electronic textbooks and

teaching aids, implemented the software system ‘Electronic-Digital Educational Resource,’ and ensured cadets’ access to the leading electronic library systems of the Russian Federation [2].

The integration of digital technologies in foreign language learning creates entirely new educational opportunities thanks to the diversity of available tools and resources. However, the realization of this potential is constrained by several objective factors. This article discusses the advantages and limitations of using digital technologies in teaching English to cadets at military higher education institutions.

As Kolesnikova notes, electronic educational resources must comply with several key criteria: ensuring high quality in both aesthetic and technical implementation, containing comprehensive and well-structured information, incorporating effective methodological tools, and providing visual clarity alongside a logically organized sequence of presenting educational material [3].

According to the research of N. V. Goncharova, the use of electronic resources facilitates the enhancement of foreign language learning quality [4]. Zh. Zh. Karbozova further emphasizes that a contemporary teacher must possess competencies in information technologies and be capable of designing electronic educational resources [5].

In international scholarly literature, the integration of digital editions into the higher education process is extensively addressed. For instance, P. Diaz and E. Chain, in collaboration with S. Maynard, conducted a comprehensive analysis of the benefits and limitations of such implementation [6,7]. A distinct research strand focuses on issues related to language learning in digital environments: C. Wang and Y. Liu examined strategies for overcoming the language barrier in online English lessons and found that learners encounter difficulties when completing listening exercises [8].

The analysis of the application of digital technologies in the foreign language preparation of military academy cadets allows for the identification of the following pedagogical contradictions:

- between the didactic potential of digital tools (interactivity, game mechanics, variability of tasks) and the necessity of substantial material and technical resources (computerization of classrooms, provision of cadets with devices).
- between the opportunities presented by digitalization to enhance learning engagement and the risk of diminishing the intensity of face-to-face communication, which is critically important for the development of oral speech.
- between the need for access to a broad spectrum of online resources and the constraints imposed by state secrecy protection requirements.
- between the potential of digital platforms and the risks associated with technical malfunctions and infrastructure instability.
- the contradictions between the learner’s autonomy in the digital environment and the insufficiently developed self-organization skills among some cadets.

Resolving these contradictions requires the development of hybrid learning models that integrate digital tools with traditional forms of interaction and consider the specifics of military-professional preparation.

Table 1. Approaches to resolving contradictions in organizing the foreign language learning process in military universities.

Analysis of contradictions and issues in the system of organizing foreign language training for cadets at military educational institutions.	Approaches to optimizing organizational-methodological contradictions and enhancing the effectiveness of foreign language training in military universities.
Limited provision of computers in classrooms for individual use.	The use of a computer or personal laptop equipped with the necessary software constitutes a mandatory requirement for organizing the educational process.
Attenuating the role of the foreign language teacher to that of a consultant can adversely impact the motivation and engagement of military cadets. The reduction of direct pedagogical interaction creates conditions conducive to communicative gaps and a decline in the level of mutual understanding within the 'teacher – learner' system.	The use of electronic educational resources allows the instructor to effectively facilitate the learning process. Based on the evaluation of completed assignments, the instructor develops individualized educational trajectories for cadets, thereby promoting the adaptation of instruction to their specific needs and level of proficiency.
Limitations of digital resources due to information security measures.	Utilization of digital educational environment resources in military higher educational institutions: interactive whiteboards, media resources, electronic textbooks, and library internet access. Effectiveness of traditional contact teaching methods.
Risk of diminishing intensive live foreign language interaction.	Combine digital resources with traditional methods. Digital technologies should not replace live communication and direct engagement with the instructor. It is important to maintain a balance between online formats and face-to-face instruction where direct interaction is feasible
Insufficient development of self-organization skills among cadets.	Mentoring. Stimulation of independent work. Implementation of innovative methodologies, utilization of electronic textbooks, and organization of targeted group and individual consultations

Currently, there is a transformation of the structural components of the pedagogical system for foreign language instruction, encompassing:

- conceptual foundations;
- target guidelines;
- content of the educational process;
- didactic means;
- forms and types of learning activities.

The contemporary paradigm of higher education is characterized by a transition from a knowledge-based model to a competency-oriented approach. Within the context of foreign language education at universities, this entails not only the formation of communicative and sociocultural competencies and the familiarization of cadets with a foreign-language environment, but also the development of digital literacy:

- abilities to find, select, and critically analyze information resources on the Internet; communication skills employing modern information and communication technologies.

- The transformation of the educational process is accompanied by the emergence of new forms of organizing learning activities:

- slide-based lectures;
- practical classes with interactive presentation of the material.

Simultaneously, the variety of learning tasks and exercises expands, among which the following can be distinguished:

- training and educational tasks;
- preparation of slide presentations;
- information retrieval tasks;
- specifically targeted communicative tasks;
- web projects.

At the same time, the model of educational interaction does not undergo radical changes but is enriched through the integration of information and communication technologies (ICT). A new communication structure emerges in the chain «instructor – ICT – cadet», which leads to the establishment of a digital environment for educational communication. This environment does not replace traditional interaction but complements it, expanding didactic opportunities and ensuring a more flexible adaptation of the educational process to contemporary conditions.

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**MUSICAL ART AS A FACTOR OF PATRIOTIC EDUCATION
OF A PERSON IN DOMESTIC PEDAGOGY:
HISTORY AND MODERNITY**

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Abstract. *In order to preserve the historical and pedagogical heritage of the past, to draw public attention to the problem of developing the theory of music education in a domestic primary school, this article considers the views of domestic teachers of the second half of the 19th – early 20th centuries, who recognized the important role of musical art in the education of national and patriotic feelings. As examples of the continuation and development of the traditions of domestic teachers in the patriotic education of students, the work provides examples of the inclusion of musical art in various forms and directions of educational work from the practice of a modern school.*

Key words: *musical art, patriotic education, primary school, domestic pedagogy, history.*

Modern reality – a period of tension in relations between different countries, natural and man-made disasters, the need to unite Russian society in the face of possible threats, determines the special attention of teachers to the patriotic education of children on the basis of the spiritual and moral values of the peoples of Russia, and national-cultural traditions. In this regard, the appeal to musical art as one of the most important factors in the upbringing of a patriot and a citizen of his country becomes relevant. Studies of historical and pedagogical orientation are of particular value. The second half of the 19th – early 20th centuries was a period when the theory of music education was actively developing in primary school. With the participation of philosophers, teachers, music critics, and methodologists, issues of teaching and raising children through interaction with music were developed, and the influence of musical works on the formation of the personality of future citizens was considered.

Domestic teachers of that time recognized the important role of musical art in the education of national and patriotic feelings. “Education should prepare patriots in

the true sense of the word, i. e. people who love their sovereign and their fatherland above all else”, wrote N. Avenarius [4, p. 64]. However, you can love what you know, therefore, “for the development of patriotism in a person, it is necessary that he get acquainted with Russia from childhood with the help of her folk songs and fairy tales, with the help of stories from her fate and life” [4, p. 64].

According to K. Yelnitsky, the patriotic feeling consists in love for compatriots and the fatherland, and a solemn celebration of days dedicated to the recollection of events that are especially important in the life of the fatherland, as well as “singing songs and studying verbal works expressing a deep sense of devotion and love for the fatherland” [3, p. 55].

The teacher G. Rokov pointed out the need to “expand the bright and high pages of native history and native life” [1, p. 177].

According to the teacher V. F. Dinze, nation, nationality, national consciousness and feeling are words that are especially common. A nation is not only a natural, but also a cultural community that conveys peculiar physical and spiritual qualities, and in various forms of communication – various cultural values. A nation is “a community of character on the basis of a community of fate”. The main sign of a nation is unity [2, p. 10, 12, 15]. Every nation, like a person, strives in its own way to realize in life the highest ideals of truth, life, love and beauty. Every nation has its own special task, the fulfillment of which is its moral duty [2, p. 17].

The tasks of national education, according to V. F. Dinze, are addressed to the people and personality. The first task of national education is to “introduce the whole people to the national culture”, to make great spiritual wealth the property of our children. The second is “in the development of the best sides of the people’s soul”, The main thing at the same time is to study all parties of a national nature, to coordinate all events with them. The third task is to “create national cohesion”, that is, to weaken class isolation and class strife, a strong national connection based on a common culture and activity [2, p. 18].

According to the teacher, Russian youth should “approach” folk life, feel their native way of life [2, from 20]. “Until then, the Russian school will not stand on its own feet, will not take its proper place, will not achieve respect until it remains as indifferent to native sources as it has remained until now”, argued V. F. Dinze [2, p. 20]. In the article “On the National Russian School,” the teacher insisted that education should be upbringing: “the Russian school is obliged not only to educate, but also to bring up” [2, p. 38]. He was sure that the Russian school should not educate “a revolutionary member of the future proletarian family, not a zealous defender of the obsolete general order”, but only “the future Russian citizen and only him,” the ideal is “the Russian school outside politics and parties, outside class aspirations and class claims” [2, p. 38–39].

In the article “National and Heroic in Education,” published in the journal “Bulletin of Knowledge” (1915, No. 1), teacher V. N. Soroka-Rosinsky insisted that in order to educate a national and heroic feeling, it is necessary to turn to music and singing, especially to the folk song sung by grandfathers and great-grandfathers [5, 132]. “It is necessary that the student from an early age hear his native song and get used to be inspired at the sounds of it and feel in himself the blood of his people and everything heroic and high that lurks in the folk soul; it is necessary that the national song accompany all the solemn moments of the student’s life” [5, p. 135],– he urged.

Continuing and developing the traditions of domestic pedagogy, the modern school pays significant attention to musical art as an important factor in the patriotic education of pupils. Among the areas of work – learning and performing patriotic songs about our Motherland, its people, labor exploits; musical works dedicated to the Great Patriotic War and the Great Victory of 1945 during the organization of school festivals, concerts, holidays, literary and musical evenings and performances, during excursions to places of military glory within the framework of the All-Russian military-patriotic program “Victory Roads.”

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SIMULATION OF PROFESSIONAL INTERACTION AS A TOOL FOR TRANSLATOR TRAINING

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Abstract: *The present study addresses the persistent gap between theoretical models of translator training and the realities of professional communicative practice. It explores simulation-based modelling of professional communicative situations as a pedagogical tool for developing sociolinguistic competence in would-be translators. While existing approaches emphasize competence-based frameworks, they often fail to operationalize communicative complexity within classroom settings. The paper proposes a translation-oriented typology of communicative situations based on decision-making processes and introduces a methodological algorithm for implementing simulation-based modelling in university-level translator training. The findings suggest that this approach enhances learners' ability to navigate communicative uncertainty, manage intercultural differences, and make context-sensitive translation decisions. The study contributes to rethinking translator education by shifting the focus from text-based instruction to professionally situated practice.*

Keywords: *sociolinguistic competence, translator education, simulation-based learning, communicative situations, intercultural communication.*

In recent years, translator education has undergone a noticeable shift from a predominantly linguistic paradigm towards a broader competence-based framework that integrates cognitive, technological, and intercultural dimensions. Contemporary research consistently highlights that translation training can no longer be confined to linguistic accuracy alone, but must include the ability to operate within complex communicative environments. For instance, Deyan Zou, Huahui Zhang, Ying Zhao and Piao Xu emphasize that “the development of interpreting expertise involves structured practice in risk awareness, progressive internalisation of decision-making processes, and integration of theoretical knowledge with practical skills” [2, p. 4].

A closer examination of current pedagogical practices reveals a structural inconsistency that continues to affect translator training. On the one hand, educators emphasize the importance of situational and practice-oriented learning. On the other hand, classroom instruction is often based on text exercises that deprive communication of real context. This contradiction has been repeatedly noted in recent research, where communicative and sociolinguistic competences are acknowledged as essential, yet insufficiently implemented in actual teaching practices.

Another issue concerns the limited applicability of existing classifications of communicative situations. Although widely used in language pedagogy, such classifications tend to overlook the operational nature of translation, particularly the role of decision-making under conditions of uncertainty. Modern translator education must incorporate technological and cognitive dimensions, including the ability to manage complexity and ambiguity in real time. Therefore, it should be restructured to incorporate not only linguistic knowledge but also interpersonal and contextual awareness, reflecting the complexity of real communicative interactions. As we can read in the article by Jane Yau “idea of packaging learning content and making it available in a way which enables its reuse in different contexts and for different purposes appears intuitively useful and meaningful” [7, p 5].

For this reason, the present study proposes a refined conceptualization of the communicative situation in translator education. Rather than viewing it as a static set of contextual parameters, a communicative situation is understood here as a dynamic, multi-layered configuration of professional interaction, within which the translator actively negotiates meaning, context, and communicative intent.

This interpretation aligns with the view that intercultural communicative competence involves the integration of contextual, social, and pragmatic. This perspective shifts the focus from language reproduction to decision-making processes, which more accurately reflect professional practice. In the view of Adele D’Arcangelo “an intercultural competent translator is one who demonstrates a high level of intercultural knowledge, skills, attitude and flexibility throughout his or her professional engagements” [1, p 8].

The novelty of the study lies in the development of a translation-oriented typology of communicative situations based on the nature of translation decision-making. Unlike traditional classifications, which are typically created according to external features such as formality or modality, the proposed typology is based on the translator’s cognitive and communicative activity.

From this standpoint, several types of communicative situations can be identified, including regulated, variable, conflict-driven, intercultural, cognitively demanding, and improvisational contexts. Such differentiation is supported by research on interpreting competence, which highlights the importance of managing cognitive load and processing constraints in real-time communication. According to Anthony

Pym, "...we should not use newspaper texts, since they are poor representatives of most real-world translation situations" [6, p 144]. Regulated situations involve highly structured communicative contexts, such as institutional discourse, where accuracy and adherence to norms are paramount. Variable situations introduce elements of unpredictability, requiring adaptive strategies and contextual judgement. Conflict situations are characterized by communicative tension and demand mediation skills beyond literal translation. Situations of intercultural mismatch arise when communicative norms diverge across cultures, requiring sensitivity to implicit meanings and pragmatic conventions. Situations of cognitive overload, often encountered in interpreting, challenge the translator's processing capacity under time pressure. Finally, improvisational situations require immediate decision-making in the absence of preparatory information. This typology reflects a broader trend in translation studies, where competence is increasingly viewed as a complex and dynamic construct shaped by multiple interacting factors, including cognition, context, and technology.

Methodologically, the study builds on simulation-based modelling as a means of recreating professional activity within an educational setting. This perspective is consistent with González-Davies' concept of situated learning, which emphasizes the importance of embedding learning processes in authentic communicative contexts. Additionally, González-Davies and Enríquez-Raído emphasize that "students actively involved in translation research tend to exhibit higher confidence levels and stronger analytical skills compared to those who learn through conventional methods" [3]. Similarly, Lance Hewson underlines the role of creativity and problem-solving in translator training, particularly in situations requiring non-standard solutions [4].

However, it is important to note that simulation is often misunderstood as merely a form of role-play. In contrast, this study conceptualizes simulation-based modelling as a structured pedagogical system that integrates contextual authenticity, role distribution, problem-solving, and reflective analysis.

The proposed methodological algorithm for implementation consists of several interconnected stages. Initially, instructors identify and design communicative scenarios that reflect authentic professional contexts. This is followed by a preparatory phase, during which students engage with relevant linguistic, thematic, and cultural material. The core stage involves the reconstruction of simulated situations, where students assume professional roles and engage in real-time translation tasks. Subsequently, a reflective phase allows for critical evaluation, peer discussion, and instructor feedback. Finally, students are encouraged to transfer acquired skills to new and more complex communicative contexts. Moreover, collaborative learning plays a key role in enhancing both professional competence and learner autonomy. At the same time, the integration of digital tools responds to the increasing

technological demands of the profession, as highlighted in studies on translation technology and cognitive load. Jean Nitzke, Anke Tardel & Silvia Hansen-Schirra claim that “these would include translation-related skills including the incorporation of machine translation into existing work environments, and the handling and storage of training data, handling human-machine interaction etc.” [5, p. 294].

Such an approach aligns with recent developments in translator and interpreter education, which emphasize experiential learning and active engagement as key drivers of competence development. In particular, simulation-based and collaborative learning environments have been shown to enhance both linguistic performance and professional awareness, while also revealing gaps in traditional training models.

An additional aspect that cannot be overlooked is the role of digital technologies in shaping contemporary translation practice. With the increasing integration of AI tools and remote communication platforms, translators are required to manage not only linguistic complexity but also technological and cognitive demands. Recent research highlights that modern translator training must incorporate these elements in order to remain relevant and effective.

At this stage, it is worth recognizing the limitations of the proposed approach. Although simulation provides a more realistic view of professional activity, its implementation requires significant methodological training and experience of the teacher. Without careful design, there is a risk that simulation tasks may turn out to be superficial and will not be able to reflect the depth of real communicative interaction. This suggests that further empirical research is needed to clarify both the typology and the methodological framework.

In conclusion, the study argues that the effectiveness of translator training depends on the extent to which educational practices reflect the complexity of real-world communication. The findings of this study suggest that the effectiveness of translator education depends not merely on the acquisition of linguistic knowledge, but on the extent to which training environments replicate the complexity of real communicative practice. In this regard, simulation-based modelling emerges as a particularly promising approach, as it enables the integration of cognitive, sociolinguistic, and professional dimensions within a unified pedagogical framework. By reconceptualising communicative situations as dynamic, decision-driven configurations, the study offers a shift away from static and text-centered instructional models. The proposed translation-oriented typology highlights the central role of decision-making under varying degrees of uncertainty, thereby aligning training practices more closely with the realities of professional translation. This perspective contributes to ongoing discussions in translation studies, where competence is increasingly viewed as a situated and adaptive construct rather than a fixed set of skills. At the same time, the study underscores that the pedagogical value of simulation-based modelling is contingent upon its methodological rigor.

Poorly designed simulations risk reducing complex communicative processes to superficial role-play, thereby undermining their educational potential. This indicates a need for carefully structured implementation, supported by clear learning objectives, authentic scenarios, and systematic reflection. It should also be acknowledged that the present study is primarily theoretical in nature. While the proposed typology and methodological framework offer a conceptual basis for improving translator training, further empirical research is required to validate their effectiveness across different educational contexts. In particular, future studies could explore the impact of simulation-based learning on specific components of translator competence, including decision-making speed, pragmatic accuracy, and intercultural sensitivity. In a broader perspective, the study contributes to the ongoing transformation of translator education in response to global and technological changes. As professional translation increasingly involves multimodal communication, digital tools, and collaborative environments, training models must evolve accordingly. Simulation-based approaches, especially when combined with digital technologies, have the potential to bridge the gap between academic instruction and professional practice, thus supporting the development of adaptable and context-aware translators. Ultimately, the integration of simulation-based modelling into translator education can be seen not simply as a methodological innovation, but as part of a broader paradigm shift – from knowledge transmission to professional formation.

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CASE STUDY TECHNOLOGY IN HIGHER EDUCATION: BUILDING COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE EDUCATIONAL PSYCHOLOGISTS

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Abstract: *This study explores the role of case study technology in the formation of professional competencies of future educational psychologists in higher education. The modern educational paradigm requires specialists who are not only theoretically prepared but also capable of solving real-life professional problems. Case study technology is considered an effective pedagogical tool that integrates theory and practice, promotes critical thinking, and develops decision-making skills. The research employed a mixed-method approach, including surveys, observation, and experimental teaching. The results demonstrate that the use of case studies significantly enhances students' professional competencies, particularly analytical, communicative, and reflective skills. The findings confirm the effectiveness of case-based learning in preparing competitive educational psychologists.*

Keywords: *case study technology, professional competencies, educational psychology, higher education, competence-based approach*

The rapid transformation of contemporary higher education is driven by globalization, digitalization, and the increasing complexity of professional environments. In this context, the traditional knowledge-based model of education is being replaced by a competence-based paradigm that emphasizes the development of practical skills, critical thinking, and professional adaptability. This shift is particularly significant in the field of educational psychology, where future specialists are expected to address multifaceted challenges related to students' cognitive, emotional, and social development within diverse educational settings.

Educational psychologists play a crucial role in ensuring the psychological well-being and academic success of learners. Their professional responsibilities include diagnosing learning difficulties, supporting students' psychological

development, collaborating with teachers and parents, and creating safe and inclusive educational environments. Therefore, the preparation of future educational psychologists requires not only a solid theoretical foundation but also the ability to apply knowledge effectively in real-life situations.

However, numerous studies highlight a gap between theoretical training and practical readiness among graduates of higher education institutions. Traditional lecture-based instruction often limits students' opportunities to engage with real-world professional scenarios, resulting in insufficient development of essential competencies such as problem-solving, communication, and decision-making. This challenge necessitates the integration of innovative pedagogical technologies that promote active learning and experiential engagement.

One of the most effective approaches in this regard is case study technology. Originating from business and legal education, the case study method has been widely adopted in various disciplines due to its capacity to simulate authentic professional situations. Case study technology involves the analysis of real or hypothetical scenarios that require students to identify problems, evaluate alternative solutions, and make informed decisions. This method fosters deeper understanding, encourages collaborative learning, and enhances the ability to transfer theoretical knowledge into practice.

In the context of educational psychology, case study technology is particularly relevant because it reflects the complexity and variability of real educational environments. Through case-based learning, students can explore issues such as classroom behavior management, psychological safety, inclusive education, and parent–teacher interaction. Moreover, this approach contributes to the development of reflective thinking, allowing future specialists to critically evaluate their actions and continuously improve their professional practice.

Despite the recognized advantages of case study technology, its implementation in the training of educational psychologists remains insufficiently explored, especially in terms of its impact on the formation of professional competencies. There is a need for systematic research that examines how case-based learning influences key competency domains, including analytical, communicative, and reflective skills.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of case study technology in building the professional competencies of future educational psychologists in higher education. The research seeks to answer the following questions:

- (1) How does case study technology influence the development of professional competencies?
- (2) Which specific competencies are most affected by case-based learning?
- (3) What are the pedagogical conditions necessary for the successful implementation of case study technology?

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to the modernization of higher education practices and the improvement of professional training in educational psychology. By providing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of case study technology, the study aims to support the development of more practice-oriented, student-centered educational models that prepare competent and competitive specialists for the demands of contemporary educational systems.

The transition to a competence-based model of education has become a central trend in modern pedagogical science. Professional competence is generally understood as an integrated system of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and personal qualities that enable effective performance in a specific professional context (Mulder, 2014). In the field of educational psychology, competencies encompass not only theoretical knowledge of psychological principles but also practical abilities such as assessment, intervention, communication, and reflective practice.

Scholars emphasize that the development of professional competencies requires learning environments that simulate real-life situations and encourage active student participation. According to David A. Kolb (1984), effective learning occurs through experience, reflection, conceptualization, and experimentation. His experiential learning theory provides a strong theoretical foundation for interactive teaching methods, including case study technology. Similarly, Lee S. Shulman (1992) highlighted the importance of case-based instruction in teacher education, arguing that cases help bridge the gap between theory and practice by presenting complex, context-dependent situations.

Case study technology has its origins in business education, particularly at Harvard Business School, where it was developed as a method for preparing students to deal with real-world managerial challenges. Over time, this approach has been adapted to various disciplines, including medicine, law, and education. Robert K. Yin (2014) defines case study as an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident.

In educational research, case study technology is closely related to problem-based learning (PBL) and inquiry-based approaches. John R. Savery (2006) argues that such methods promote self-directed learning, critical thinking, and collaborative problem-solving. These skills are essential for future educational psychologists, who must navigate complex interpersonal and institutional dynamics.

Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of case-based learning in developing key competencies. For example, Biggs (1996) introduced the concept of constructive alignment, emphasizing that teaching methods should align with intended learning outcomes. Case study technology aligns well with this principle, as it allows students to actively engage with learning objectives through practical tasks. Furthermore, research indicates that case-based learning enhances higher-order cognitive skills, including analysis, synthesis, and evaluation.

In the context of educational psychology, the application of case study technology has gained increasing attention. Irina A. Baeva emphasizes the importance of psychological safety in educational environments and highlights the need for future specialists to develop competencies related to risk assessment, conflict resolution, and supportive communication. Case-based scenarios provide an effective means of exploring such issues in a controlled learning environment.

Moreover, recent studies underline the role of case study technology in fostering reflective practice. Reflection is considered a key component of professional competence, enabling individuals to analyze their experiences, identify strengths and weaknesses, and improve their performance. Case-based learning encourages students to reflect on their decisions and consider alternative perspectives, thereby enhancing their professional development.

Despite the growing body of literature supporting the use of case study technology, several challenges remain. These include the need for well-designed case materials, the requirement for trained instructors, and the difficulty of assessing competency development. Additionally, there is limited research focusing specifically on the formation of competencies among future educational psychologists, particularly in the context of higher education systems undergoing rapid transformation.

In summary, the literature indicates that case study technology is a powerful pedagogical tool for developing professional competencies. It integrates theoretical knowledge with practical application, promotes active and student-centered learning, and supports the development of critical and reflective thinking. However, further empirical research is needed to explore its effectiveness in specific educational contexts and to identify optimal conditions for its implementation in the training of future educational psychologists.

This study employed a mixed-method research design combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the effectiveness of case study technology in developing professional competencies of future educational psychologists. A quasi-experimental design was used, involving both experimental and control groups, which allowed for comparison of learning outcomes under different instructional conditions.

The research was conducted in three stages:

1. Diagnostic stage – identification of the initial level of students' professional competencies;
2. Formative stage – implementation of case study technology in the educational process;
3. Control stage – evaluation of the effectiveness of the intervention and comparison of results.

The study involved undergraduate students majoring in educational psychology at a higher education institution.

- Total number of participants: 60 students
- Experimental group: 30 students (case study-based instruction)
- Control group: 30 students (traditional teaching methods)

Participants were selected using purposive sampling to ensure similar academic backgrounds and levels of prior knowledge. All participants were informed about the research objectives and provided consent.

To assess the formation of professional competencies, a set of complementary research instruments was used:

- Questionnaires – to measure students’ perceptions of their competency development;
- Competency assessment tests – to evaluate analytical, communicative, and decision-making skills;
- Observation protocols – to monitor student engagement and behavior during learning activities;
- Reflective journals – to assess the development of reflective competence;
- Expert evaluation – instructors assessed students’ performance based on pre-defined criteria.

The instruments were designed based on the competence-based approach and aligned with key competency domains relevant to educational psychology.

The experimental group was taught using case study technology integrated into the curriculum over one academic semester. The instructional process included: analysis of real and simulated psychological-pedagogical cases; group discussions and collaborative problem-solving; role-playing activities (e.g., psychologist–student, psychologist–parent interactions); development of intervention strategies for specific cases; presentation and defense of proposed solutions.

Each case was structured to reflect real-life professional situations, including issues such as student behavioral problems, psychological safety, communication with parents, and inclusive education.

In contrast, the control group received traditional instruction based on lectures, textbook analysis, and standard assignments without case-based activities.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including: percentage analysis; mean score comparison; pre-test and post-test evaluation.

Qualitative data from reflective journals and observations were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify patterns related to competency development.

The level of professional competencies was assessed according to the following criteria: Analytical competence – ability to identify and analyze problems; Communicative competence – ability to interact effectively with students, teachers, and parents; Decision-making competence – ability to propose and justify solutions; Reflective competence – ability to evaluate one’s own actions and outcomes.

Each competency was evaluated at three levels: low, medium, high.

The study adhered to ethical research standards. Participation was voluntary, and confidentiality of participants' data was ensured. Students were informed about the purpose of the research and had the right to withdraw at any stage.

The analysis of the experimental data demonstrated a positive impact of case study technology on the development of professional competencies among future educational psychologists. A comparative assessment of the experimental and control groups was conducted at the diagnostic (pre-test) and control (post-test) stages.

At the initial stage, both groups showed relatively similar levels of competency development, with the majority of students demonstrating a medium level across all assessed competencies. This confirmed the comparability of the groups prior to the intervention.

After the implementation of case study technology in the experimental group, significant changes were observed.

Changes in competency levels (Experimental Group):

- The proportion of students with a high level of analytical competence increased from 20% to 45%;
- Communicative competence improved from 25% to 55%;
- Decision-making competence increased from 18% to 46%;
- Reflective competence rose from 22% to 50%.

At the same time, the percentage of students with a low level of competencies decreased considerably in all categories.

In contrast, the control group demonstrated only minor improvements:

- average increase of 5–10% across competencies;
- no significant shift from medium to high levels.

These findings indicate that traditional teaching methods have limited effectiveness in fostering higher-order professional competencies compared to case-based learning.

A comparison of post-test results between the two groups highlights the advantages of case study technology: Students in the experimental group demonstrated stronger problem analysis skills, showing the ability to identify key issues and underlying causes in complex educational situations; They exhibited higher levels of communication competence, particularly in simulated interactions with students and parents; Their decision-making abilities were more structured and evidence-based; Reflective journals revealed deeper self-analysis and professional awareness.

The improvement in competencies can be attributed to the active and practice-oriented nature of case study technology, which engages students in real-life problem-solving processes.

The results of this study confirm the effectiveness of case study technology as a pedagogical tool for competency development in higher education. The findings are consistent with the principles of experiential learning proposed by David A. Kolb, which emphasize learning through experience and reflection. Case-based learning

creates conditions where students actively construct knowledge by engaging with authentic professional situations.

Furthermore, the results support the concept of constructive alignment introduced by John Biggs, as case study activities align closely with intended learning outcomes related to professional competence. Students are not passive recipients of information but active participants in the learning process.

The significant improvement in communicative and reflective competencies highlights the social and interactive nature of case study technology. This is particularly important in educational psychology, where professional success depends on effective interpersonal communication and the ability to understand diverse perspectives.

Another important finding is the role of case study technology in bridging the gap between theory and practice. Students reported that working with real-life scenarios helped them better understand how theoretical concepts are applied in professional contexts. This supports previous research indicating that case-based learning enhances the transfer of knowledge to practical situations.

In addition, the use of case studies contributed to increased student motivation and engagement. The interactive format encouraged collaboration, discussion, and critical thinking, creating a dynamic learning environment. However, several challenges were identified during the implementation: the need for carefully designed and context-relevant case materials; the requirement for instructor training in facilitating case discussions; time constraints in covering extensive case analyses within limited class hours.

Despite these challenges, the overall results indicate that the benefits of case study technology outweigh its limitations. The findings of this study have important implications for higher education: Case study technology should be systematically integrated into educational psychology curricula; Educators should be trained in designing and implementing case-based learning; Institutions should develop repositories of case materials relevant to local educational contexts; Assessment systems should be adapted to evaluate competency development rather than only theoretical knowledge.

The present study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of case study technology in the formation of professional competencies of future educational psychologists in higher education. The findings clearly demonstrate that integrating case-based learning into the educational process significantly enhances students' professional readiness and competency development.

The results confirm that case study technology is a powerful pedagogical tool that facilitates the transition from theoretical knowledge to practical application. Students who participated in case-based learning showed substantial improvement in key competency domains, including analytical thinking, communication, decision-making, and reflective skills. These competencies are essential for educational

psychologists, whose professional activity requires the ability to address complex psychological and pedagogical challenges in real educational settings.

One of the most important contributions of this study is the evidence that case study technology promotes active, student-centered learning. It encourages learners to engage in problem-solving, collaborate with peers, and critically evaluate different perspectives. As a result, students develop not only cognitive skills but also personal and social competencies that are crucial for their future professional roles.

Furthermore, the study highlights the role of case-based learning in bridging the gap between theory and practice. By working with real-life or simulated professional situations, students gain a deeper understanding of how theoretical concepts are applied in practice. This experiential approach increases motivation, enhances engagement, and prepares students for real-world professional tasks.

Despite its effectiveness, the implementation of case study technology requires certain pedagogical conditions. These include the development of high-quality case materials, the training of instructors in facilitation techniques, and the allocation of sufficient time for in-depth case analysis. Addressing these challenges will further enhance the impact of case-based learning in higher education. In conclusion, the integration of case study technology into the training of future educational psychologists is both necessary and beneficial. It aligns with modern educational trends focused on competence-based learning and contributes to the preparation of highly qualified, competitive, and adaptable specialists.

Future research should explore the long-term effects of case-based learning, its integration with digital technologies, and its application in different cultural and educational contexts. Additionally, further studies may focus on expanding the range of competencies assessed and developing standardized tools for evaluating competency development.

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**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING INTEGRATIVE CONTEXTUAL
TASKS IN TEACHING BIOLOGY AT SCHOOL
FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC LITERACY**

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Abstract. *The article addresses the theoretical and methodological foundations for the development of scientific literacy (ENG), which constitutes a component of functional literacy within the education system. The study is conducted on the basis of the conceptual principles and approaches to the assessment of international comparative studies, specifically the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). The author proposes a methodological system for the design and implementation of integrative contextual tasks aimed at the development of scientific literacy in the process of teaching biology in general education schools.*

The purpose of the article is the scientific substantiation and development of a theoretical model of a methodological system for the formation of scientific literacy, founded on the organization of activities involving the solution of integrative contextual tasks in biology lessons at general education schools. Integrative contextual tasks combine subject-specific, interdisciplinary, and metasubject content, thereby reinforcing scientific

Keywords: *school biology, student, integrative contextual tasks, scientific literacy, biology teaching methodology.*

Introduction

At the contemporary stage of societal development, human potential constitutes a significant factor in the socio-economic growth of the country. As a component of functional literacy, scientific literacy (ENG) provides strategies for addressing problems associated with substance extraction technologies, energy, ecology, medicine, and various other fields. Society is interested in school graduates who possess scientific literacy, that is, the ability to utilize and enhance existing scientific knowledge and skills. [1]

The development of ENG in biology lessons, which are a component of the discipline ‘Natural Sciences,’ represents a response to evolving social demands and serves as a priority educational objective aimed at quality education and functional literacy. These authoritative studies define the level of functional literacy in schools through the acquisition by adolescents of competencies such as scientific explanation of phenomena, understanding of the characteristics of the natural sciences, data interpretation, and the use of scientific evidence for drawing conclusions. [2] Moreover, the existing valid set of tasks does not provide a sufficient number of assignments to ensure the organization of the development of ENG. [3]

Teaching biology at all stages of secondary school education. Furthermore, such tasks are primarily aimed at assessing the development of functional literacy rather than organizing instruction to achieve discipline-specific outcomes and the development of scientific literacy. The methodology for working with such tasks in biology lessons is practically absent, which creates difficulties in fostering scientific literacy in biology education at the secondary school level. The change in the above-mentioned target benchmarks determines the relevance and timeliness of addressing the problem of scientifically substantiating methods for the development of scientific literacy in biology education. [4]

Materials and Methods

The processes of globalization in the 21st century, the ecological crisis, climate change, and the advancement of biotechnology and genetics place new demands on the education system. The cultivation of an individual capable of responding to these global challenges, critically analyzing information, understanding other

cultures, and making reasoned decisions is one of the principal aims of the contemporary school.

According to the OECD (2018), global competence consists of four main components:

1. knowledge of global and local problems;
2. openness to the perspectives of others and intercultural understanding;
3. effective interaction with others;
4. skills of rational behavior [5]

The emphasis of PISA research on the global assessment of competencies since 2018 has exerted a considerable influence on the education system [6]. In this regard, the biology subject encompasses content that enables students to comprehend significant global issues such as life, ecology, the environment, health, and genetics. [7] Although the existing literature aims to establish a more precise conceptual framework of the term and to assess scientific literacy among students of various age groups, the school-level factors that facilitate the further development of scientific literacy among the younger generation remain unclear in terms of how they contribute to [8] the acquisition of relevant 21st-century skills through the education system. Specifically, determining methods for development within the Kazakhstani context holds practical significance, given its unique geopolitical role in Eurasia and its diverse ecological environment. [9] To examine the factors influencing the scientific literacy of Kazakhstani schoolchildren, the present study conducts regression analysis utilizing PISA 2018 data, disaggregating factors at the levels of students and educational institutions; the analysis of literacy assessment results is performed in two stages. The results of the analysis indicate that factors at both the individual and school levels significantly affect the extent to which students have acquired scientific literacy [10].

At present, significant transformations are being implemented within the educational process, accompanied by updates to the educational content. In the era of globalization, the priority lies not only in cultivating a literate individual who actively engages in the learning process, possesses the capacity for creative and autonomous decision-making, and effectively applies acquired knowledge in life, but also in establishing favorable conditions to facilitate this. This is reflected in the State Program for the Development of Education and Science of Kazakhstan for 2020–2025, which sets forth objectives to enhance the global competitiveness of Kazakh education and science, and to nurture and educate individuals grounded in universal human values [11]. Boix Mansilla & Jackson, OECD, and Reimers place primary emphasis on students' engagement with global issues and the development of functional, activity-oriented scientific literacy. [12] Andreotti, Banks – examines this competence based on social justice, multiculturalism, and critical thinking. [13]

While Fantini proposes comprehensive approaches, such as self-assessment, monitoring, and testing, OECD – PISA instruments [14] allow for the evaluation of cognitive, affective, and social components. [15]

To address the tasks set, the following research methods were employed: theoretical methods, including the analysis of psychological-pedagogical and methodological literature concerning the research problem; methodological analysis of the concept of the state educational standard and PISA, programs, and educational texts; theoretical modeling of the methodological system for the formation of scientific literacy (ENG) through the implementation of integrative contextual tasks in biology lessons at the basic school; empirical: experimental work, methodological modeling and explanation of results; methods of qualitative and quantitative analysis of experimental data: dispersion and correlation analysis, ranking, and graphical representation of results.

Approaches to the tasks of monitoring and assessing the development of scientific literacy (ENG) as a conceptual basis for integrative contextual tasks are examined, and a theoretical model of the methodological system for the development of natural science literacy through the use of integrative contextual tasks to foster ENG in biology education at secondary schools is proposed.

Results and Discussion

The reliability of the research findings was determined by the reproducibility of the described experiment, the validity of the employed methods and their alignment with the research objectives, the substantiation of conclusions based on the analysis of scientific literature, the evidential support from control and experimental groups, and the statistical treatment of the obtained results.

The empirical stage of the study involved 1003 teachers specializing in science and mathematics and 4286 students from grades 8–9 of secondary schools. Using survey methods, the social demand for the development of scientific literacy competencies was confirmed, and the need for tasks integrated into the current curriculum for formative purposes in biology lessons was identified (Figures 1, 2).

Teachers require a method for independently composing such tasks based on the concept of a specific lesson and ENG assessment methods that do not necessitate expert judgment. The expert survey addressed the criteria for assessing the level of development of ENG, and the responses were processed using a rating method: the frequency of criterion ratings was evaluated according to their significance, enabling the assessment of critical weighting coefficients. To demonstrate the validity of the proposed set of tools, the evaluation was conducted using two approaches: 1) based on the PISA methodology and 2) based on the developed system of criteria. For the sample utilized, the Spearman's coefficient was 0.54, corresponding to an 'observed' correlation strength according to Chaddock's scale. The statistical significance of the correlation coefficient was determined by means of the π -test.

Figure 1 – Results of the survey of students in grades 8–9 of schools in Almaty.

Figure 2 – Results of the Survey of Subject Teachers of ENG (Natural Science and Mathematical Fields) in Schools of Almaty

Table 1 – Scale for monitoring the level of formation of ENG

Indicators of Integral Values	15–13	12–10	9–7	6–3	3–0
Level of Scientific Literacy Development	High Level	Above	Average	Basic	Below Basic

The level of scientific literacy development of participants in the experimental study was recorded separately according to individual criteria and as an integral indicator. The statistically verified reliability of similarity permitted classification of the 'a' parallels of grades 8 and 9 as the control group, and the 'b' parallels as the experimental group. 8th-grade students participated for two years, whereas 9th-grade students participated for one year.

Figure 3 – Results of the final assessment of scientific literacy of 8th-grade students in the control and experimental groups.

Figure 4 – Results of the final assessment of scientific literacy of 9th-grade students in the control and experimental groups.

The sample comprised 120 participants. During the control period, all criteria and the integral indicator of scientific literacy formation were compared between the control and experimental groups (Figures 3, 4), and the dynamics of changes in the integral indicator were determined in the group engaged in experimental work

over two years in grades 8 and 9. The comparison of empirical and critical values of the Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney criterion confirms the 95% significance of differences in the compared samples for the four identified criteria and the integral indicator of ENG development.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results presented in this dissertation study represent a consistent resolution of the stated objectives, confirm the proposed hypothesis and defended provisions, and also summarize the following:

The methodology for constructing integrative contextual tasks, taking into account the lesson topic and its intended outcomes, as well as a set of integrative contextual tasks for the development of scientific literacy in the natural sciences through biology instruction in grades 8–9, can be applied in educational practice to foster ENG in biology education within general education schools;

For the development of students' scientific literacy, the proposed methods for working with integrative contextual tasks in biology lessons have been implemented in educational practice and may be employed in the training of students in biological-pedagogical specialties and fields at the pedagogical university, as well as for the substantive updating of academic disciplines within the framework of teacher retraining and professional development programs;

The methodology for assessing the level of scientific literacy, grounded in specific criteria, can be employed in educational practice for ongoing, periodic, and final assessment of the development of scientific literacy in secondary school biology instruction.

The results of the experimental work confirmed the validity of the proposed hypothesis. The objective of the study has been achieved, and the set tasks have been fully accomplished.

The results of this study can be applied to both basic and advanced biology teaching in secondary schools. The development of a methodology for constructing integrative contextual tasks based on the theme of a specific lesson and its intended outcomes, as well as methods for organizing learning activities founded on the solution of tasks within a Unified Natural System of biology teaching in educational practice; updating the content of academic disciplines at the pedagogical university in the training of students in biological-pedagogical specialties and fields; and can be utilized for the advanced training and professional development of teachers.

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PROFESSOR LUDWIG ALEKSEEVICH CHIBIROV ABOUT A SCIENTIST WITH A GUIDING GIFT.

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Annotation. *This article is a review of the book “A Thinker with a Guiding Gift (In Memory of V.I. Abaev)” by renowned Russian ethnologist and historian Professor Ludwig Alekseevich Chibirov (Tskhinvali, House of Printing of the Republic of South Ossetia, 2026). Chibirov dedicated the book to the memory of Vasily Ivanovich Abaev, a distinguished linguist, Iranologist, etymologist, folklorist, Nart scholar, epic scholar, and Ossetian scholar. The author believes that the success of this newly published publication is predictable and is largely due to the emotional, intellectual, and documentary memory Chibirov has carried through the years of his colleague and friend, who contributed to the study of ethnogenesis, spiritual culture, the Nart epic, ethnic worldview, and the cultural and everyday characteristics of Ossetian ethnocultural contacts. The evidence preserved for posterity of decades of friendship and fruitful scientific collaboration between these two luminaries of Ossetian studies also allows us to clearly see the outstanding guiding gift of V.I. Abaev, the influence of his extraordinary personality and scientific creativity on the formation and direction of regional cultural and scientific trends and preferences.*

Keywords: *L. A. Chibirov, V. I. Abaev, Ossetian studies, cooperation, memory, scientific heritage.*

L. A. Chibirov is a distinguished scholar whose every study and publication naturally commands gratitude, admiration, and respect. The authority of these works among both scholars and the widest readership remains consistently high. The beginning of the current year was marked by the publication of his latest book, *The Thinker with the Gifts of a Mentor (In Memory of V. I. Abaev)*, dedicated to the outstanding Ossetian scholar V. I. Abaev – the recognized patriarch of etymology, Iranian studies, folklore studies, and Nartology (2).

Previously, on the occasion of V. A. Abaev’s 100th anniversary, L. A. Chibirov published a collection of memoirs titled ‘Encounters with Vaso Abaev’ (5), and ten years later this work, revised and expanded, was published as part of the essay

collection 'Names' (3; 4). Positive responses to these publications, along with the sustained and even growing interest in the personality of the outstanding Iranist, his biography, way of life, and the need for a deeper understanding of his legacy, led L. A. Chibirov to conceive a new book about the scholar, which he entitled 'The Thinker with the Mentor's Gifts'.

As a specialist, L. A. Chibirov perceived and deeply comprehended the role, status, and significance of V. I. Abaev both in national scholarship and in the ethnocultural and scientific context of Ossetia. For several decades, they maintained a friendly correspondence, and during their personal meetings, they consistently addressed questions concerning the language of ethnogenesis, ancient history, and the cultural heritage of the Ossetians. V. I. Abaev and L. A. Chibirov were not merely professional collaborators; they were close family friends, which is why the memories, letters, photographs, and documents related to the scholar's life and work were collected and carefully preserved by the author of the book over many decades. All these materials were compiled together with research articles in which L. A. Chibirov illuminates the milestones of the scholar's scientific career and his contributions to linguistics, folklore studies, ethnography, the ethnic worldview, and ethno-cultural contacts of the Ossetians.

In the first section of the book, devoted to the scientific legacy of Vasily Ivanovich, the author outlines the scholar's views on key issues within the humanities of Ossetian studies, conveys the essence of his approaches to addressing these problems, demonstrates the broad scope of his research interests, and emphasizes the significant value of his contributions to solving the principal challenges of ancient history, ethnogenesis, and the spiritual and material culture of the Ossetian people. Special emphasis is placed on the scientific novelty of the issues first developed by the scholar: the Scythian-Alan-Ossetian linguistic continuity, the identification of the oldest homeland of the Iranian-speaking ancestors of the Alan-Ossetians, the directions of their movements during the Great Migration Period, as well as the language, narrative motifs, cyclicity, time of origin, and historical foundation of the Nart sagas.

In addition to providing the reader with a detailed analysis of V. I. Abaev's contribution to scientific Ossetology, the book presents the image of a man of high moral and ethical qualities and extensive scientific erudition – an exemplar of an ideal personality. The content of the first article in the section 'His Ideal Was a Bright Image of Freedom (On the Early Spiritual Maturity of Vasso Abaev)' opens how the spiritual and moral formation, the choice of scientific preferences, and the shaping of the scholar's personality took place during his adolescence and youth, when he studied at the First Tiflis Classical Gymnasium and later at Petrograd University.

In the article entitled 'V. I. Abaev's Views on Certain Issues of Ossetian Studies,' L. A. Chibirov speaks of him not only as a coryphaeus of Ossetian studies but also describes his perception of him as a person, as an individual: 'Like many of my

colleagues, I came to Vasily Ivanovich Abaev through his works; the deeper I immersed myself in them, the more they fascinated me' (2, 27). Here he also outlines the core of the discussions and conversations on Ossetian studies that Abaev held in his presence: about the necessity of studying the Gujaret Ossetians, who were later expelled from their traditional settlements by Gamsakhurdia's bands; about the origins of the Ksani eristavs, traced to the Bibilov family name; about the hypothesis concerning the Ossetian roots of the Bagrationi dynasty; about the significance of V. F. Miller's 'Ossetian Etudes' for Ossetian culture, and so on.

L. A. Chibirov highlights the principled stance characteristic of V. I. Abaev when addressing discrepancies with scientific truth (particularly regarding the folk etymology of certain toponyms), his benevolent attitude toward and advice for young authors (notably, the recommendation conveyed through L. A. Chibirov to A. Kozaev to include aphorisms of Sanat Sem and other Ossetian sages when republishing the book "Anacharsis"), his concern for the preservation of archaeological heritage, and the necessity of constructing a dedicated museum building for the exhibits of the Tli Bronze Age culture.

An important thesis of the scholar, articulated in an article and conveyed during an oral discussion with L. A. Chibirov, states that '...we err significantly when, in studying the history of the settlement of our ethnos, we confine ourselves to the territorial boundaries of modern Ossetia.' Specifically, when studying the pre-Mongol period, it is necessary to adopt a broader perspective and examine a larger territory: the object of study should not be Ossetia, but the territory of Alania" (2, 32).

An indisputable humanistic message is also conveyed by the episode describing Vasily Ivanovich's sharp reaction to the flagrant ban imposed in the early 1980s by the circle around the then First Secretary of the North Ossetian Regional Committee of the CPSU on the publication in North Ossetia of V. A. Kuznetsov's monograph *Essays on the History of the Alans*: 'In large part thanks to the intervention of V. I. Abaev, six months later Kuznetsov's book appeared in the republic's bookstores' (2, 32).

And finally, I cannot but cite one more, more extensive quotation from Chibirov's article, which may be regarded both as a leitmotif and an epigraph for the entire book under discussion: 'The more time passes since V. I. Abaev's passing from this world, the more majestic his luminous image will become to the generations to come;' such is the destiny of great individuals. At the same time, the present young generation and those to follow will admire not only the scholar's outstanding works, but will increasingly be interested in his extraordinary human qualities. Those who communicated and worked closely for years with this outstanding contemporary can make a significant contribution to the study of V. I. Abaev's personality. There remain many such individuals both in Russia and abroad. Therefore, alongside the ongoing intensive study of the great scholar's scientific legacy, we are obliged to collect, piece by piece, and bring to

the knowledge of our history all that characterizes the human persona and moral credo of Vasily Ivanovich Abaev. The lessons that V. I. Abaev imparted to all of us through his scholarly achievements are both significant and instructive. For the younger generation, the personality of V. I. Abaev and his moral lessons may prove even more important, useful, and instructive” (2, 33).

The materials of the following sections of the publication are organized according to their category: the second section contains reviews, critiques, and responses to previous editions by Ludwig Alekseevich on Abaev, demonstrating the wide demand for this information among readers.

The third section of the book comprises texts of speeches and greeting addresses delivered at jubilee celebrations marking significant dates in the scholar’s life.

The chronicle of meetings with V. I. Abaev is set forth in the fourth section of the book; this section also includes the author’s speeches at events honoring him, letters, speeches, and reviews. Also included here is a review of V. I. Abaev’s monograph «Nart Epic of the Ossetians», titled «An Outstanding Work on Nart Studies».

The fifth section of the book gathers documents related to the commemoration of V. I. Abaev (including a speech at the funeral memorial service, information about the monument to the scholar in Vladikavkaz, documentary films, the first lifetime monument to the scholar, and others).

Of particular value is the section ‘Appendices’: it contains the correspondence of V. I. Abaev, K. G. Tskhurbaeva, and L. A. Chibirov, accompanied by photocopies of the handwritten original letters, offering readers the opportunity to see the handwriting – the living, handwritten letters of the preeminent figure in Ossetian studies. Also included is the informative article by I. T. Tsorieva, “V. I. Abaev and L. A. Chibirov. Milestones of Friendship and Cooperation,” as well as a list of publications by L. A. Chibirov on V. I. Abaev. Also included is the informative article by I. T. Tsorieva, “V. I. Abaev and L. A. Chibirov. Milestones of Friendship and Cooperation,” as well as a list of publications by L. A. Chibirov on V. I. Abaev.

How else might the presented material be used so that it becomes not only a legacy and reference work for the scholarly community, intellectuals, and local historians? Collectively, the materials in the book strike me as an excellent foundation for a script not only for a documentary but perhaps also for a feature film about Vaso Abaev. For the screenwriters of such a film, this book will save considerable time and effort: it is entirely feasible to construct the film’s narrative around it, incorporating key quotations and the scholar’s foundational theses. The book also contains a wealth of exclusive illustrative material.

In today’s information environment, such a creative video product is capable of reaching the broadest audience of learners in Ossetia, the Caucasus, and the academic-educational community. Its relevance and demand will undoubtedly also extend to Ossetian diaspora communities abroad, especially given the possibility of

using subtitles in the respective languages. Such a film, crafted by a talented hand and reaching its audience, will truly help the reviewed book become a guiding gift for many. Moreover, in the educational sphere, it will serve as an effective pedagogical tool. By the way: the word ‘pedagogy’ derives from the Ancient Greek *παιδαγωγική* and literally means ‘child-leading’ or ‘child-guiding.’ In Ancient Greece, a pedagogue was a slave responsible for watching over the child and accompanying him on the way to school.

The guiding idea in the discussed book lies not only in highlighting the outstanding merits of V. I. Abaev as a scholar but also in portraying his personal qualities that enabled him to emerge as a professional and patriot: extraordinary diligence, scientific integrity, profound reverence for the homeland, steadfast loyalty to the postulates and teachers he once embraced, and gratitude towards colleagues and friends.

Reading the book by L. A. Chibirov, which once again fully conveys the magnitude of the scholar’s personality, one realizes that the words spoken by Vasily Ivanovich about the universal significance of the national symbol of his people, Kosta Khetagurov are equally applicable to Vaso himself: ‘The universal significance of figures like Kosta is inseparably linked to their national significance.’ It could not be otherwise. The path to the universal human lies through the national. There is no other way. To become a representative of humanity, one must be the best representative of their own people. ... Thus, the peak of the national becomes the peak of the human. ... The numerical strength of a people holds no particular significance in this regard. A pearl remains a pearl, wherever it is found, whether in a small sea or a vast ocean” (1, 550).

All of us who knew V. I. Abaev during his lifetime, and who regularly engaged with his works, revered his personality and his scholarship; yet it was precisely L. A. Chibirov who found the time, made the effort, and discovered a way to convey this to his contemporaries and descendants through a book. A commemorative book written by the grateful hand of a colleague, follower, and faithful, close friend. The phenomenon of Abaev as a person, who became for the author of the book ‘The Thinker with the Guiding Gift’ an exemplary personality and scholar, appears to the reader not only as a guide for many but also as a ‘guiding beacon’ in scientific advancement, in the development of the civic worldview, and in the national character of L. A. Chibirov himself, as precisely noted by the scientific editor of the edition, I. T. Tsorieva, in her introduction (6, 5–11).

In the book under consideration, it is especially valuable that V. I. Abaev is presented not only as a scholar who provides guidance through his gifted scientific investigations, but also as a person who reveals to a wide circle of acquaintances the product of his mountain ethnic heritage, tact, an example of loyalty in friendship, devotion to his teacher, and attention to junior colleagues, to whom he consistently expresses sincere gratitude for their care.

In seeking ways to more vividly and memorably capture the image of Vaso Abaev, the author employs a series of figurative epithets – each standing for itself: a great scholar, a person of noble soul, a wise mentor, a bearer of extraordinary human qualities, an outstanding researcher radiating wisdom and kindness, an unsurpassed historian who left a vivid mark in memory, a living legend who received recognition during his lifetime, a supreme authority, an exemplar of selfless dedication to his native people, who attained the highest position in the field of Ossetian studies, serving as a guiding beacon.

Against this background, as a kind of summary, one conclusion of the book's content is a call not only to intensively study Vaso's scientific legacy but also to delve into the lessons he imparted through his scientific achievements, recognizing his moral credo, which is equally important and instructive" (2, 33).

The author of the book conveyed to us the words spoken by Vaso in an oral conversation with him, characterizing him as a person of utmost modesty: 'Those who say that I have exalted the Ossetian people are mistaken.' Quite the opposite, it is the Ossetian people themselves who made me the person I am. It is precisely to my people that I owe what I have managed to accomplish. And also to my present position" (2, 160).

The materials of the book are important as an example of how one can and should honor a colleague, friend, teacher, and a worthy individual. Indeed, the reader is presented not only with the author's individual memory, but the publication also carries a conceptual message aimed at materializing memory within public consciousness through the preservation of a person's creative legacy, as well as the description and evaluation of the significance of this legacy.

In such work, within the framework of the laws governing the social dynamics of memory, it is important to engage in activities aimed at shaping how subsequent generations perceive the ideas, works, and persona of an individual. This, in turn, necessitates an appropriate interpretation of the creator's intentions and viewpoints for various socio-age groups of citizens. In any case, the transmission of memory is always a form of social interaction, initiated through the application of effort, time, and the individual's creative imperative.

Through the implicit presence of the author's persona within the content of the book under discussion, one can clearly observe how, through what efforts, it is possible to immortalize one's idol in the memory of thousands by writing a book about him, defending his noble name, establishing a museum in his honor, initiating a competition for monument designs, and disseminating his words about the significance of the native language in the life of every individual and the entire nation... All these reflections linger after reading the book, which offers us a vivid and memorable exemplary portrait of a person who guides the reader toward truth, goodness, and beauty.

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TOWARD THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENCYCLOPEDIAS «VOLGA BULGARIA» AND «GOLDEN HORDE»

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Abstract. *The article briefly examines the prehistory, history and culture of Volga Bulgaria and the Golden Horde; the history of the term «Tatars»; the initial stages of the ethnogenesis of the modern Tatar people and the roots of the politogenesis of the Republic of Tatarstan. The publication also reports on the relevance and importance of scientific popularization of the history and culture of Volga Bulgaria, the Golden Horde and the post-Horde Tatar khanates, on the development of concepts and the beginning of the compilation of dictionaries of the encyclopedias «Volga Bulgaria» and «Golden Horde».*

Keywords: *Volga Bulgaria, Golden Horde, Tatar khanates, encyclopedia, encyclopedic dictionary, Institute of Tatar Encyclopedia and Regional Studies.*

The history of statehood in the territory of modern Tatarstan has deep roots tracing back to medieval states such as the Hunnic Empire, the Western Turkic Khaganate, and the Khazar Khaganate. From the 2nd to the 7th centuries, during the period known as the ‘Great Migration of Peoples,’ Turkic-Ugric tribes actively penetrated the territory of the Middle Volga region. The culture of the Turkic-speaking population in the region, which significantly increased in the 6th to 8th centuries, was closely related to the cultures of the Western Turkic and Khazar Khaganates, as well as the Great Bulgar of the Black Sea region. In the 670s the latter was conquered by the Khazars, and part of the Bulgars (the state-forming population of Great Bulgaria) in the 7th-9th centuries. From the regions of Western Trans-Caspia, the North Caucasus, and the Northern Black Sea area migrated to the Middle Volga region, Volga-Kama, and Western Trans-Ural.

In the 10th century, the Bulgars founded on the territory of the modern Republic of Tatarstan, at the very center of the renowned Baltic-Volga trade route, the first state in the Middle Volga and Trans-Ural region – Volga-Kama Bulgaria, which

incorporated numerous local Turkic and Finno-Ugric tribes, along with representatives of Iranian and Balto-Slavic tribes [2; 3; 4].

The location of archaeological sites makes it possible to outline the territory of Volga Bulgaria in general terms – the principal monuments of the Bulgar period are located within the territories of the contemporary Republic of Tatarstan, the Chuvash Republic, the Republic of Bashkortostan, as well as the Ulyanovsk, Samara, and Penza regions. By the end of the 12th century, the Bulgar rulers substantially extended their sphere of influence into the Upper Kama region (modern Perm Krai) and the Lower Volga region, with the city of Saksin (modern Astrakhan region) serving as the center. The Bulgar state possessed a large number (more than 1200) of fortresses, castles, settlements, and cities that emerged in the 9th-12th centuries. The cities of Bulgar, Suvar, Bilyar, Alabuga, Bryakhimov, Dzhuketau, Oshel, as well as the so-called ‘Muromsky Gorodok,’ ‘Khulash Settlement,’ ‘Zolotarev Settlement,’ ‘Yulovsky Settlement,’ among others, constituted significant military-political and cultural-economic centers. In comparison with synchronous Old Russian and Western European cities, Bulgar cities were larger both in size and in population. For instance, Bilyar (‘Great City’ in the Russian annals) covered an area exceeding 800 hectares and had a population of up to 100,000 inhabitants. Political, trade-economic, and cultural relations with the countries and peoples of Dasht-i Qipchaq and the North Caucasus, the Abbasid Caliphate and Khwarezm, the northern and southern Russian principalities, Byzantium, the Baltic region and Scandinavia, India, Afghanistan, and China were of considerable importance in the life of Volga-Kama Bulgaria [1; 3].

Islam was the dominant confession in the state, beginning to spread into the Volga-Ural region in the second half of the 9th century and becoming the official state religion of Volga Bulgaria in 922. A significant factor in consolidating the position of Islam and securing diplomatic recognition of Volga Bulgaria as a Muslim country was the visit of an embassy from the Baghdad caliph al-Muqtadir to Volga Bulgaria in the mentioned year [4, pp. 69–88]. From the end of the 10th century virtually the entire population of the country became Muslim. In the 10th-13th centuries within the boundaries of the Middle Volga region and Western Pre-Urals, from the tribes of Bulgars, Baranjars, Barsils (Bersula), Bilers, Suvars (Suaz, Savir), Es-egel, as well as certain groups of Burtas, Magyars, Kipchaks, and Oghuz-Pecheneg tribes, a unified Bulgar ethnicity was formed (with a single language, spiritual, and material culture), and Bulgaria itself transformed into a country of highly developed agriculture, animal husbandry, urban development, crafts, and trade, which enables us to recognize the functioning of a distinct Bulgarian civilization in Eastern Europe [3]. This is also evidenced by the development within the state of various forms of art and literature, science, and monumental architecture. Thanks to a well-developed, multi-tiered education system, the population of Volga Bulgaria (both

women and men – for example, in the women’s madrasas of Tuybiki and Rabiga) received instruction in the fundamentals of religion and secular sciences. This led to the emergence of prominent figures in Bulgarian history, including theologians, philosophers, writers, historians, geographers, and other scholars (notably the poet Kul Gali, the historian Yakub ibn Nugman, the physician Taj ad-Din ibn Yunus al-Bulgari, as well as philosophers and writers such as Suleiman ibn Dawud as-Saksini as-Suwari, Abu’l-‘Ala Hamid al-Bulgari, Burhan ad-Din al-Bulgari, and Khoja Ahmad al-Bulgari – who served as tutor and vizier to the great sultan of the Ghaznavid state, Yamin ad-Dawla Mahmud Ghaznavi) [6].

Thus, by the beginning of the 13th century Volga-Kama Bulgar becomes truly a unique and significant phenomenon in universal history, which enabled the Hungarian monk Julian, who in the mid-1230s undertook two journeys eastward in search of ‘Great Hungary,’ to write in his work entitled ‘The Letter on the Life, Faith, and Origin of the Tatars’ that ‘Volga Bulgar is a great and powerful kingdom with wealthy cities’ [4, pp. 148–157]. However, in 1236–1237 As a result of the Mongol-Tatar conquest, Bulgaria, which by that time already comprised a collection of several independent Bulgarian «principalities», ceased to exist, and its territory during the second half of the 13th century was fully incorporated into the Ulus of Jochi (the Golden Horde). Subsequently, the population of Volga Bulgaria became one of the most significant components of the medieval Tatar ethnic group, and the country’s culture became an essential element of the Tatar historical and cultural heritage.

During the existence of the Golden Horde, the principal processes of political, economic, and ethnocultural consolidation of the Turkic-speaking peoples within this vast Chinggisid–Jochid empire occurred, alongside the formation of the medieval Tatar ethnos – the forerunner of the modern Tatar nation. At present, approximately 200 Golden Horde cities are identified, thus providing a basis to speak of an integrated Golden Horde civilization [5; 10; 12]. Among the largest cities of the state were Bulgar (the first capital of the Golden Horde, present-day Tatarstan), Sarai al-Makhrusa and Khadjitarhan (Astrakhan Oblast), Sarai al-Jadid and Beljamen (Volgograd Oblast), Muksha/Narovchat (Penza Oblast), Ukek (Saratov Oblast), Azak (Rostov Oblast), Madzhar (Stavropol Krai), Derbent (Dagestan), Kyrk-Yer and Crimea/Solhat (Crimea), Akkerman (Ukraine), Saraychik and Syganak (Kazakhstan), Old Urgench (Turkmenistan), Isker/Siberia (Tyumen Oblast), among others [10]. The Middle Volga cities Bulgar, Dzhuketau, Iski (Echke) Kazan, Kazan, Kashan, Kermenchug, and others served as centers of administrative authority, artisanal production, trade, and the cultural and confessional life of the Bulgar ulus of the Golden Horde. Historical sources provide clear evidence of the existence in the Middle Volga region of a certain state formation centered in Kazan already before the second third of the 15th century, prior to the establishment of the Kazan Khanate. For example, there is evidence that the “Kazan Horde” was established

by Sartaq, the son of Khan Batu, already in the mid-13th century, and by the 14th century Kazan, along with the cities of Bulgar, Dzhuketau, and Kermenchuk, was already mentioned specifically as the political center of one of the local “principalities.” This clearly indicates the increased sovereignty of Kazan from Sarai, while still remaining within the unified Golden Horde.

The disintegration of the Ulus of Jochi led to the emergence of an entire “constellation” of new states, which continued the traditions of the Golden Horde civilization and represented a fully coherent medieval confederation...

The ethnogenesis and cultural genesis of the modern Tatar people are directly connected with the period of the Golden Horde. Tatars (self-designation «tatar», «tatarlar») constitute a Turkic-speaking ethnic group with a rich history and culture, having formed as a nation at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries; the second-largest ethnic group within the Russian Federation and the principal population of the Republic of Tatarstan and the Republic of Bashkortostan. Tatars reside compactly in numerous cities and regions across the Russian Federation (including Moscow and the Moscow Region, Saint Petersburg and the Leningrad Region, the Volga Region and the Cis-Urals, Siberia, and the Far East), as well as diasporically in Kazakhstan and Central Asia, Ukraine, Turkey, Azerbaijan, Georgia, the United States, China, countries of Eastern Europe and Scandinavia, Japan, and Australia. The estimated total population of Tatars worldwide is approximately 7–10 million individuals, with about 5 million in Russia, 2 million in Tatarstan, 1 million in Bashkortostan, and abroad ranging from 500 individuals (Poland) to 200,000 individuals (Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan); the population of Tatars in Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Iran cannot be quantified due to a number of subjective factors [9].

The ethnonym ‘Tatars’ was first distinctly and unambiguously attested among the ancient Turkic-Mongol peoples of Eastern Turkestan in the 5th-6th centuries.– during the period of the disintegration of the Rouran Khaganate and the establishment of the Turkic Khaganate. In the 7th-12th centuries. As an ethnopolitonym, it was widely used throughout the territory of Eastern and Central Eurasia in the 13th century.– across the vast territory of the Mongol Empire from the Yellow Sea to the Danube.

The history of the ancestors of modern Tatars encompasses the history of the Saka, Huns, and Xiongnu; the history of the Western Turkic and Eastern Turkic, Avar, Uighur, and Kimak Khaganates; the history of the Pontic Great Bulgar and Khazaria; the history of the Pechenegs and Kipchaks (Polovtsy); and the history of Volga Bulgaria and the Tatar states of Central Asia in the 11th-12th centuries. In the 13th-15th centuries. In the Golden Horde (Ulus of Jochi), the term ‘Tatars’ (politonym, socionym, ethnonym) acquires an ethno-integrating meaning, initially denoting the military-service estate, and later the population of the state’s urban agglomerations, the majority of which were Islamized and communicated in a common language of

the Kipchak branch of Turkic languages. This language gave rise to a new literary language ('Volga Turks'), in which masterpieces of science and literature such as 'Qisas al-Anbiya' ('Tales of the Prophets') by Burhan ad-Din Rabghuzi (1310), 'Kalandar-nama' by Abu Bakr Kalandar (1320–1340s), 'Muhabbat-nama' ('On Love') by Khorezmi (1353), 'Nahj al-Faradis' ('The Path to Paradise') by Mahmud Bulghari (1358), 'Jumjuma Sultan' ('Tsar Skull') by Khisam Kiyat (1369), 'Kisekbash' ('Severed Head') by an unknown author, 'Khosrow wa Shirin' ('Khosrow and Shirin') by Kutb (1383), 'Gulistan bit-Turki' ('Gulistan in Turkic') and 'Sukhail wa Guldursun' (1391) by Saif Sarai, along with lyrical poetry by Ahmad Khwaja as-Sarai, were composed. Mavlia Kaziya Mukhsin, Mavliana Ishak, Fakih Berke, and numerous others. The grand historical events of the Golden Horde period are reflected in such an epic narrative as the dastan "Idegey" [6, pp. 63–152].

The active spread of Islam in the Ulus of Jochi (the Golden Horde), intensive urbanization, the broad dissemination of literacy, and, correspondingly, of a standardized literary language constituted a significant factor in the dynamic integration of the majority of the Golden Horde population, its transition away from tribal segmentation, and, consequently – the formation and strengthening of Tatar ethnopolitical identity [5; 9; 12]. Following the dissolution of the Golden Horde, new Tatar states emerged – the Astrakhan, Kazan, Kasimov, Crimean, and Tyumen/Siberian khanates, within the territories of which the unified ethnonym 'Tatars' was ultimately definitively established [8; 9; 12]...

Thus, the prehistory and history of modern Tatarstan and the contemporary Tatar people encompass several centuries. The ethnogenesis and cultural genesis of the Tatar nation, as well as the political genesis of the Republic of Tatarstan, were complex and unfolded through many stages of their 'prehistory' and history; here, I have briefly examined only some of the most significant epochs – the periods of Volga-Kama Bulgaria, the Golden Horde, and the post-Horde Tatar states...

In 2024, I addressed the relevance of the scientific popularization of the history and culture of Volga-Kama Bulgaria, the Golden Horde, and the post-Horde Tatar khanates, as well as the necessity of creating multimedia academic encyclopedias "Volga Bulgaria" and "Golden Horde" in the Russian and Tatar languages, and the conceptual framework for these encyclopedias. These topics were presented in my scientific reports at the IV International Scientific-Practical Seminar "Tatar studies in the Context of Paradigm Shifts: Theory, Methodology, Practice," at the VI International Congress of Archaeology of the Eurasian Steppes, and at the International Scientific Forum "Regional Encyclopedistics in the Context of Modern Innovative Challenges" in 2025. I delivered a report titled 'On the Preparation of the Dictionary of the Encyclopedia "Volga Bulgaria"' at the XVII Final Scientific Conference of the Institute of Tatar Encyclopedics and Regional Studies named after M. Kh. Khasanov of the Academy of Sciences of

the Republic of Tatarstan, and presented a report titled ‘On the Preparation of the Dictionary of the Encyclopedia “Golden Horde”’ at the International Scientific Seminar ‘Kazakhstan and Tatarstan: Humanitarian and Cultural Connections in the Past and Present.’ The texts of all these reports, along with other materials of mine on this topic, have been published (in Russian, Tatar, and English) in scientific journals and collections, and uploaded to the internet, in particular on the websites of RSCI (the page of B. L. Khamidullin) and the Institute of Linguistics named after G. Ibragimov, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tatarstan, Institute of Archaeology named after A. Kh. Khalikov, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tatarstan; journals «Echo of Centuries – Gasyrlar avazy» and «Bezneñ miras»; the newspaper «Mädäni comğa»; portals «Online Encyclopedias Tatarica» and «Academia.edu» (see, for example: [7, pp. 266–269; 11]).

At the end of 2024, the leadership of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tatarstan adopted the final conclusion on the relevance and feasibility of implementing these significant academic initiatives. The aforementioned topics have found their rightful place in the Regional Program of the Republic of Tatarstan titled ‘History and Culture of the Peoples of Steppe Eurasia,’ approved by decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Tatarstan on January 26, 2026. (program implementation period: 2026–2034).

Academic encyclopedias entirely dedicated to individual states of antiquity and the Middle Ages that no longer exist on the current political map of the world – such as the Turkic, Khazar, and Kimak khanates; the Black Sea Great Bulgar and Volga-Kama Bulgar; Ulus of Jochi / Golden Horde; and the Kazan, Crimean, Astrakhan, Tyumen, and Kasimov khanates – have not existed in Russian and Tatar languages until very recently. Thus, the staff of the Institute of Tatar Encyclopedia and Regional Studies named after M. Kh. Khasanov of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tatarstan are entrusted with the challenging task of being ‘trailblazers.’

We anticipate that the one-volume encyclopedias ‘Volga Bulgaria’ and ‘Golden Horde’ will include the most comprehensive reference material possible on the prehistory of Volga-Kama Bulgaria and the Golden Horde (Ulus of Jochi); on the history, culture, and geography of Volga-Kama Bulgaria, the Golden Horde, and the successor khanates; about the historical and cultural tangible and intangible heritage of the Bulgar and Golden Horde states; about the individuals who have professionally studied and are currently studying the history and culture of these states, etc.

Since the first serious stage in preparing any encyclopedia is the development of its concept [11] and the compilation of its dictionary, from the end of 2024, Candidate of Historical Sciences B. L. Khamidullin and Doctor of Historical Sciences, professor, full member of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tatarstan, director of the Institute of Archaeology named after A. Kh. Khalikov

and A. G. Sitdikov of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tatarstan carried out extensive initial work, which resulted in the development of a concept and the preparation of preliminary glossaries for the specified encyclopedias (approximately 1500 plus approximately 1500 'black words' arranged alphabetically). The scientific editor of the dictionary of the encyclopedia 'Volga Bulgaria' is the prominent archaeologist and Bulgarologist, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Corresponding Member of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tatarstan, F. Sh. Khuzin.

The process of compiling dictionaries continues. Naturally, in the future, the encyclopedic dictionaries of Volga Bulgaria and the Golden Horde (possibly in the form of separate brochures) will certainly be presented for professional study, discussion, critique, and supplementation by the broader scholarly community...

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TURQUERIE AS A BRIDGE: EUROPEAN VIEWS OF OTTOMAN CULTURE

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Abstract. *The cultural phenomenon known as Turquerie – the European fascination with Ottoman manners, dress, theatrical motifs, and exotic imagery – occupies a pivotal position in the intellectual and artistic history of early modernity. This article examines Turquerie as a mechanism of cross-cultural mediation by analysing three primary bodies of source material: the corpus of French seventeenth-century theatrical turqueries as defined and catalogued by Sylvie Requemora; the geographical and geopolitical framing of Turkey between East and West as presented by Marcel Bazin; and the first-hand epistolary accounts of Lady Mary Wortley Montagu as examined through the scholarship of Nazli Gündüz. Employing a comparative textual methodology informed by postcolonial theory and cultural historiography, the article argues that Turquerie functioned simultaneously as a literary genre, a political discourse, and a sartorial practice, each mode serving a distinct but interrelated purpose in constructing European self-understanding through the figure of the Ottoman Other. The study identifies a tension between the othering impulse characteristic of Orientalist discourse and the more nuanced, occasionally empathetic gaze present in primary sources such as Montagu’s letters. The article concludes that Turquerie, far from being a merely decorative cultural vogue, constituted a serious and structurally complex engagement with questions of power, sovereignty, gender, and cross-cultural legibility.*

Keywords: *Turquerie; Ottoman Empire; cross-cultural representation; early modern theatre; Lady Montagu; Orientalism; French drama; cultural identity.*

1. Introduction

The term Turquerie designates a broad cultural phenomenon through which European societies – primarily French, English, and Austro-Hungarian – engaged with, imitated, and imaginatively reconstructed elements of Ottoman Turkish civilisation during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. As a field of scholarly inquiry, Turquerie sits at the intersection of literary history, performance studies, art

history, and the broader postcolonial critique of Orientalism. While Edward Said's foundational framework in *Orientalism* (1978) has provided the dominant analytical lens through which Western representations of the East have been interrogated for several decades, recent scholarship has called attention to the heterogeneity and internal contradictions within the Orientalist tradition. The sources under examination in this article reflect precisely such contradictions, revealing a space in which fascination, fear, political allegory, and genuine ethnographic curiosity coexisted.

The significance of *Turquerie* for Turkic studies lies not only in what it reveals about European perceptions of the Ottoman world, but also in what it illuminates about the mechanisms by which cultural otherness is produced, commodified, and eventually parodied. The theatrical corpus studied by Requemora demonstrates that Ottoman subject matter occupied French dramatic culture well before the celebrated *turqueries* of Molière and Racine, functioning as a vehicle for political commentary on absolutism, dynastic succession, and the nature of tyranny. The geopolitical framing proposed by Bazin foregrounds the structural liminality of Turkey between Orient and Occident, a liminality that was already inscribed into the cultural imagination of early modern Europe. Finally, Montagu's letters, as analysed by Gündüz, offer a rare instance of a Western observer whose engagement with Ottoman material culture – and specifically with Ottoman dress – transcends the merely exotic to approach something resembling genuine cultural recognition.

The central thesis of this article is that *Turquerie* operated as a multi-layered cultural technology: it was simultaneously a theatrical mode, a political metaphor, a sartorial fashion, and an epistemological strategy. Understanding this complexity requires reading the theatrical, geographical, and epistolary sources in dialogue with one another rather than treating them as discrete cultural artefacts.

2. Literature Review

Sylvie Requemora's study of theatrical *turqueries* in seventeenth-century France offers the most systematic treatment of the dramatic corpus available in the attached scholarship. Her analysis identifies a precise body of texts – seven tragedies and three tragi-comedies produced between 1621 and 1681 – which she defines as works placing their dramatic action within the Ottoman court of the sultans, centring specifically on the clan of Suleiman II [Requemora, 2004, p. 133]. Requemora argues that the term *Turquerie* has been applied too broadly in critical discourse, designating at various times the Turkish entries in court ballets, the Mamamouchi scenes of Molière's *Le Bourgeois Gentilhomme*, the broader vogue for chinoiseries, and even the wholesale penetration of Arabic vocabulary into the French lexicon through words such as *alcool*, *algèbre*, *divan*, and *sofa* [Requemora, 2004, p. 133]. Her intervention is to restrict the category to works defined by their strict localisation of the dramatic action within Oriental settings involving Oriental characters,

while acknowledging that this narrower corpus must be read against the wider sociocultural phenomenon from which it emerges.

Requemora draws attention to the paradox that the social mode des turqueries was assigned a date in French cultural memory – associated with *Le Bourgeois Gentilhomme* of 1670 and Racine's *Bajazet* of 1672 – that postdates by several decades the actual period of dramatic production, which she locates principally in the years 1621 to 1656 [Requemora, 2004, p. 134]. This displacement between literary practice and social perception underscores the extent to which *Turquerie*, as a cultural category, was constructed retrospectively and in relation to canonical works rather than reflecting the actual chronology of theatrical production. Her analysis of the six historical episodes drawn upon by the *turquerie* dramatists – ranging from the reign of Tamerlan and *Bajazet I* to the assassination of Osman II in 1622 – reveals a consistent dramaturgical investment in questions of dynastic legitimacy, polygamy, political intrigue, and the relationship between law and sovereign will [Requemora, 2004, p. 135].

Marcel Bazin's geographical introduction to a special issue on Turkey offers a complementary macrostructural perspective. Writing in 1986, Bazin identifies a long process of cultural degradation in the French public image of Turkey, tracing a decline in prestige from the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries – when the prestige of the *Grand Turc* imposed the fashion of *turqueries* – through the nineteenth century sick man of Europe narrative to the marginalisation of Turkey within both European and Middle Eastern frameworks by the mid-twentieth century [Bazin, 1986, p. 3]. Bazin's framing of Turkey as a country between Orient and Occident – geopolitically, culturally, and epistemologically – resonates with the structural ambivalence that characterises the theatrical *turqueries*: the Ottoman court functions in these dramas neither as purely alien nor as transparently analogous to the French monarchy, but as a distorted mirror in which European political anxieties are simultaneously projected and disavowed.

Nazli Gündüz's article on Lady Mary Wortley Montagu's *The Turkish Embassy Letters* provides a third analytical register, moving from the theatrical and geopolitical to the personal and sartorial. Gündüz situates Montagu within the broader *Turquerie* vogue of the eighteenth century, noting that the fashionable phenomenon of wearing Ottoman clothing and having portraits painted in Turkish dress was prevalent among European nobles [Gündüz, 2019, p. 121]. What distinguishes Montagu from the theatrical and pictorial representations of *Turquerie* analysed by Requemora is the directness and personal specificity of her engagement: she was present in Ottoman spaces, interacted with court members, and wore the clothing she described. Gündüz argues that Montagu's descriptions of Ottoman female dress – the *salvar*, *entari*, *ferace*, and *yasmak* – exhibit a different and generally non-marginalising attitude from that of other western travelers [Gündüz, 2019, p.

122], and that her account of the *yasmak* as a device conferring a form of freedom upon Ottoman women directly contradicts the later Orientalist construction of the veil as an instrument of oppression.

Taken together, these three bodies of scholarship frame *Turquerie* as a phenomenon that cannot be adequately explained through a single analytical lens. Each source foregrounds a different register of the phenomenon – the theatrical-political, the geographical-structural, and the personal-sartorial – and each implicitly challenges reductive accounts of European-Ottoman relations as simply and uniformly Orientalist in Said’s sense.

3. Methodology

The methodological approach of this article is comparative textual analysis informed by the theoretical frameworks of cultural historiography and postcolonial studies. The three bodies of source material identified above are treated not as independent data sets but as mutually illuminating texts whose convergences and divergences generate analytical insight unavailable to any single source alone. The comparative reading proceeds on three levels: thematic, formal, and historical.

At the thematic level, the article traces the recurrence across all three sources of a set of core concerns: the representation of Ottoman sovereignty and political order; the role of dress and material culture in signifying identity and cultural difference; the gendering of the Eastern gaze; and the relationship between fascination and fear in the construction of the Ottoman Other. At the formal level, attention is paid to the specific genres and media through which *Turquerie* was articulated – theatrical tragedy and tragicomedy in *Requemora*, geographic-academic prose in Bazin, and epistolary literature in Gündüz – since the formal properties of each medium shape the representations it can produce. At the historical level, the article situates each source within its specific moment of production: the French Fronde and the associated preoccupation with tyranny and absolutism in the 1640s and 1650s; the Cold War geopolitical context in which Bazin’s 1986 assessment of Turkey was formulated; and the early eighteenth-century diplomatic culture within which Montagu’s letters were written.

The article does not seek to reconstruct the actual Ottoman reality behind the European representations it examines; such a project would require a different archive and a different set of methodological tools. Rather, it treats these representations as cultural documents that tell us primarily about the European societies that produced them, while acknowledging, particularly in the case of Montagu, that first-hand observation can create moments of genuine cross-cultural recognition that exceed the ideological frameworks within which they were produced.

4. Results and Discussion

The comparative analysis of the three sources yields several findings of scholarly significance. The first and most structurally fundamental of these concerns the political function of *Turquerie* in French dramatic culture.

Requemora's analysis demonstrates persuasively that the theatrical turqueries of the 1620s through 1650s were not simply exotic entertainments but vehicles for political reflection on the nature of sovereignty and the limits of royal power. The *Dictionnaire de Furetière* entry cited by Requemora is revealing in this regard: *Turquerie* is defined primarily as a manner of acting cruel and barbarous, like that employed by the Turks [Requemora, 2004, p. 137]. This definition transforms *Turquerie* from a descriptive cultural category into a moral and political one, designating a style of governance characterised by despotic excess and the subordination of law to sovereign will.

The political allegory becomes most transparent in plays such as Magnon's *Le Grand Tamerlan ou la mort de Bajazet* (1648) and Jacquelin's *Soliman ou l'esclave généreuse* (1653), composed during and immediately after the Fronde. Requemora observes that these plays elaborate a black myth of despotism, which places in parallel the despotic oriental power structures and French absolutist ones [Requemora, 2004, p. 137]. The confrontation between Tamerlan and Bajazet in Magnon's play – both characters claiming universal sovereignty and dismissing the other as tyrant – functions as a theatre of political self-examination in which the spectre of French absolutism under Richelieu is never far from the surface. This politicisation of the Ottoman figure is a distinctive feature of the theatrical turquerie that sets it apart from the decorative and sartorial forms of *Turquerie* analysed elsewhere.

The second major finding concerns the gendering of the *Turquerie* figure. Across both the theatrical corpus and Montagu's letters, women occupy a structurally ambivalent position: they are simultaneously objects of the male Ottoman sovereign's tyrannical desire and agents of political manipulation in their own right. Requemora shows that the character of Roxelane – who appears in various guises across multiple turquerie plays – consistently embodies a paradoxical combination of subjection and agency. Her manipulation of Ottoman legal structures in Desmares's *Roxelane*, for example, follows a strategy in three stages to raise herself to the supreme rank [Requemora, 2004, p. 140], exploiting the very legal framework that ostensibly constrains her. This dramatic figure of the politically astute Ottoman woman finds its counterpart in Montagu's accounts of the court women she encountered in Edirne and Istanbul.

Gündüz draws attention to Montagu's description of the wife of the Grand Vizier and particularly of the strikingly beautiful Fatma Hanim, whose dress is rendered in meticulous detail: a brocade entari, an embroidered tulle shirt, diamond-encrusted bracelets, a belt of diamonds, and hair ornaments incorporating rubies, emeralds, and jasmine-shaped diamonds [Gündüz, 2019, pp. 129–130]. What is significant here is not merely the luxury of the description but its function as an act of cultural recognition. Montagu does not exoticise or eroticise these women in the manner characteristic of later Orientalist painting; instead, as Gündüz argues, she records their dress as part

of an attempt to document the material culture of a society she regards with genuine admiration [Gündüz, 2019, p. 134]. The contrast with the theatrical turqueries is instructive: in the plays examined by Requemora, the Oriental woman is primarily a dramatic function – a prize over which male sovereigns compete, or a political operator whose machinations drive the plot – whereas in Montagu’s letters she is a social subject with her own aesthetic sensibilities and cultural protocols.

The third finding relates to the structural liminality of Turkey as both a geographical and cultural entity. Bazin’s observation that Turkey occupies an uncomfortable position at the borders of Europe and the Orient [Bazin, 1986, p. 5] resonates with Requemora’s analysis of the theatrical function of the Ottoman setting. In the tragic turqueries, Constantinople and the seraglio serve as a space beyond the limits of European order – what Requemora, following Émelina, calls a Far East of the Grand Siècle, a zone of excess and passion beyond the reach of Christian moral order and monarchical law [Requemora, 2004, p. 148]. Yet this spatial otherness is always relative and dialectical: the Turkish court is not simply alien but structurally analogous to the French court, its despotism a distorted image of French absolutism rather than a categorically different political formation.

This structural liminality generates what might be called the epistemological paradox of *Turquerie*: the Ottoman world is simultaneously too familiar to be genuinely foreign and too different to be straightforwardly legible. Requemora captures this paradox in her observation that Racine’s *Bajazet* compensates historical proximity by distance in space [Requemora, 2004, p. 147] – a formulation that applies equally to the broader phenomenon. Montagu navigates this paradox through the practice of disguise: by donning the *yasmak* and *ferace*, she renders herself temporarily legible within Ottoman spatial codes, moving through Istanbul streets in a manner that would have been impossible without this sartorial transformation [Gündüz, 2019, p. 133]. Her use of Ottoman dress is thus not merely a fashionable *Turquerie* gesture but an epistemological strategy, a way of accessing a social reality that European conventions of gender and visibility would otherwise have rendered inaccessible.

A fourth and original contribution of this analysis concerns the temporal structure of *Turquerie* as a cultural phenomenon. Requemora’s identification of the paradox that the social mode des turqueries was associated in cultural memory with events of 1670–1672, some two decades after the peak of actual theatrical production, suggests that *Turquerie* was not simply a response to Ottoman cultural prestige but a retrospective construction that organised a dispersed set of cultural practices into a coherent vogue only after the fact. Bazin’s analysis of the subsequent decline in French knowledge of and interest in Turkey – from the eighteenth-century prestige of the *Grand Turc* to the twentieth-century marginalisation of Turkey as economically and politically weak [Bazin, 1986, p. 3] – indicates

that this retrospective construction was itself historically contingent, representing a particular moment in Franco-Ottoman relations that could be and was superseded. The temporal dynamic of *Turquerie* thus illuminates a more general mechanism by which European cultures process their relations with geopolitical Others: through a combination of productive fascination, retrospective organisation, and eventual dissolution into cultural indifference.

5. Conclusion

This article has argued that *Turquerie* constitutes a complex and multidimensional cultural phenomenon that cannot be adequately explained either as mere exoticism or as straightforward Orientalist othering. Drawing on three bodies of scholarship that address the theatrical, geographical, and epistolary dimensions of the phenomenon, the analysis has identified four major findings: first, that theatrical *Turquerie* functioned as a vehicle for political commentary on absolutism and tyranny in seventeenth-century France; second, that the gendering of the Ottoman figure in both theatrical and epistolary *Turquerie* reveals a tension between subjection and agency that complicates simple narratives of Oriental passivity; third, that the structural liminality of Turkey – between Europe and the Orient, between the familiar and the foreign – generated a dialectical imaginary that shaped cultural representations across multiple media; and fourth, that *Turquerie*'s temporal structure was retrospectively constructed and historically contingent rather than simply reflective of immediate cultural encounters.

The scientific novelty of this contribution lies in the systematic comparative reading of theatrical, geographical, and epistolary sources as a unified corpus, revealing structural correspondences and tensions that individual analyses of each body of material have been unable to identify. In particular, the juxtaposition of Requemora's theatrical analysis with Gündüz's reading of Montagu foregrounds the contrast between the theatrical Ottoman woman as a political function and the epistolary Ottoman woman as a social subject – a contrast that has significant implications for the history of cross-cultural representation and the gendered dimensions of Orientalist discourse.

Future research might productively extend the comparative framework proposed here to include Ottoman sources that record indigenous responses to European fascination with Turkish culture, as well as to examine the afterlives of *Turquerie* in nineteenth- and twentieth-century cultural production, where its theatrical and sartorial modalities were revived and transformed under very different geopolitical conditions. The question of how Ottoman self-representation interacted with and responded to European *Turquerie* remains largely unexplored and constitutes a significant lacuna in current scholarship.

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SOCIO-CULTURAL ESSENCE OF HUMAN WELL-BEING

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Abstract. *The article considers those material and spiritual foundations of a prosperous life that ensure the stability of human existence in conditions that meet and do not meet objective criteria of well-being. It is asserted that the well-being of a person as a social being and a cultural subject, in contrast to the biological well-being and normal functioning of his body, means the acquisition and continuous improvement of such socio-cultural qualities that make a person capable of conscious, creative, and normatively regulated activities. Gaining “well-being” at the cost of losing these qualities is equivalent to destroying a person as a socio-cultural subject.*

Keywords: *human well-being, socio-cultural qualities, value resource of social adaptation, spiritual motivation, standards of material and spiritual well-being.*

Like all socio-cultural characteristics, well-being is a dialectical unity of the material and spiritual aspects of human existence. There are not only universal criteria for assessing the degree of satisfaction of basic material and spiritual needs, applicable to the analysis of the vital activity of any cultural subjects, but also objective economic, social, political, and legal conditions, the absence of which does not allow a person to feel prosperous with any degree of autonomy from the outside world.

However, whatever the material, objectively fixed features of a cultural subject's life activity may be, only he himself can judge his own well-being or disadvantage, thereby expressing his own perception of the degree of satisfaction of his needs. There have always been and always will be people whose assessment of their own lives does not correspond to the public assessment and opinion of others about their inner state. No amount of exhortation can convince a person that his life is completely safe or completely not safe if he does not feel it himself, but, on the contrary, perceives his existence either as dysfunctional and requiring change, or as completely safe and not influenced by external factors.

This article examines those material and spiritual foundations of a prosperous life that ensure the stability of human existence in conditions that meet and do not meet objective criteria of well-being.

The well-being of a person as a social being and a cultural subject, in contrast to the biological well-being and normal functioning of his body, means the acquisition and continuous improvement of such socio-cultural qualities that make a person capable of conscious, creative, and normatively regulated activities. Gaining “well-being” at the cost of losing these qualities is equivalent to destroying a person as a subject of socio-cultural activity, which differs from animal-like, instinctive behavior by the presence of spiritual motivation, the ability to set goals and create meaning.

The process of achieving well-being as a state of satisfying the material and spiritual needs of cultural subjects is essentially adaptive, requiring people to be able to resist circumstances that hinder the achievement of their goals, the desire to defend their value orientations and ideals, and confidence in their life purposes. The ability to adapt to any natural and social conditions, even the most cruel and inhumane, without losing socio-cultural essence and individual certainty, is one of the most important features of a person as a subject of culture, and the formation of this ability is one of the main tasks of both the process of socialization in general and the process of vocational training in particular.

Despite the inexhaustible reserves of adaptive resources potentially contained in a person’s ability to carry out conscious practical activities, the very possibility of using these resources is determined by the level of development and the actual state of one of them – the value one. The value dimension of human life activity is a powerful resource for social adaptation and well-being, primarily because it provides an opportunity for spiritual motivation of the types of activities required by objective conditions while preserving the identity of the subject of activity [5].

This resource is inaccessible to the direct impact of environmental factors and cannot be destroyed even by deprivations that exceed a person’s physical strength: a value resource disappears only with the very bearer and creator of goals and meanings – a person as a subject of socio-cultural activity. Acting as the main resource and condition for achieving well-being, the value dimension of a cultural subject’s life activity contains fundamental criteria for perceiving human existence as prosperous or dysfunctional [4].

The degree of embodiment in human life of the ultimate goals and meanings of human life: Truth, Good and Beauty – should be considered as the absolute criterion of socio-cultural well-being. Where the value regulation ends, the kingdom of nature begins. An attempt to adapt to conditions in which the Truth, Good and Beauty is being trampled on, become the beginning of the dehumanization of the individual. On the verge of trampling on the ultimate goals and meanings of socio-cultural

existence the pursuit of well-being either degenerates into a struggle to preserve the identity of the subject of socio-cultural activity, or ends with its destruction.

The assessment of the socio-cultural well-being of a cultural subject based on fundamental value criteria must be distinguished from “current” assessments of well-being based on one or another transitory, specific historical grounds. Failures in the process of adapting to constantly changing living conditions, the need for significant adjustments in the usual forms of value regulation and established ideas about the goals and meanings of one’s own life can be perceived by the cultural subject himself as signs of trouble. However, in reality, all these processes are not only natural and inevitable, but also indicative of real functioning of fundamental value criteria of well-being.

The results of socialization, upbringing, and education can be considered successful only when they provide a person with a value resource that allows him/her to adapt to the widest possible range of objective conditions that affect the implementation of her/his life plans, professional activities, and perception of their own life as prosperous or dysfunctional [2, 3].

The lack of spiritual motivation makes it impossible to achieve well-being of any level, type, and content. In turn, the formation of spiritual motivation is conditioned by the presence and satisfaction of spiritual needs that are associated with knowledge of the world, its aesthetic and artistic development, religious and philosophical comprehension, and deep emotional experience.

However, no degree of socialization can destroy the biological needs of a human being as a representative of the species *Homo sapiens*. Yet, any product of material culture is the result of socio-cultural activity, which carries a certain value content, expressing the specifics of the real way of life of the cultural subject who created this product [1].

A low standard of material well-being is expressed in the absence of comfort, convenience, and economy of human resources, while a high standard is expressed in meeting material needs in the most efficient way possible. Achieving a high standard of material well-being requires appropriate value motivation, as a result of which the activity, related to the satisfaction of material needs, turns into one of the forms of self-realization of an individual or a group as social beings and subjects of culture.

Thinking about more and more complete, comprehensive and even sophisticated satisfaction of growing material needs leads to higher standards of material well-being, to the development and improvement of the civilizational side of culture, its substantive and universal normative content. Some cultures are more capable of technical creativity than others, precisely because this creativity is considered in these cultures as highly meaningful, intellectual, liberating a person from unproductive expenditures of physical and mental energy, and therefore highly encouraged and rewarded by society and the state.

The process of standardization and related social institutions arise and exist in society just because the standard, the model that the products of material production must meet, embodies the ability to best meet well-defined material needs of people. Moreover, the higher the level of standardization of material production, the higher the quality of mass-produced products that meet the basic human needs for food, housing, clothing, etc. Ultimately, the “world standard” reflects the presence in the manufactured product of such properties that ensure the maximum (of the realistically possible at this stage) satisfaction of a particular material need.

Thus, the satisfaction of material needs is a necessary aspect of human life. However, satisfying material needs does not make a person’s life meaningful, although it does make it more convenient. No matter what physical and intellectual forces the consumer society expends on the production of increasingly diverse and high-quality things, no matter by what ideological means it justifies and glorifies its consumerism, the essence of the matter will not change: plumbing will still remain plumbing, and it will not make human life meaningful and spiritual.

Achieving meaningful existence is the result of activities other than material production. That is why a low level of material well-being may be based on a highly developed sense of meaning, according to which a cultural subject simply does not consider it necessary to spend his life time creating material comforts.

So, human well-being as a socio-cultural characteristic of human life is the inseparable unity of the spiritual and material foundations of human existence. The way of satisfying material needs and the ideal of material well-being are the most important characteristics of culture. However, the lack of spiritual motivation makes it impossible to achieve well-being of any level, type and content.

A cultural subject’s perception of his own existence as prosperous or dysfunctional is determined not by the absence or presence of unfavorable conditions and factors, but by the state of meaningfulness inherent in this existence and a person’s willingness to overcome any obstacles to the implementation of his own plans and achieve well-being.

For a mature person, the problem of gaining well-being is usually associated with finding ways and means to implement one’s life plans in circumstances that are beyond the control of the individual oneself. Only an existence that allows a person to preserve his socio-cultural essence, his individuality, and his life purpose can be considered truly prosperous.

At the same time, it is impossible to recognize as truly prosperous existence leading to a fundamental change in the value content of human life, since such changes are associated with a violation of the self-identity of the subject of culture and, in essence, do not differ from its destruction. A successful socio-cultural existence of a person is a stable, meaningful, value-oriented existence, rooted in inexhaustible reserves of meaning, possessing the ability to self-regulate and a high degree of autonomy in relation to momentary fluctuations in the external and internal environment.

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ART JOURNALISM AS A SEGMENT OF THE CONTEMPORARY CULTURAL MEDIA SPACE: SPECIFICS OF THE FUNCTIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The article examines the place and role of art journalism within the media cultural space amid sociocultural transformations of society. The study proposes theses, organized in a table, that characterize the specifics of its functional system. The research results demonstrate significant heuristic potential and reveal meaningful directions for empirical verification and comparative studies. The prospects for further research involve the empirical analysis of specific media projects in art journalism, comparative studies of national models of cultural journalism, and the development of methodologies for assessing its value-shaping effect.*

Keywords: *art journalism, media cultural space, functional system, sociocultural transformation.*

Introduction

The relevance of researching the phenomenon of art journalism amid the transformation of the sociocultural space is conditioned, on one hand, by the fact that mass culture increasingly displaces complex artistic forms, simplifying semantic codes and blurring value systems; and on the other hand, by the growing role of the media as a space for symbolic production and the contestation of meanings. The objective of the study is to identify the institutional characteristics of art journalism that define its status as a distinct cultural communication institution within the structure of the contemporary media space.

This research is based on a comprehensive methodological approach adapted to the specificity of the research object – art journalism as a phenomenon located at the intersection of media, culture, and axiology.

The inductive-deductive method was employed as the primary approach, enabling a progression from describing particular cases to constructing a general theory, verifying theoretical postulates concerning the value function of journalism,

and uncovering stable regularities in the development of art journalism. The application of the systemic method enabled a comprehensive understanding and structuring of the phenomenon of art journalism. The comparative method facilitated a shift from a simple description of the state of art journalism to the identification of stable trends through comparisons between the 'traditional' and the 'innovative,' the 'elitist' and the 'mass,' the 'value-based' and the 'consumer-oriented,' thereby underscoring the necessity to justify the preservation of the culturally formative dominant within the context of sociocultural transformation.

Within the media cultural environment, art journalism occupies an interdisciplinary position due to its capacity to function as a component of cultural journalism. Art journalism belongs to a broader cluster of cultural media (cultural sections of mainstream media, specialized magazines, online platforms), where art is examined in connection with socio-economic and political processes.

In the media cultural environment, art journalism serves as a mediator between 'high' and popular culture, translating complex artistic language into everyday vernacular, thereby promoting the democratization of access to culture and broadening cultural participation. Through critical analyses of artistic activities (such as performances, exhibitions, festivals), and discussions about art, art journalism participates in forming the cultural public sphere, where issues of identity, memory, justice, and development are debated.

Relying on the key tenets of P. Bourdieu, the mediatization of art through art journalism redistributes symbolic capital: critical evaluations, various rankings, attention to art representatives, and influences their status and the hierarchy of tastes within society [7].

It should be noted that research in the axiology of media indicates that the media are one of the key channels for transmitting spiritual and moral guidelines. At the same time, artistic and spiritual narratives possess a significant potential to shape value frameworks. Cultural journalists highlight socially significant issues through art and function as intermediaries in enriching this art with meaning and value, thereby influencing societal perception of these issues (for example, environmental and climate challenges).

Ultimately, the role of art journalism in the formation of societal values may encompass several dimensions. The normative-aesthetic role consists in articulating norms (tolerance, respect, social responsibility) embedded in artistic practices. For instance, the cultivation of responsibility and respectful attitudes toward nature in society can be facilitated through cultural and artistic practices.

Through the cultural-identificational function of art journalism, representations of 'self' and 'other,' as well as national, regional, and local identities, are constructed via reflection on the cultural heritage of contemporary art [1, 5]. The educational role is aimed at expanding the cultural horizon of the audience and developing skills

for critical engagement with the visual and audiovisual environment. Thus, art journalism in the media cultural sphere serves not as a peripheral, but as a structuring element, where it connects artistic, media, and socio-political dimensions.

The concept of media culture in academic discourse is associated with the culmination of processes of social mediatization and the digital transformation of communications. This allows “media culture” to be interpreted as a distinct type of culture, in which media products and the practices of producing and consuming information play a central role as key mechanisms of symbolic exchange [2, 3]. At the same time, the contemporary media space can be characterized by several features:

- *convergence and multimodality*. The essence of these features lies in the intersection of traditional and innovative media, as well as textual, audio, and visual forms [4];

- *networked nature and fragmentation of the public sphere*. The ‘unified’ public sphere disintegrates into multiple intersecting hierarchical and horizontal spaces, including platform-based and niche communities [6];

- *strengthening of the visual dimension*. The increasing role of visual perception, or the so-called ‘power of images’ in the era of new media, shapes a specific online media reality that influences visual experience and value orientations;

- *interactive participation of the audience*. Users become not only recipients and consumers but also co-creators of media content, thereby altering the structure of influence and the mechanisms legitimizing cultural meanings.

In this context, art journalism functions at the intersection of several professional media subspaces (newspapers, magazines, television), digital platforms (online publications, video services), social networks, and specialized cultural media. The media environment establishes specific technological conditions (format, pace, algorithmic selection of content) while simultaneously serving as a platform for the competition of value narratives, within which the potential of art journalism as an instrument for value formation is realized.

The primary objectives of art journalism are to interpret facts, events, and processes in the field of art for a broad audience, to convey a set of values with both universal and national significance, and, consequently, to shape the aesthetic taste of the target audience. Based on this interpretation and the objectives of art journalism, its functional system can be delineated (Table 1).

Function	Content of the function	Mechanism for the realization of functions	Influence on the formation of value orientations in individuals and society
Culture-forming	Transmission of cultural values and behavioral norms	Transmission of traditional values	Formation of value orientations in society and individuals
		Consolidation of cultural-behavioral norms	Fostering cultural competence among recipients (audience)
		Modeling of aesthetic perception	Development of skills in interpreting art objects
Communicative function	Establishing contact between art, the art agent (e.g., the artist), and the audience	Mediation between the creator of the art object and the consumer (viewer)	Bridging the semantic gap between the creator and the consumer
		Organization of feedback	Formation of an interactive art space
		Adaptation of the language of art	Audience expansion
Educational function	Educating the audience in the fundamentals of art perception and evaluation	Development of educational materials	Formation of cultural literacy
		Contextualization of art objects	Deep and meaningful comprehension of an artwork beyond superficial impression
		Comparative analysis	Development of critical thinking and skills for comparative evaluation
Information and promotional function	Satisfaction of cultural news needs, organization of leisure activities	Announcement of events	Organization of cultural leisure activities
		Recommended materials	Organization and assistance in navigating cultural offerings
		Presentation of new figures in the field of culture and art	Expansion of the cultural consumption field
Ideological	Formation of value orientations and public opinion	Value labeling of events	Strengthening patriotic and spiritual-moral guidelines
		Construction of the cultural agenda	Formation of a positive image of national (regional, local) culture
		Ethical argumentation	Development of a reflexive approach to cultural practices
Recreational	Aesthetic pleasure, reduction of social tension	Visual attractiveness	Emotional involvement, experiencing aesthetic pleasure
		Entertainment	Playful form of cultural engagement, lowering the threshold of entry
		Escapist component	Psychological relief, restoration of resources through culture

Within the described functional system, the culture-shaping function is dominant, since this function is not externally 'added' to art journalism but is inherently inherent in it by virtue of its nature. Art journalism, by interpreting art, inevitably transmits value codes and actualizes them within the media space. Agents of art journalism not only inform but also shape the audience's value system, rendering the cultural formation function normatively a priority. Meanwhile, the other functions (communicative, educational, informational-advertising, ideological, and recreational) serve to realize the cultural formation function. They expand the audience, ensure accessibility of content, and create conditions for perception, while the ultimate goal remains the formation of value orientations. For example, the cultural-mass function (announcements, recommendations) attracts a mass audience, but without the cultural-forming component, it leads to commercialization and the loss of substantive depth.

Conclusion

The conducted study demonstrated that within the intentional field is the representation of a system of values characteristic of a particular historical period, alongside a comprehensive analysis of the specifics of the functional system as the basis of various art forms in the cognition of the world and the human being. The informational and advertising trajectory in the development of art journalism complements the cultural and educational one: each person, possessing creative potential, expands their cognitive and emotional experience within the cultural sphere. Prospects for further research are related to the empirical analysis of various media projects in art journalism, comparative studies of national models of cultural journalism, and the development of methodologies for assessing its value-shaping effect.

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LITTLE LIES FOR POSITIVE COMMUNICATION: PITFALLS OF INTERACTION AT THE CROSSROADS OF CULTURES

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Abstract. *The paper dwells upon the phenomenon of positive communication as a way of constructing alternative social reality; it is also explored cross-culturally in interaction with culturally dissimilar Others. Positive communication is contrasted with negative communication. In this perspective, positive communication is considered as a social-interactive phenomenon of a pragmatic nature. Cultural differences in conceptualizing positive communication viewed as pitfalls of intercultural interaction are examined. Little lies are focused upon and analyzed as a pragmatic value, a cultural norm, and 'a new normal' aimed at creating positivity in relations with communicative partners. An attempt is being made to identify typical motives for using little lies in communication by means of a survey among Russian and international students primarily from South Asian cultures. Other methods used in the ongoing research are participant and non-participant observation, social and mental experiment as well as case studies, followed by duoethnographic interpretation of the results.*

Keywords: *little lies, positive communication, negative communication, intercultural communication, culturally dissimilar Other, norms, pitfalls of interaction*

Communication is the most significant human agency: in communication meanings are constructed and reconstructed, shared and transmitted. Through and by means of communication human relations can be built or destroyed, improved or worsened. People use communication tactics and strategies relying on the norms and standards, as well as assumptions and expectations resulting from

their sociocultural experience. Their cultural ‘mental program’ prompts the right decisions and regulates their communicative behavior.

The situation dramatically changes when communicators come from different national or ethnic cultures, when they appear to be *dissimilar Others* to each other, when the communicative contexts are not familiar to them, and the semiotic spaces of their interaction involve unfamiliar or ambiguous signs and symbols. Dissimilar Others tend to interpret signs and symbols differently, under-interpret them (apply ‘thin’ description, not being able to use ‘thick’ description for comprehensive interpretation), misinterpret them, or even fail to notice them at all. These are the pitfalls of intercultural interaction that are not always visible or tangible; frequently people come to experience them as such only when they fail or anticipate failing in a communicative act.

In terms of pitfalls when cultural differences become obstacles, positive communication is perceived as a universal paradigm of interaction, generated by the prototypical nature of Man, who strives for universal human values, ethics and harmony.

In addition, positive communication increases people’s emotional intelligence, sensitivity, and ability to share feelings and emotions, or referring to the idea of M. Csikszentmihalyi: “The main function of conversation is not to have things accomplished but to improve the quality of experience” (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990, p. 129).

At the same time, there should be no doubt that positive communication is a social-interactive phenomenon of pragmatic nature. In the context of semiosis, positive communication can be compared to the phenomenologically pragmatic practice of gift-exchange where *gift* is conceptualized as any tangible or intangible sign of positive intentions, purposes, expectations, and attitudes. With good intentions in mind, people in all cultures express the spirit of positivity through gift-exchange: “they exchange words of greeting, they exchange hugs, handshakes. They invite further connection, going for coffee or meeting for lunch. Gifts immediately begin to circulate, and they circulate in abundance... The gift-exchange is all about relationship” (Marujo & Neto, 2014, pp. 12–13).

Practices of positive communication can be supported by Duranti’s concept of agency in language: any instance of language-in-use or any act of speaking involves some kind of agency because “by speaking we establish a reality that has at least the potential for affecting whoever happens to be listening to us, regardless of the originally intended audience” (Duranti, 2004, p. 451). Positive communication has a definite potential for creating a new sociocultural reality where interactants feel more psychologically comfortable to display their *alter ego*, that is an alternative and different Self (a smiling Self, a caring Self, a sharing Self, etc.). Besides, positive communication pursues the idea of people’s interconnectedness on our planet.

Julien C. Mirivel argues that conceptually positive communication “refers to any verbal and nonverbal behaviors that function positively in the course of human

interaction and includes all of the behaviors that reflect our best, that produce personal and relational happiness and satisfaction, as well as those that challenge our self to move in the direction of others and to act ethically” (Mirivel, 2014, p. 7). In his Model of positive communication Mirivel presents seven behavioral patterns as constructive elements that lay the basis for the core principles of positive communication: 1. *Greeting* creates contact. 2. *Asking* discovers the unknown. 3. *Complimenting* affects the development of self. 4. *Disclosing* deepens relationships. 5. *Encouraging* gives support. 6. *Listening* transcends human separateness. 7. *Inspiring* influences others (Mirivel, 2014, p. 9).

Olga A. Leontovich defines positive communication as “an interaction based on positive attitude, aimed at mutual understanding and satisfying for all the parties involved” (Leontovich, 2014, p. 125). According to Leontovich, the universal components of positive communication include positive intentionality, initiative, adaptation to the interlocutor, empathic listening and social support (Leontovich, 2014, p. 121). Further on, she extends the characteristic constructs of positive communication to “communicative initiative, involvement, communicative adaptation to the interlocutor, social support, and congruence” (Leontovich, 2020, p. 20–22). While positive communication is “favorable, effective, constructive, expressing positive intention, optimism, psychological support of the interlocutor, a focus on a positive outcome of communication, progress and development” (Leontovich, 2020, p.14), negative communication is “hostile, destructive rather than constructive, demoralizing and ineffective” (Leontovich, 2014, p.122).

When considering the concept of ‘positive communication’, it is important to emphasize that communication is not simply the exchange of information about some facts – it is about *sharing* of everything that can be shared by humans: knowledge, ideas, thoughts, memories, plans, experiences, impressions, attitudes, emotions, and feelings. Besides, people can communicate context, atmosphere, mood, spirit, and various other entities that do not have a typically standard informative nature.

Comparing ‘information’ and ‘communication’, Leontovich points out phatic communication as an example of non-informativity, but aimed at building and maintaining relations: it “can establish a connection and show good attitude without giving new knowledge about facts and phenomena” (Leontovich, 2014, p.123). From this perspective, smiling as a sign of greeting (or just accepting the right for a Stranger to share a lift, car, carriage, compartment, or any other public space); nodding as a sign of understanding; gesturing as a sign of welcoming, inviting, letting pass first, etc. are about constructive (and thus positive) communication. Positive communication is not only about constructing alternative positive reality, it is also about entailing some positive outcome or result: action, idea, mood, or feeling. As Leontovich concludes, a positive communicator is characterized by acceptance, affirmation, agreement, or permission (Leontovich, 2014, p.123).

Meanwhile, from a cross-cultural perspective, positive communication is not culturally expected and socially practiced in all cultures in contact in the same way or at all. The state of expressed happiness in some cultures is perceived as a life imperative; demonstration of positivity as a behavioral norm; optimism as a communicative strategy, while in other cultures displaying positivity in communication may be interpreted as inappropriate, unreasonable, insincere, false, and even stupid (Moshnyaga, 2023, p. 154). Positivity is not a universal communicative value and a cultural norm followed and expressed by interactants worldwide. Russians, for example, reject the idea of positive communication considering it false, unnatural, insincere, inauthentic, fake, deceitful, misleading, and manipulative. The cultural and historical romanticization of sadness, sorrow, and suffering in Russian linguistic culture, reflected in texts, thesauri, and corpora, actually indicates the alienation of positive communication (Moshnyaga, 2022, p. 65). In the same vein, commenting on negative communication of Russians, Olga A. Leontovich refers to the “communicative pessimism” typical for Russians as a communicative norm and adds that “they are apt to complain and self-deprecate”. (Leontovich, 2014, p. 122)

Among the reasons and causes of ‘negative communication’ in intercultural interaction as opposed to ‘positive communication’, incompatible values and beliefs, and therefore – standards and norms, definitely stand out. Without tuning into a certain positive mode of behavior, without changing (without adjusting) our state of mind in accordance with the expectations of our cultural partner (in particular, a culturally dissimilar Other), we (Russians) express ourselves in a habitual way, that is, intraculturally, where negative communication with strangers feels to be the norm. Common arguments among foreigners staying in Russia include claims such as: *Russians never smile, Russians are unfriendly, Russians always look gloomy, Russians are rude, Russians do not show empathy* when communicating with Strangers (with other Others, especially with dissimilar Others). A Nigerian graduate student who relocated to Canada from Russia shared her new experience on social media: *In Russia people smile only if they genuinely like you, and I acquired that behavior, now that cost me a job! I have to learn to smile every time I communicate with someone. Back in Russia if I smile at someone whom I don't know or don't like, it means lying, pretending, being false.*

Russians need compelling reasons to be positive communicators. There is a solid cause for that – that is when they find themselves in the mode of hosts accommodating guests. Acting in the spirit of hospitality and creating the atmosphere of hospitality is about accepting the Other. Otherness has long and often been felt in many cultures as a threat, thus provoking uncertainty and anxiety at encountering the unfamiliar, and developing antagonistic behavior in people. Nowadays national or ethnic differences are not generally viewed as threats. Similar and dissimilar Others have

become part of our regular and daily communicative spaces (infoscapes, linguistic landscapes, cityscapes, touristscapes, eduscapes and other types of 'scapes').

Negative communication can be interpreted as Othering that involves communicative strategies used to emphasize the differences of another culture or people, that is designating them as Strangers and Aliens. Dissimilar Others may signal their dissimilarity to the local community or society consciously (intentionally), or subconsciously (out of habit), for instance, by wearing national dress typical for men in Pakistan, India, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan, such as the *shalwar kameez* during religious festivals or other momentous occasions. Black skin color, or *hi-jabs*, or *shalwar kameez* are visible signs of dissimilar Others for Russians. Such features and attributes can provoke Othering of other Others through avoiding of contact or negative communication or, conversely, this may encourage positive communication: displaying friendliness, open-mindedness, hospitality, and the exciting experience of intercultural contact (without the need to travel abroad) which can become a new cultural as well as human (and humanistic) value. These alternatives are a matter of goodwill, aspiration, positive intention, competence, cultural and emotional intelligence. They are also about manifestation of mutual recognition and acceptance of differences. They are about direct personal face-to-face exploration (and discovery) of the unfamiliar.

What are the ways to express positivity in intercultural communication? Are there universal means? Or do culturally specific modes prove to be more effective? Our research focus in this study is on the phenomenon of *little lies*. As a social, cultural, and interactional phenomenon little lies prove to be applied for the sake of constructing an inclusive positive environment through positive communication.

By a 'little lie' we mean an act of manipulation aimed at achieving a goal; a conscious and intentional use of a distorted view of reality to influence and manipulate the interlocutor's consciousness for the purpose of gaining some benefit. A little lie is a communicator's ability to adapt to circumstances, common to varying degrees across different cultures, and is either recognized, expected, and encouraged, or, conversely, discouraged and condemned. Little lies can be perceived in a sociocultural context as a communicative value or anti-value, a norm or an anti-norm. When considering the use of little lies as a communicative norm, it is worthwhile to refer to the pragmatic value of little lies that is supported by the obvious fact that humans tend to strive for an idealized picture of the world with positive value orientations. As a matter of fact, there is also a norm of expectation of little lies in different speech (or communicative) acts with the subsequent assessment of compliance or non-compliance with the expectations, for example, in greetings, farewells, congratulations, gratitudes, requests, etc.

Little lies as some fictitious messages in communication can also be explained by psychological factors. Deviations from the norm attract attention, stir the mind,

and evoke an emotional response. As a renowned Russian linguist Nina D. Arutyunova argues: “The perception of small facts and familiar objects that regulates everyday life does not provide food for communication” (Arutyunova, 1999, p. 81). Simple communication such as conversation or talk, which have a primarily phatic function, is not so varied as to be unpredictable. Therefore, “even boring interlocutors choose ‘deviant’ material from life for their messages.” Everyday routine life does not excite mental and communicative centers of interacting humans. It is the demand for departure from the stereotype of life that gives rise to little lies. “Deviations from the norm excite not only attention and communicative centers, but also emotions” (Arutyunova, 1999, p. 81–82). In intercultural communication (in the cross-cultural space), little lies in interaction appear to be the new norm, or more broadly, the ‘new normal’. This seems all the more natural and logical in the context of the ‘post-truth era’.

Applying little lies in communication is perceived as natural, normal, and authentic in South Asian communication, as an example. This acquired ability feels like a behavioral habit or a developed competence. Pragmatics of little lies as a communicative competence includes: (1) awareness of the problematic situation; (2) knowledge of sociocultural communication norms; (3) motivation to solve the problem without losing face; (4) communication/manipulation skills; (5) experience of success/failure; (6) ability (preparedness to face the problem); (7) willingness to act here and now (to solve the problem).

Referring to Mirivel’s Model of positive communication, little lies as a method of constructing a positive reality, may constitute part in the contents of messages found within all seven principles of positive communication by Mirivel discussed above.

(1) Greeting: smiling when you are not in a good mood and saying that you are doing great when you are not, for example, responding: “*Absolutely great!*” to the greeting: “*I trust you are doing great!*”. A typical greeting case with little lies involved can be found in the novel “Kane and Abel” by Jeffrey Archer: two partners are greeting each other, asking about their wives as part of the greeting: – *How is your wife, Abel? – Swell. And yours, Henry? – Just great.* And the author comments: “They were both lying”¹.

(2) Asking: inquiring about something and displaying interest or concern when you are in a hurry or do not have time to process the information, when you are not interested in something, or when you receive an answer that is uninspiring, disappointing, or confirms your worst expectations.

(3) Complimenting: praising or flattering someone for any purpose is the most typical case of little lies (our research showed that most respondents believe that compliments are intentional lies designed to please the other person). International

¹Archer, J. (1993). *Kane and Abel*. London: Harper Collins Publishers, p. 407.

students from South and East Asia would frequently email or personally express compliments to their professor such as: *You are the best professor I have ever met! I am proud to be your student! I am lucky and happy to be guided by you!* Russian faculty members never expect to get such complimentary comments from their Russian students (or it would be some very rare and special case).

(4) Disclosing: uncovering something hidden or secret in communication is not appropriate in some cultures, so little lies become helpful: often people are reluctant to reveal some personal information to strangers or feel that they will be not able to express and explain some important nuanced details; or in a cross-cultural context what is appropriate to ask about in one culture is not appropriate to disclose in another one. So, a little lie can be a good way to avoid awkward situations, for example, on issues such as salary/income, age, family relationships, health, ideological/religious beliefs, or political views and preferences.

(5) Encouraging: optimistically insisting that some act, action, activity, or move on the part of our communicative partners would be right because they really want it and expect support, and we do not want to disappoint them. We approve and support, even if we do not believe they will succeed or simply do not know the specific situation: *You will manage! You will win! You will overcome!*

(6) Listening: displaying attention and concern could be achieved through tolerance or/and patience from the part of the listener while having no interest in the topic or issue being discussed.

(7) Inspiring: acting in a similar way as for encouraging but multiplied by complimenting: *I am proud of you! You are the best in your field!* International students frequently email or tell their professors: *I am privileged to be supervised by you! It is a great honor for me to be your co-author! You are the most encouraging and inspiring professor!* Russian faculty members are gradually getting used to such formulas from international students but would generally not like such formulas from Russian students, as they seem too unnatural and insincere. Asian students are taught to express these formulas, though they correspond to the Western style of communication.

The survey conducted by us among Russian and international (primarily South Asian) students allowed us to learn the most typical motives for using little lies in communication (based on our questionnaire with open-ended questions). For Russians the most frequent motives were: *to be like the others; not to be like the others; to save face; to get approval; to avoid blaming; to maintain a dialogue;* for South Asians those were: *making others happy; avoiding conflicts; habit; politeness; safety; defense.*

For Russians little lies are expected in communication with people from Eastern and Asian cultures. There are concepts familiar to all Russians such as ‘Eastern flattery’, ‘Eastern cunning’, ‘the East is a subtle matter’. Russians believe that lying is

not the norm, it is unacceptable, it should be condemned. It is a common belief that if people tell lies, they do not respect their audience. Therefore, when conducting a social and mental experiment, when Russian and South Asian respondents were asked to count how many times per day, and then per week, they used little lies in communication, Russian participants expressed sincere surprise, reporting that they did not expect themselves to use them more often than they had assumed.

Meanwhile, limitations of our study are clearly identified by one of the respondents from Bangladesh: *Our answers about little lies may also be little lies!* However, this comment only proves that little lies are embedded in the mental programming of people from certain cultures.

The study of little lies as a norm in the communicative behavior of people from different cultures in multicultural spaces, in the university eduscape as our example, is ongoing. Our goal is to further identify the universal and the culturally specific motives and reasons, that make interactants apply little lies in communication. Our research interest is fueled by the fact that multicultural classes in many Russian universities that promote international programs are now dominated by students from the countries of South Asia, Africa, and East Asia. Methods used by us for the research include participant and non-participant observation, survey, social and mental experiment, as well as case studies, followed by duoethnographic interpretation of the results (by researchers from different cultures – in our case, Russia and Pakistan).

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EATING THE SEASONS: AESTHETICS OF TIME IN JAPANESE CUISINE¹

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Abstract. *This article examines the role of seasonality in Japanese cuisine as a cultural and aesthetic system through which temporality is materialized and experienced. Focusing on the concept of kisesukan (季節感, seasonal awareness), the study explores how food practices in Japan encode and communicate time, transforming it into a sensory and symbolic phenomenon. Drawing on interdisciplinary approaches from semiotics, anthropology of food, and sociology of taste, the analysis integrates theoretical perspectives associated with Roland Barthes and Pierre Bourdieu to conceptualize cuisine as both a system of meaning and a socially structured practice.*

The article demonstrates how the aesthetics of seasonality are articulated in both elite and everyday contexts, from *kaiseki* (懷石) cuisine to *bento* (弁当) and contemporary consumer food culture. It argues that Japanese cuisine operates as a form of temporal practice, allowing individuals to engage with philosophical notions such as *mujō* (無常, impermanence) through embodied, sensory experience. By “eating the seasons,” individuals participate in a cultural framework that renders time visible, tangible, and aesthetically meaningful.

Keywords: *Japanese cuisine; seasonality; kisesukan (季節感); mujō (無常); kaiseki (懷石); bento (弁当); aesthetics; temporality; food anthropology; semiotics; cultural sociology*

Japanese cuisine is often associated with refinement, harmony, and balance; however, such characterizations tend to obscure one of its most distinctive

¹ The study was conducted under the state assignment of Lomonosov Moscow State University “Theory and practice of teaching foreign languages”, No. 122041400073–2 and “History and culture of the oriental countries; contacts between civilizations” No. 122041300084–9

features – its deep engagement with temporality. The concept of *kisetsukan* (季節感, seasonal awareness) permeates Japanese culture, structuring not only culinary practices but also broader aesthetic and philosophical sensibilities. Rather than conceiving of time as an abstract, linear continuum, Japanese food culture renders it tangible, sensory, and experiential.

This essay argues that Japanese cuisine functions as a cultural system through which time is materialized and consumed. By integrating philosophical notions such as *mujō* (無常, impermanence) with semiotic and sociological frameworks, food becomes a medium that encodes, communicates, and reproduces temporal awareness. Drawing on the theories of Roland Barthes and Pierre Bourdieu, as well as anthropological approaches to food, this essay examines how seasonality operates across both elite and everyday contexts, from *kaiseki* (懷石) cuisine to modern consumer practices.

Seasonality and the cultural construction of time

Seasonality in Japan is marked by an acute sensitivity to environmental and temporal change. The traditional calendar divides the year into twenty-four seasonal periods (*sekki*, 節気), each associated with specific natural phenomena such as the first frost or the blooming of particular flowers [8, 2003, p. 12]. This detailed temporal framework reflects a broader cultural orientation toward observing and valuing transience.

The aesthetic appreciation of impermanence is closely linked to the Buddhist concept of *mujō* (無常), which emphasizes the fleeting nature of all existence. As Varley observes, “the acceptance of transience became a central element in Japanese aesthetic sensibility” [7, 2000, p. 54]. This sensibility manifests not only in visual arts and literature but also in culinary practices, where the ephemeral nature of food aligns with philosophical reflections on time.

Food, by its very nature, is transient: it is prepared, presented, and consumed within a limited temporal frame. In Japanese culture, this transience is not merely acknowledged but actively aestheticized. Seasonal ingredients are valued not only for their flavor but for their temporal specificity – what is known as *shun* (旬), the peak moment of freshness and taste. The consumption of food at its *shun* represents an ideal alignment between human activity and natural cycles.

From an anthropological perspective, food practices can be understood as systems that encode cultural knowledge and values. Mintz argues that “food habits... express the ways societies organize themselves and their environments” [5, 1996, p. 13]. In Japan, the emphasis on seasonality transforms food into a medium for experiencing and understanding time, making the passage of seasons a lived, sensory phenomenon.

Kaiseki and the semiotics of edible aesthetics

The aestheticization of time finds its most sophisticated expression in *kaiseki* (懐石), a form of haute cuisine closely associated with the tea ceremony (*chanoyu*, 茶の湯). *Kaiseki* is governed by principles of harmony, simplicity, and seasonal appropriateness, integrating ingredients, presentation, and utensils into a unified aesthetic experience.

From a semiotic perspective, *kaiseki* can be interpreted as a system of signs. Roland Barthes conceptualized food as “a system of communication... a body of images, a protocol of usages” [1, 1997, p. 21]. In *kaiseki*, visual elements such as color, texture, and arrangement function as signifiers that evoke specific temporal and natural references. A dish might incorporate motifs of falling leaves, snow, or blossoms, thereby situating the meal within a particular seasonal moment.

Rath emphasizes that early modern Japanese cuisine developed as a form of “culinary display” in which aesthetic and symbolic dimensions were central [6, 2010, p. 78]. The arrangement of dishes is not arbitrary but carefully composed to create a narrative progression, guiding the diner through a sequence of seasonal impressions. This narrative dimension transforms the meal into a temporal experience, where each course corresponds to a particular phase within the seasonal cycle.

Moreover, the utensils used in *kaiseki* – ceramic bowls, lacquerware, and bamboo implements – are themselves selected according to seasonal appropriateness. The tactile and visual qualities of these objects contribute to the overall aesthetic experience, reinforcing the connection between food and time. In this sense, *kaiseki* exemplifies a total aesthetic environment in which multiple sensory modalities converge to produce a unified perception of seasonality.

Taste, distinction, and social practice

While *kaiseki* represents a highly codified aesthetic system, it also reflects broader social dynamics related to taste and cultural capital. According to Pierre Bourdieu, taste is not an individual attribute but a socially structured disposition shaped by education, class, and cultural exposure [2, 1984, p. 6]. The appreciation of subtle seasonal cues in cuisine presupposes familiarity with cultural codes and aesthetic conventions.

In the Japanese context, however, the relationship between taste and social hierarchy is nuanced. While elite culinary practices such as *kaiseki* require specialized knowledge, the underlying principle of *kisetsukan* is widely diffused across society. As Bestor notes, “refinement of taste... is cultivated through socialization and education” [3, 2011, p. 45], yet it is not limited to a narrow social elite.

This diffusion suggests that seasonal awareness functions as a form of shared cultural competence. While differences in sophistication remain, the basic framework of recognizing and valuing seasonal change is broadly accessible. In this sense, Japanese food culture complicates a strictly Bourdieusian

model, demonstrating how aesthetic values can be both socially structured and culturally pervasive.

At the same time, distinctions persist in the degree of refinement and the contexts in which seasonal aesthetics are expressed. High-end *kaiseki* dining represents one end of the spectrum, characterized by meticulous attention to detail and adherence to tradition. At the other end are everyday practices that adapt these principles in more accessible forms.

Everyday aesthetics: bento and commodity culture

The incorporation of seasonal aesthetics into everyday life is particularly evident in the practice of *bento* (弁当), a packed meal that combines practicality with visual and symbolic considerations. *Bento* often reflects seasonal themes through the selection and arrangement of ingredients, transforming an ordinary meal into an aesthetic object.

As Cwiertka argues, “the bento represents a domesticated version of elite culinary aesthetics” [4, 2006, p. 134]. The principles that govern *kaiseki* – balance, harmony, and seasonal awareness – are adapted to the context of daily consumption. This adaptation demonstrates the flexibility of Japanese aesthetic values, which can be applied across different social and economic contexts.

Seasonality is further reproduced within modern consumer culture. Convenience stores and supermarkets offer a wide range of seasonal products, often marketed as limited-time offerings. These products, while mass-produced, nonetheless adhere to the cultural logic of *shun* (旬), reinforcing the importance of consuming food at its seasonal peak.

From an anthropological perspective, this phenomenon can be understood as a form of cultural continuity. Rather than eroding traditional values, commercialization reinterprets them within new economic frameworks. As Bestor observes, “tradition... is maintained through innovation” [3, 2011, p. 62]. The persistence of seasonal aesthetics in contemporary food culture thus reflects the adaptability of Japanese cultural practices.

Temporality, consumption, and the aesthetic experience

Beyond its cultural and social dimensions, the aestheticization of time in Japanese cuisine can also be understood as a particular mode of experience. Eating becomes not merely an act of nourishment but a form of temporal engagement, in which the diner participates in the cyclical rhythms of nature.

The notion of “eating the seasons” implies a direct, embodied relationship with time. Unlike abstract representations of temporality, food offers an immediate sensory experience that integrates taste, sight, and touch. This multisensory engagement allows individuals to perceive and internalize temporal change in a concrete manner.

From a phenomenological perspective, this experience can be seen as a form of “lived time,” in which temporal awareness is grounded in bodily practice. The

consumption of seasonal food thus becomes a way of aligning human activity with natural cycles, reinforcing a sense of continuity between the individual and the environment.

Conclusion

Japanese cuisine offers a distinctive model of temporal experience in which time is not merely measured but aesthetically embodied. Through the concept of *kisetsukan* (季節感), food becomes a medium for engaging with impermanence (*mujō*, 無常) and appreciating the transient nature of existence.

By integrating semiotic, anthropological, and sociological perspectives, this essay has demonstrated that Japanese food culture operates as a system of meaning in which time is rendered visible, tangible, and consumable. From the refined practices of *kaiseki* (懷石) to the everyday creativity of *bento* (弁当), the act of “eating the seasons” reflects a broader cultural orientation toward the aestheticization of life itself.

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ARCHITECTURAL AND ETHNOGRAPHIC MUSEUM «TALTSY» IN PAINTING

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Abstract. *The article examines landscape artworks depicting old wooden buildings located within the territory of the Architectural and Ethnographic Museum Taltsy. The open-air Architectural and Ethnographic Museum Taltsy is located near the city of Irkutsk. It contains exhibits related to the initial urban development of the city and its adjacent territories. The city of Irkutsk has a centuries-old history, and its wooden architecture continues to be the subject of in-depth, comprehensive study by specialists across various scientific disciplines.*

This study is based on the paintings by artists: A. F. Vesnina Sketch «Taltsy», 1996–2001, is held at the Municipal Budgetary Institution of Culture «Art Gallery»; A. P. Perminova 'Irkutsk Taltsy', 2004, is located at the State Autonomous Cultural Institution 'Trans-Baikal Regional Art Museum'; V. A. Kuzmina 'Taltsy Museum', 2005, is located at the State Budgetary Cultural Institution 'Irkutsk Regional Art Museum named after V. P. Sukachev'.

Keywords: *Architectural and Ethnographic Museum «Taltsy», landscape, realism, Irkutsk, landscape painters.*

The subject of this study is of current relevance due to its reference to the profound history of the region in question. This concerns the fact that, thanks to the open-air museum, residents of the oblast have the opportunity to freely engage with the way of life of their ancestors who formerly inhabited this territory. 'Monuments of history and culture are structures, memorial sites, and objects connected with historical events in the life of a people, the development of society and the state, as well as works of material and spiritual creativity that possess historical, scientific,

artistic, or other significance.' [2, p. 2]. The Architectural and Ethnographic Museum «Taltsy» is a unique site which, in conjunction with its natural surroundings, creates a singular and remarkable atmosphere of the past, perceptible to visitors. The Museum's allure draws numerous talented and creative individuals, both professionals and enthusiasts, who seek to faithfully document their encounters through art. For this reason, an enduring love for one's small homeland and native land remains pertinent for those deeply connected to their historical heritage.

The objective of this article is to examine the paintings by the artists A. F. Vesnin «Sketch «Taltsy»», A. P. Perminov «Irkutsk Taltsy», V. A. Kuzmin «Taltsy Museum», executed in the genre of landscape painting, to conduct a comparative analysis and to identify their common characteristics and distinctions.

In accordance with the stated objective, the following tasks must be addressed:

- to provide a list of scholarly sources that address the indicated topic in their research;
- to list and describe the methods employed in the present study;
- to provide a concise historical and geographical overview of the architectural and ethnographic museum Taltsy;
- within the context of the aforementioned data, to analyze the paintings created by the artist A. F. Vesnin «Sketch «Taltsy»», A. P. Perminov, 'Irkutsk Taltsy'; V. A. Kuzmina, 'Taltsy Museum'.

The Architectural and Ethnographic Museum «Taltsy» is widely recognized by local residents owing to its symbolic significance and popularity. Each artist, by virtue of their individual talent and skills, recreates the visage of its architectural edifices and the atmosphere uniquely, with personal and creative diversity.

The novelty of this research lies in the analysis of landscape paintings depicting a single specific site, emphasizing features that highlight the commonalities and distinctions among the presented works.

Furthermore, this study possesses practical significance, as all obtained results and conclusions can be applied in pedagogical and scientific activities, particularly in the further research of landscape painting within a specific region.

The present study is conducted employing general scientific methods, including:

- description, which constitutes a characterization of the studied objects – in this case, paintings depicting the architectural and ethnographic museum Taltsy;
- comparative analysis is employed to juxtapose significant features of the elements presented in the landscape artworks;
- induction (from particular to general) in this example may be regarded as an investigation of specific landscape artworks, on the basis of which a general conclusion about landscape painting is formulated;
- deduction (from general to particular) entails the transition from the general concepts of the entire visual arts to the examination of individual specific works;

– following the comparative analysis, the results obtained are summarized and systematized, upon which the corresponding conclusions are drawn.

During the preparation of this study, relevant scientific literature was selected and analyzed, which can be broadly categorized into several groups.

The first group of publications comprises works devoted specifically to the architectural aspects of the city of Irkutsk. Among these are: the article by K. A. Gaskova, A. D. Prusakova, and N. V. Mardusina, entitled ‘Analysis of the Implementation of Historical Patterns and Ornaments in Architecture Using the Example of the City of Irkutsk’ [1]; as well as the scientific work of M. D. Konshina and M. G. ... Zakharchuk, ‘Problems of Restoration of Cultural Heritage Sites in the Historic Quarter of Irkutsk’ [2]; publication by E. E. Ledeneva and M. G. Zakharchuk, ‘Mansions of the Late 19th – Early 20th Century: Historical and Cultural Significance of Irkutsk’ [4]; scientific article by B. P. Yarovoy, ‘Architectural Silhouette of the Irkutsk Wooden Kremlin in the Urban Landscape: Preliminary Experiments in Graphic, Model Reconstruction, and Computer Modeling Linked to Historical Location’ [8]. Preliminary experiments in graphic and layout reconstruction, along with computer modeling linked to the historical location” [8].

The second group comprises works specifically devoted to the culture and visual arts of the Eastern Siberian region, including the monograph by E. S. Manzyreva, ‘Artistic Culture of Eastern Siberia (19th – early 20th centuries)’ [5]; the article by M. V. Moskalyuk and T. Yu. Serikova, ‘Painting of Siberia in the Second Half of the 20th – Early 21st Century in the Context of Cultural Visualization’ [6]; and the work by N. S. Sysoeva and M. A. [Surname]. Averianova’s City in Time. Irkutsk in Paintings and Graphics from the Collection of the V. P. Sukachev Irkutsk Regional Art Museum» [7].

The historical tale Artamoshka Luzin by G. F. Kungurova [3], in the present study, serves an illustrative purpose by providing a detailed description of the earliest wooden structures of the Irkutsk settlement.

The cited scholarly literature fully facilitates an objective elucidation of the present study’s topic: Architectural and Ethnographic Museum «Taltsy» in Painting.

The aforementioned academic literature can also be employed as the methodology of this study.

The Architectural and Ethnographic Museum «Taltsy» constitutes a unique collection of historical, architectural, ethnographic, and cultural monuments of Russian wooden architecture from the 17th to the 20th centuries. The Irkutsk region possesses a multi-century history. The museum itself was established in 1969. The first visitors were able to view the exhibited collection as early as 1980. The foundation of the museum is composed of historic wooden structures from the earliest settlements (villages, towns, rural settlements) of the Irkutsk region, which were partially or wholly inundated during the construction and commissioning of hydroelectric power plants

on the Angara River in the mid-20th century (Bratsk, Ust-Ilimsk, Irkutsk). The museum's name is not arbitrary [1]. Previously, a large village of the same name occupied this site, which was also partially submerged in the lowland areas. Subsequently, the museum was established on an elevated site. Currently, the exhibition is extensive, comprising just over 40 unique monuments of architecture and wooden vernacular architecture, as well as approximately 9,000 diverse exhibits related to the daily life and customs of people from the 17th to 19th centuries [4]. The museum's territory is conventionally divided into four zones, each representing distinct wooden structures and household items of Russian, Buryat, Evenki, and Tofalar cultures. Furthermore, within the museum territory, a section of the Ilimsky ostrog wall has been reconstructed, encompassing the Great Spasskaya Tower (1667) and the Church of the Kazan Mother of God (1697). These artifacts were transported from Ilimsk, a location similarly affected by flooding. Currently, the Architectural and Ethnographic Museum «Taltsy» functions as a recreational venue for both residents and visitors of the city of Irkutsk [8].

The description of the wooden buildings of the original Irkutsk settlement of that period is provided in the historical chronicle by G. F. Kungurova 'Artamoshka Luzin':

Within the watch fortress stood the sovereign's court – the residence of the voivode; it comprised two large chambers – one located beneath the fortress tower, the other as an adjoining structure. Soft light permeated the chambers through windows fitted with mica shutters sheathed in white iron. The chambers were richly appointed: benches painted with azure, Chinese-made carpets on the floor, and a table draped with a patterned cloth. In the warm corner – the icon of the Savior; Vivid reflections from the burning lamp fell upon the silver riza of the icon.

Not far from the voevoda's house stood a series of izbas – the clerk's, the guard's, those of the voevoda's servants and Cossacks, two granaries, a kitchen, two washhouses, an inn courtyard, and a deeply embedded gunpowder cellar. At the center of the ostrog stood a wooden church.

Behind the voevoda's house, in a dark, remote corner, hidden amidst prickly weeds, lay a black izba. Even the voivode's retainers glanced at her with unease and, casting cautious glances around, whispered in fear: 'Pytoshnaya!'

Surrounding the Trading Square were merchant houses arrayed in irregular rows, featuring small windows, closed shutters, and robust gates.

However, not all were privileged to dwell within the fortified walls and thick log structures of the town. The laboring populace – including day laborers, artisans, and plowmen peasants – constituted the common people who resided on the periphery, removed from the fortress walls. They provided food, clothing, and shoes for the town's residents, ranging from the voivode himself to his Cossacks and servants; they constructed, fortified, and beautified the town's buildings" [3, 5].

For the purpose of art historical analysis, this article presents paintings by local landscape artists.

First, we consider the painting Sketch «Taltsy» (1996–2001) by the artist A. F. Vesnin. The composition of the landscape is horizontal. Throughout nearly the entire breadth of the painting along the horizon line, wooden structures, traditional huts, and a cathedral are depicted. Additionally, gates and a fence are represented. None of the depicted structures feature perfectly straight lines. This technique was employed by the artist to convey that these houses and the cathedral have stood for several decades. The color palette of the artwork is rich and exudes warmth. The artist employs a full range of browns and beige tones. The wooden architectural elements of the museum are portrayed during the summer season. Green grass is depicted on the ground. In contrast to the rich warm tones of the huts, the sky and the background featuring hills are rendered in cool shades. These are executed in blue and light-blue hues. Despite the objective coolness of these colors, they nevertheless complement the depictions of the old structures, resulting in an overall composition that appears both harmonious and picturesque. To emphasize the natural robustness of the wood, the artist employs broad, volumetric brushstrokes that create a distinctive texture on the canvas. The artwork appears deliberately unrefined, yet very lively and natural. It is as if the houses themselves wish to communicate with the viewer, presenting themselves as living entities. All objects in the painting are arranged according to perspective and the existing scale, with dimensions corresponding to reality. Thus, it can be affirmed that the work bears the characteristics of the realism style [5]. The atmosphere of the work is warm and vibrant, evoking a sense of joy and uplifted spirit. An authentic landscape can be interpreted as a ‘landscape-mood.’

The following analysis examines the work of the artist A. P. Perminov, Taltsy near Irkutsk, 2004. The composition of the work is also oriented horizontally. In contrast to the previous work, the wooden structures within the landscape are clearly arranged according to three cardinal directions, forming a well-defined rectangular geometric configuration. The wooden houses, gate, and church exhibit straight lines in their architectural forms, which are absent in the preceding work. The artist portrayed a bright, sunny day at the museum. The chromatic scheme of the work corresponds accurately to the natural colors. Green grass, blue sky, and white clouds evoke the atmosphere of a tranquil Sunday afternoon. All details in the work are meticulously rendered by the artist, closely approximating reality. On the basis of the above, it can be asserted that the landscape is executed in the style of realism. In light of the foregoing, this work may be classified as a ‘Landscape as Reconstruction,’ since even the distances between the depicted structures correspond to their actual physical dimensions at the appropriate scale. The artist presents the viewers with a plan-like painting in which specific houses, distinct gates, and a church are depicted, distinguishing it from the previous work [7]. The atmosphere of the museum is neutrally calm, characterized by a predominance of rational information over feelings and emotions.

Finally, we will examine the work of the artist V. A. Kuzmin. 'Taltsy Museum,' 2005. The composition, as in the two preceding works, is oriented horizontally. The artist depicts wooden architectural structures amidst trees within a verdant woodland area. As in previous works, the artist represents a bright, sunlit day. In the foreground, a rural road is depicted, along which flows of people move in both directions. The composition comprises multiple artistic planes and a profound depth of perspective, evident in the river's meander and the opposite bank. The landscape's color palette is notably warm, abundant with beige and brown hues. The objects in the landscape lack distinct, well-defined lines. Within the balanced composition, the figures in the painting are positioned strictly in the foreground, while the wooden structures rise prominently above them. Beyond this, the viewer observes the river and the opposite bank, receding into the sky. Given the perspective and scale, this work can be interpreted as a **Landscape as Scenery**, wherein the human figures situated in the lower portion of the painting correspond to the spatial position of the viewers themselves. Other objects and compositional elements are depicted from an elevated vantage point [6]. Similar to the preceding two works, with a realistic color palette, perspective, and scale, this landscape may be classified as executed in the style of realism. The work's atmosphere is warm, inviting, and conducive to visual engagement.

When considering, in their entirety, the works by artists A. F. Vesnin, A. P. Perminov, and V. A. Kuzmin, which focus on the depiction of wooden structures of the architectural and ethnographic museum Taltsy, it can be affirmed that:

- all the presented works of the artists depict wooden structures of the architectural and ethnographic museum Taltsy;
- all the presented works of the artists belong to the landscape genre;
- all the presented works of the artists exhibit characteristics of the realism style;
- all the artists' works feature a horizontal composition, which establishes a dynamic quality associated with the breadth and scale of the depicted wooden structures of the open-air museum;
- all the works possess a unique artistic representation of the architectural and ethnographic museum Taltsy, dependent on the individuality and personality of the artist who created them;
- the work of the artist A. F. Vesnin The sketch «Taltsy» by A. F. Vesnin can be regarded as a «Landscape as Mood»;
- the work of the artist A. P. Permyakov «Irkutsk Taltsy» by A. P. Permyakov can be regarded as a «Landscape as Reconstruction»;
- the work of the artist V. A. Kuzmin «Taltsy Museum» by V. A. Kuzmin can be regarded as a «Landscape as Scenery».

Thus, in the course of the conducted study:

- a list of scholarly sources addressing the specified topic in their research was presented;
- the methods employed in the present study were outlined (their descriptions provided);
- a concise historical and geographical overview of the architectural and ethnographic Taltsy Museum was presented;
- in the context of the aforementioned data, landscape artworks by the artists A. F. Vesnin «Sketch «Taltsy»; A. P. Perminov «Irkutsk Taltsy»; V. A. Kuzmin «Taltsy Museum» were analyzed and corresponding conclusions formulated.

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**SEMANTIC FOUNDATIONS OF EQUIVALENCE OF PROVERBS
AND SAYINGS WITH ZOONYMIC AND PHYTHONYMIC
COMPONENTS IN ENGLISH, TAJIK AND CHINESE LANGUGES**

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This article examines the equivalence of zoonymic and phytonymic proverbs of English, Tajik and Chinese languages. The study showed that, along with other components of proverbs and sayings of the three languages studied, the use of zoonymic and phytonymic components in their composition is significant. The main indicators for determining paremiological equivalence with zoonymic and phytonymic components in English, Tajik and Chinese languages are aimed at expressing human moral qualities – spiritual and moral concepts, human social activity, human appearance, psychological and emotional state of a person, human labor activity, emotional and mental state of a person, his physical and spiritual abilities, various categories of human behavior, personality, age, physical disabilities, health status, material security, mental abilities.

Keywords: *semantic equivalence of proverbs and sayings, paremiology, zoonymic and pheotonymic components, equivalence indicators, English, Tajik, Chinese languages, various categories of human activity, physical and spiritual abilities of a person.*

Proverbs and sayings are considered one of the genres of folklore of every nation and people, through which ethnocultural characteristics are expressed. The study of this genre, alongside folklorists, is also carried out by scholars from other fields, including linguistics.

The lexical components of proverbs and sayings are diverse, and the presence of zoonymic (animal-related) and phytonymic (plant-related) elements within them is particularly notable. The study of the universal features of proverbs and sayings by various scholars serves to determine their internal connections and equivalence, which is based on the commonality of their meaning and structure.

The subject of this article is to identify the equivalence of proverbs and sayings containing zoonymic and phytonymic components in the English, Tajik, and Chinese languages. The research is based on lexical, structural, and metaphorical equivalence.

Subjective connotation– evaluative meaning – is also considered important in proverbs and sayings, as they express the moral and social characteristics of a person. The study of paremiological equivalence indicators with zoonymic and phytonymic components in the three studied languages shows that they cover the following areas: expression of human moral qualities, social activity, physical appearance, psychological and emotional state, labor activity, physical and spiritual abilities, individuality, and others.

Human moral qualities are an inseparable part of human existence, and traits such as caution, determination and courage, sociability, immorality, frivolity, carelessness, hypocrisy, cunning, curiosity, and others are their main components. In the proverbs and sayings of the three studied languages, these are expressed through zoonymic and phytonymic components as follows:

Better ride an ass that carries us than a horse that throws us – Der oyadu sher oyad [4,155], in Chinese: 欲速则不达 [yù sù zé bù dá] – the concept of careful, deliberate work.

The scalded cat fears cold water – Moĥii tashtdida har mawjro shast donad [22] – 烫伤的猫怕冷水 [tàngshāng de māo pà lěngshuǐ] – the concept of caution.

Give never the wolf the wether to keep // Don't set the fox to keep your geese // Send not a cat for lard – Gurg vakili gusfand shudaast! // Gurgro chuponi andokhtan [4,161] – 不要让狐狸留住你的鹅 [Bùyào ràng húlí liú zhù nǐ de é] – leaving something in danger.

Take heed of the snake in the grass – Bo gurg dunba mekxuradu? bo chupon girya mekunad[4,77] – 留意草丛中的蛇 [Liúyì cǎocóng zhōng de shé] – deceitfulness.

A dog in the manger – Na az man kah, na az vay rah [4,245] – 马槽里的一条狗 [Mǎcáo lǐ de yītiáo gǒu] – neither for oneself nor for others.

He that will steal an egg will steal an ox – Tukhmduzd shuturduzd meshavad // Murgduzd shuturduzd meshavad [4,302] – 偷蛋者将偷牛 [Tōu dàn zhě jiāng tōu niú] – a thief in small things is a thief in large things.

One cannot run with the hare and hunt with the hounds // Dogs that put up many hares kill none – Sagi dukhona sabil monad // Sagi dukhona miyoni roh ast [4,67] // Murgi hamagir hejgir ast! [22] – 饲养许多野兔的狗不会杀死任何野兔 [Siyǎng xǔduō yětù de gǒu bù huì shā sī rènhe yětù] – indecisiveness.

Don't ride a high horse – Ba aspi qashqa savor shudan – 不要骑得高高在上 [Bùyào qí dé gāogāozàishàng] – one should not be arrogant.

Every dog is a lion at home – Har sag dar nazdi honai khud sher ast // Sag dar khonai sohibash sher ast [4,243] – 公雞在自己的糞堆上稱雄。狗是百步王，只在門前狠 – everyone is strong at home.

Barking dogs seldom bite // Dogs that bark at a distance don't bark at hand – Sagi loyanda giranda naboshad [22] – 狂吠的狗很少咬人。善吠的狗不咬人 – loud noise, no action.

What can you expect from a hog but a grunt? // Geese with geese and women with women – Gurg bo gusfand oshnoi nadorad // Barzagov gul nabuvad va oshnoii bulbul najuyad [4,111;4,161] – 鵝與鵝 [É yǔ é, women yǔ women] – like seeks like.

When the fox preaches, take care of your geese – Gurba dar khob dumbaro mebinad // // Fil dar khobash Hinduston mebinad // Shutur dar khob binad pumbadon // Hamesha gurba mushro ba khob mebinad [4,122] – 当狐狸布道时，照顾好自己的鵝 [Dāng húlí bùdào shí, zhàogù hǎo nǐ de é] – everyone looks after their own interests.

A wolf in sheep's clothing – Gusfandsuratu gurgsirat [4,167] – 披着羊皮的狼 [Pīzhe yángpí de láng] – a wolf in sheep's clothing.

With foxes we must play the fox – Joyi gul gul boshadu, joyi khor– khor [4,124] – 面对狐狸，我们必须扮演狐狸 [Miàn duì húlí, wǒmen bìxū bànyǎn húlí] – fight fire with fire.

Two dogs over one bone seldom agree – Du tarbuz ba yak qultuq nabebarad [4,185] – 过着猫狗的生活 [Guòzhe māo gǒu de shēnghuó] – two rulers cannot coexist; conveys mutual exclusivity.

Another group of equivalent proverbs with zoonymic and phytonymic components in the three studied languages is formed through the expression of life experience, the nature of life, hardships, misfortune, and failure. Clear examples include:

A curst cow has short horns – Govi beshir ovozi baland dorad // Ovozi govi beshir baland ast [22] – 诅咒牛的角很短 [Zǔzhòu niú de jiǎo hěn duǎn] – meaningless talk, nonsense.

A fly in the ointment – Yak govi rikhin hama podaro meolonad [4,36] – 美中不足 [Měizhōngbùzú] – the concept of an obstacle.

As the tree falls, so shall it lie – Darakhti kajro alow rost mekunad – Odami badro gur // Darakhti kaj rost nameshavad [4,174] – 当树倒下时，它也会躺下 [Dāng shù dǎo xià shí, tā yě huì tǎng xià] – the concept of irreparable.

Better an egg today than a hen tomorrow – Gurbai zinda beh az sheri murda // Gunjishkb naqd beh don, ki tovuse ba nasiya [22] – 鸟在手胜过双鸟在林 [yī niǎo zài shǒu shèng guò shuāng niǎo zài lín] – contentment.

It is a good horse that never stumbles – Asp chor po doshta boshad ham, peshpo bekhurad [4,96] – 这是一匹永远不会绊倒的好马 [Zhè shì yī pǐ yǒngyuǎn bù huì bàn dào de hǎo mǎ] – possibility of something.

To count one's chickens before they are hatched – Murge, ki dar havost, naboyad dar sikh kashid // Chujaro dar tiramoh shumur [4,302] – 在小鸡孵化之前数它们的数量 [Zài xiǎo jī fūhuà zhīqián shù tāmen de shùliàng] – not to be premature.

Wait for the cat to jump – Mor to rost nagardad, meravad bar surokh [22] – 等猫跳起来 [Děng māo tiào qīlái] – waiting.

You cannot catch old birds with chaff // The fox is not taken twice in the same snare. – Murge, ki ramida gardad az dom, minba'd ba dona kay shavad rom? [22] – 老雀不易受骗 – experienced people cannot be easily deceived.

An old ox will find a shelter for himself. – Barzagov gul nabuyad va oshnoii bulbul najuyad [4,111] – 老牛会为自己找到庇护所 [Lǎo niú huì wèi zìjǐ zhǎodào bìhù suǒ] – everyone acts according to their own nature.

One swallow does not make a summer // One woodcock does not make a winter – Bo yak gul guftan bahor nameshavad [4,141] – 一燕不能成夏。不可言之过早。不可以偏概全 – everything has its proper time.

If the sky falls, we shall catch larks – Gurbai miskin, agar par doshti, tukhmi gunjishk az jakhon bardoshti [22] – 如果天塌下来，我们就去捉百灵鸟 [Rúguǒ tiān tā xiàlái, wǒmen jiù qù zhuō bǎilíng niǎo] – the concept of possibility.

There is small choice in rotten apples – Sagi zard – yori gurg // Lubiyovu kadu la'nat ba har du [4,227] – 烂苹果的选择很少 [Làn píngguǒ de xuǎnzé hěn shǎo] – similarity, little difference.

The fox may grow grey but never good – Gurgzoda gurg shavfd, garchi bo odami buzurg shavad – 狐狸可能会变灰，但永远不会好 [Húlí kěnéng huì biàn huī, dàn yǒngyuǎn bù huì hǎo] – something or someone cannot be reformed.

One cannot run with the hare and hunt with the hounds – Murgi hamagir hejgir ast! [22] – 兩面討好 – being indecisive, trying to please both sides.

Let the cock crow or not, the day will come – Khurus dod zanad nazanad ham, subh meshavad – 选项 鸡叫不叫，这一天总会到来 [Xuǎnxiàng jī jiào bù jiào, zhè yītiān zǒng huì dào lái] – everything has its proper time, regardless of circumstances.

As well be hanged for a sheep as for a lamb – Buzro chi ba anjuman kushandu chi ba sur [22] – 不论是对一只羊还是对一只羊来说，都可以被汗泽德 [Bùlùn shì duì yī zhī yáng hái shì duì yī zhī yáng lái shuō, dōu kěyǐ bèi hàn zé dé] – no difference.

He that would eat the fruit must climb the tree // A cat in gloves catches no mice – Ba shutur alaf darkor boshad, gardanashro daroz mekunad // Ganj be moru, gul be khor nameshavad [4,72] – 吃得苦中苦，方为人上人 [chī dé kǔ zhōng kǔ, fāng wéi rén shàng rén] – calls for effort, labor, diligence.

When pigs fly – Dumi shutur ba zamin rasad [4,196] – 無奇不有。無稽之談 – waiting for the impossible.

He killed two birds with one stone – Bo yak tir du nakhchir – 一石二鸟 [yī shí èr niǎo] – accomplishing two actions at once.

Human social activity is also well reflected in proverbs and sayings, and the equivalence among these linguistic units in the three studied languages is manifested through the expression of concepts such as social relations, subjective evaluation, social status, and family. For example:

Hawks will not pick out hawk's eyes / Dog doesn't eat dog / Crows do not pick crow's eyes / Wolf never wars against wolf. – Zaboni zogro zog medonad // Zog chashmi zogro namekobod // Zaboni murgonro murgon medonad [1.40,204].— 盜亦有道 (чин.) – even among thieves there is a code; closeness in spirit, being “one of our own.”

Who scrubs every pig he sees will not long be clean himself / He that lies down with dogs must rise with fleas / Who keeps company with the wolf will learn to howl – Joyi gul-gul boshu, joyi khor khor [1.40,124].– 擦洗每头猪，没有看到 ville 不会长久清洁化学自身 (чин.) – one cannot stay clean dealing constantly with dirt; everything has its proper place.

Neither fish nor flesh – Na gusolaro shir medihand van a ba poda sar // Na gushtu na mohi; useless [1.40,246].– 既不钓鱼也不冲水 (чин.) – neither this nor that; of no use.

Every cock sings in his own manner – Buzro ba poyi khudash meovezand, guspandro, a poyi khudash [1.40,144] .– 既不钓鱼也不冲水 (чин.) – each person answers for themselves.

Birds of a feather flock together – Kabutar bo kabutar boz bo boz. – 物以類聚，氣味相投 (чин.) – like attracts like; people of similar nature come together.

Fish begins to stink at the head – Mohi az sar ganda gardad, ne az dum [4.142]. – 鱼袋然后头就臭了 (чин.) – corruption comes from the top.

As the tree, so the fruit / As the old cock crows, so does the young – Kunad bachai sher ham kori sher // Az bayzai zog bachai tovu namebaroyad // Az bulbulak bulbulak az chirchirak chirchirak // Az kajdum – kajdum, az mor – mor [1.40,50].– 有其父必有其子 (чин.) – like father, like son.

Many a good cow has a bad calf – Govi khubro hama vaqt gusolaashro bad. – 法力是一个好人，而我们却是一个坏人 (чин.) – good may produce bad; expectations can be deceived.

One chick keeps a hen busy – Gusolaho gov shavand, jigarho khun shavand [1.40,165].– 小鸡帽和嫩珠 (чин.) – waiting for someone (a child) to grow up.

A wild goose never laid a tame egg – Var nfoyd az khonai boz jugz [4.142].– 狂野的诡计从来不会对温驯的鸡蛋撒谎 (чин.) – one's nature follows their lineage.

The black crow thinks her own birds white. – Zog bachai khudro az hama khushruytar medonad [1.40,127].– 馬不知臉長，猴子不知屁股紅 (чин.) – one does not notice one's own flaws.

Expression of factors of human external appearance: human nature, human form, human perfection, and behavior – are considered in determining the equivalence of proverbs and sayings in English, Tajik, and Chinese, as follows:

All cats are grey in the dark – *Gurba shab samur namoyad* [22].

– Chinese: 貓在黑暗中通通都是灰色的。(Māo zài hēi'àn zhōng tōngtōng dōu shì huīsè) – everything looks the same; uniformity.

Can the leopard change his spots / The leopard cannot change his spots – *Oqibat gurgzoda gurg shavad, garchi bo hamdigar buzurg shavad* [22]. – Chinese: 江山易改, 本性難移 (Jiāngshān yì gǎi, běnxìng nán yí) – nature cannot be changed; innate traits remain.

The wolf may change his coat, but not his disposition – *Oqibat gurgzoda gurg shavad, garchi bo hamdigar buzurg shavad* [4,305]. – Chinese: 江山易改, 本性難移 (Jiāngshān yì gǎi, běnxìng nán yí) – character does not change.

As like as two peas – *Yak sebu du kafon* [4,329]. – Chinese: 就像你的豌豆一样 (Jiù xiàng nǐ de wāndòu yīyàng) – very similar; alike.

There is no rose without a thorn – *Gul be khor nest*. – Chinese: 朵朵玫瑰皆有刺 (Duǒduǒ méiguī jiē yǒu cì) – nothing is perfect; everything has drawbacks.

A tree must be bent while young – *Darakhti kajro alow rost mekunad / Darakhti kaj rost nameshavad* [4,174]. – Chinese: 一座树桥被弯曲 (Yīzuò shù qiáo bèi wānqū) – discipline or training must begin early; shape the young while they are flexible.

It is a good horse that never stumbles – *Asb agarchi chor poy doshta boshad ham, goho peshpo mehurad* [22]. – Chinese: 人非圣贤, 孰能无过 (Rén fēi shèngxián, shú néng wú guò) – nobody is perfect; everyone makes mistakes.

The emotional-psychological state of a person, such as: desire, wish, happiness, love and hatred, grief and sorrow, feelings of weakness, fear and anxiety – is another factor in expressing equivalence of proverbs and sayings in English, Tajik, and Chinese:

If you run after two hares, you will catch neither / He, who hunts two hares leaves one and loses another – *Murgi hamagir hejgir ast!* [22] – Chinese: 一心不可二用 (Yī xīn bù kě èr yòng) – inability to be content; trying to do two things at once leads to failure.

He that would have eggs must endure the cackling of hens / The cat would eat fish and would not wet her feet / Honey is sweet but the bee stings – *Ba shutur alaf darkor boshad, gardanashro daroz mekunad* [4,72] – Chinese: 不劳而获 (Bù láo ér huò); 吃得苦中苦, 方为人上人 (Chī dé kǔ zhōng kǔ, fāng wéi rén shàng rén) – one must work and endure hardship to enjoy the reward.

A living dog is better than a dead lion – *Az sheri murda rubahi zinda beh / Sagi zinda bosh, sheri zinda mabosh* [4,83] – Chinese: 活驢勝過死獅 (Huó lú shèngguò sǐ shī) – it is better to have something modest than to lose everything.

When the cat is away, the mice will play / The mouse lordships where a cat is not – *Dar hawze, ki mohi nest, qurboqqa sipahsolor ast* [22] – Chinese: 貓兒不在,

老鼠做怪。閻王不在，小鬼做怪 (Māo ér bù zài, lǎoshǔ zuò guài. Yán wáng bù zài, xiǎo guǐ zuò guài) – take advantage of a favorable opportunity.

Nightingales will not sing in a cage – Odami bekhona, hama jo begona [2,260]
– Chinese: 夜莺别墅不唱卡哲 (Yèyīng biéshù bù chàng kǎzhé) – the importance of freedom; the significance of homeland.

The black crow thinks her own birds white / Every mother thinks her own gosling a swan – Zog bachai khudashro az hama khushruytar medonad [4,127]

– Chinese: 该死的血认为白羊座的鸟听了 (Gāisǐ de xuè rènwéi báiyángzúo de niǎo tīng) – everyone praises their own; no one sees faults in their own.

The mountain has brought forth a mouse – Az gurba sher sokhtan [4,57]

– Chinese: 这座山有缪斯女神 (Zhè zuò shān yǒu móu sī nǚshén) – to make a fuss about nothing; to create something small out of expectation of greatness.

Human labor activity is considered an essential part of human existence. Through it, a person is polished and develops, defining their position in society. Therefore, based on work and activity, abilities and skills, the expression of laziness emerges as another form of equivalence of proverbs and sayings in the three studied languages.

He that would eat the fruit must climb the tree – Ba shutur alaf darkor boshad, gardanashro daroz mekunad [4,72] – Chinese: 并不是说吃水果的人一定要爬树 (Bìng bùshì shuō chī shuǐguǒ de rén yīdìng yào pá shù) – one must work; effort is required.

Grain by grain, and the hen fills her belly – Andak-andak ba ham shavad bisyor-dona-dona ast galla dar anbor [4,87] – Chinese: 谷物会咧嘴而笑，泰亨会是迪克贝拉 (Gǔwù huì liězuǐ ér xiào, tài hēng huì shì díkè bèi lā) – accumulation little by little; patience and steady effort.

An old dog will learn no new tricks / You cannot teach old dogs new tricks / An old dog cannot alter his way of barking – Gurgi borondida – Chinese: 朽木不可雕，老狗学不了新把戏 (Xiǔ mù bù kě diāo, lǎo gǒu xué bùliǎo xīn bǎxì) – experienced person; old habits cannot easily be changed.

The sleeping fox catches no poultry – Az rubohi khufta, murgon nuhufta

– Chinese: 睡狐品质不过家禽 (Shuì hú pǐnzhì bùguò jiāqín) – the diligent reap rewards; laziness yields nothing.

A lazy sheep thinks its wool heavy – Barrai tanbalro bahonai pashmi vaznini ust – Chinese: 懒羊羊认为 (Lǎn yáng yáng rènwéi yīcǐ wǔl hěy) – laziness; excuses for not working.

Categories of human behavior and conduct: actions, reprimands, punishments, dangers; physical condition: age, physical deficiencies, mobility, health, well-being; mental capacity: wisdom, foolishness; moral beliefs: pride, ingratitude, praise, etc. – these have provided a basis for establishing equivalence of proverbs and sayings in the three studied languages.

A bird may be known by its flight / A tree is known by its fruit – Buzi shudaniro az bujulakash ma'lum ast[4,143] – Chinese: 只鸟可能会知道它的飞行 (Yī zhǐ niǎo kěnéng huì zhīdào tā de fēixíng) – reveals the nature of a person or thing.

You cannot flay the same ox twice – Gusfandro az du jo sar namezanand [166c] – Chinese: 鹇鹇不会飞同样的哦抽搐 (Ér miáo bù huì fēi tóngyàng de ó chōuchù) – you cannot do the same task twice; one action has limits.

Do not spur a willing horse / Don't change horses in midstream – Aspi davandaro lajom namebandand– Chinese: 臨陣莫換將 (Lín zhèn mò huàn jiāng) – avoid acting recklessly or changing plans at a critical moment.

Put the saddle on the right horse – Lajomi tilloi ba asp ham ma'qul nest– Chinese: 冤有頭，債有主 (Yuān yǒu tóu, zhài yǒu zhǔ) – making the correct choice; assign responsibility properly.

I will either win the saddle or lose the horse – Yo hara peshi bor, yo bora peshi khar [4,203] – Chinese: 冤有頭，債有主 (Yuān yǒu tóu, zhài yǒu zhǔ) – either success or failure; one must accept the outcome.

Characteristics of human physical and mental qualities: age, physical deficiencies, health, material provision, intellectual abilities, spiritual and moral understanding: self-love, ingratitude, blindness to kindness, praise and flattery, hospitality – these are other categories of manifestations considered in establishing equivalence of proverbs and sayings in English, Tajik, and Chinese, and they appear in the following form:

It will be a forward cock that crows in the shell – Chujai dina az tukhm baromadagi, imruz murgro nasihat mekunad– Chinese: 鸡蛋不能教训母鸡 (Jīdàn bùnéng jiàoxùn mǔjī) – everything has its own measure and level; in-experience shows.

If one sheep leaps over the ditch, all the rest will follow / One sheep follows another – Be chupon barragon poda nestand – Chinese: 如果一个人的脖子超过了比赛，那么其余的一切都会结束 (Rúguǒ yīgè rén de bózi chāoguòle bǐsài, nàme qíyú de yīqiè dūhuì jiéshù) – without guidance, others cannot act.

A cat has nine lives – Gurbaro nuh bor zindaji bakhshidaand

– Chinese: 貓有九命 (Māo yǒu jiǔ mìng) – resilience and survival.

Fine words butter no parsnips – Sukhani shirin az zuft nayorad bar, buz ba bujub bar hargiz nashavad farbeh [4,398] – Chinese: 花言巧語不能滋潤防風草。口惠而實不至 (Huā yán qiǎo yǔ bùnéng zīrùn fángfēng cǎo. Kǒu huì ér shí bù zhì) – pleasant words without action achieve nothing.

It is enough to make a cat laugh / It would make even a cat laugh – Хара ханда, буза бозӣ [4,308]

– Chinese: 足以让聊天笑起来 (Zúyǐ ràng liáotiān xiào qǐlái) – absurd or impossible to accept; ridiculous.

All asses wag their ears – Hamai kharho az ruyi gushashon shinokhta meshavand

– Chinese: 不是 knuvs nov mani bens 制作五个 (Bùshì knuvs nov mani bens zhizuò wǔ gè) – to show one’s characteristics.

Take not a musket to kill a butterfly – Murcharo bo tabar kushtand [4,244]

– Chinese: 所以不是用来杀死蝴蝶的步枪 (Suǒyǐ bùshì yòng lái shā sǐ húdié de bùqiāng) – excessive effort for trivial matters.

First catch your hare, then cook him / Catch the bear before you sell his skin – Nakhchir dar kuhu mo jnro sanji pust mekunem [4,121] – Chinese: 不要謀之過早 (Bùyào móu zhī guò zǎo) – do not act prematurely.

To count one’s chickens before they are hatched – Chucharo dar tiramoh shumur [4,302] – Chinese: 不要做白日夢。不要打如意算盤 (Bùyào zuò báirimèng. Bùyào dǎ rúyì suànpán) – everything has its proper time.

Don’t look a gift horse in the mouth – Aspi peshkashkardaro ba dahonash nigoh namekunand [4,95] – Chinese: 别看礼物马恩泰穆恩 (Bié kàn lǐwù mǎ’ēntài mù ēn) – be grateful for gifts.

To cast pearls before swine – Khugro ruyi miz meshinoni, pohoyashro boloi miz memonad – Chinese: 對牛彈琴 (Dui niú tán qín) – offering valuable things to those who cannot appreciate them.

A good dog deserves a good bone – Sagi khub ustukhoni khubro sazovor ast – Chinese: 好狗甜点和好骨头 (Hǎo gǒu tiándiǎn hé hǎo gǔtóu) – everyone receives according to their ability or merit.

Thus, the study of the equivalence of proverbs and sayings in the three studied languages shows that the use of zoonyms (animal components) is higher compared to phytonyms (plant components) within paremiological units, and their origin depends on syntactic structure, ethnic understanding, and the language system. The structure of paremiological sentences – proverbs and sayings with zoonyms and phytonyms – is more complex, and in most of them, comparative categories include: caution, determination and courage, moderation, immorality, thoughtlessness, negligence, deceit, cunning, curiosity, life experience, character of life, difficulties of life, misfortune and failure, society, subjective assessment, social position, family, human perfection, desire and wish, feelings of happiness, love and hatred, grief and sorrow, sense of weakness, fear and timidity, labor and activity, abilities and skills, expression of laziness, age, physical deficiencies, mobility, health, well-being, mental capacities: wisdom, foolishness; moral beliefs: pride, ingratitude, praise.

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ADAPTATION OF FOREIGN STUDENTS AT A RUSSIAN UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: *The authors consider the problem of sociocultural adaptation of foreign students in the environment of the Russian medical university. The emphasis on positive psychotherapy, which integrates Eastern and Western trends of learning and communication, is of particular interest. After studying the practical works of Nossrat and Hamid Pezeshkian, young medical professionals present their reports at scientific conferences and conduct tests among their fellow students, actively promoting the concept of a positive approach in practice. Young doctors emphasize positive communication in order to normalize a person's psychoemotional state, which undoubtedly contributes to their professional development and the promotion of intercultural tolerance.*

Keywords: *positive psychology, empathy, intercultural tolerance*

Introduction: Arkhangelsk State Medical University actively collaborates with students from India. Psychologically, all foreigners in Russia face a significant challenge during the period of socio-psychological adaptation: they are not integrated into Russian society and are unfamiliar with the specifics of Russian reality. However, the distinctive psychological traits of students, shaped by their mentality, customs, lifestyle, national character, politics, and national-cultural specifics [Vorobyeva, 1999], allow them to adapt to new living conditions and successfully engage in active pursuits. The choice of effective psychological and pedagogical methods is an important direction in the development of modern education.

Solving this problem is partly achieved through scientific work by students in collaboration with representatives of Russian culture. Participation in research projects, symposiums, as well as preparation and presentation of reports on medical topics, helps foreign students understand social and ethical responsibility, develop an ideological stance, the ability for abstract thinking, analysis, and synthesis, and also promotes tolerance. Educating Indian students requires a comprehensive approach

that takes into account their cultural, linguistic, and psychological characteristics. The successful implementation of educational programs not only contributes to the training of professional medical practitioners and language acquisition but also strengthens intercultural dialogue between Russia and India.

Scientific works devoted to the relationship between intercultural communication and positive psychology represent various research directions. T. G. Stefanenko ('Ethnopsychology') describes intercultural adaptation as the process of an individual entering a new culture and achieving social and psychological integration. K. Ward identifies two types of adaptation to a new culture – psychological (based on affective responses) and socio-cultural (related to behavior and the ability to 'fit in' with the new cultural environment). M. Bennett, an American specialist in intercultural communication, developed a model of intercultural sensitivity development, which helps to understand how a person moves from rejecting cultural differences to accepting and understanding them. J. Berry's research highlights issues of integration, assimilation, separation, and marginalization in the context of intercultural interaction. G. U. Soldatova reveals positive ethnic identity as a factor of intercultural competence. The author emphasizes the importance of balancing the preservation of one's own identity with openness to other cultures. In S. V. Chigarkova's dissertation "Personal Predictors of the Formation of Intercultural Competence," the psychological factors affecting the success of intercultural interaction are explored in detail, including the role of personal resources. Works dedicated to cultural intelligence (S. Ang, L. Van Dyne, K. Earley) intersect with themes of positive psychology, such as empathy and openness to new experiences. A. D. Karnyshev, in his research, focused on the socio-psychological aspects of interethnic cooperation and intercultural communication, including the analysis of tolerance, hospitality, and ethnocentrism.

The variety of approaches to this problem proves its relevance at the present stage, and the involvement of young professionals reveals the potential opportunities for their further work. Practice shows that holding scientific symposia and events involving international students has a positive impact on their development, as well as on their integration and adaptation. This contributes to the development of sensitivity to both their own and foreign cultures, which helps them acquire new knowledge, enhances self-esteem, and dispels unfounded stereotypes or prejudices. It also helps them rethink and adjust their assessments of foreign cultures in accordance with expanding skills and experience in intercultural communication.

Research Objective: The linguistic and scientific adaptation of foreign students to the Russian environment encompasses aspects such as intercultural adaptation, empathy, conflict resolution, the formation of multicultural identity, and the development of intercultural competence. The history of the medical university provided students with the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the works of the

prominent psychologist Hamid Parsa-Pezeshkian, who visited Arkhangelsk in 1993 and met with students and faculty of the Arkhangelsk State Medical Institute. Indian students became interested in the theory and began actively using and creatively reflecting on the methods of positive psychotherapy, which are closely related to their religious beliefs and are understandable and interesting to them as representatives of Eastern culture. This is greatly facilitated by studying the Russian language. Studying the legacy of well-known Indian doctors, including the works of father and son Nosrat and Hamid Parsa-Pezeshkian, provides an opportunity to compare communicative interactions of doctor and patient in Russian and Indian practice.

Young medical professionals, in their research, have reached important conclusions. Positive psychotherapy approaches problems in an integrative way and encourages collaboration between different psychotherapeutic methods. Hamid Pezeshkian's methodology is based on the psychosocial and spiritual aspects of human life. The scholar proposes a unified concept applicable to the treatment of any disease. The central concept of positive psychotherapy can be formulated as follows: a healthy person is not someone who is free from problems, but someone who knows how to cope with them [Hamid Pezeshkian, 1993]. Students are drawn to this theory. They strive to build relationships that normalize the patient's psycho-emotional state, making them feel 'lighter,' which contributes to a speedy recovery. A fundamental characteristic of Indian culture leads to important conclusions that facilitate proper doctor-patient interaction. Hierarchical notions are strong in Indian culture: the doctor is often perceived as an authoritative figure, close to the status of a guru, so it is extremely important to find appropriate methods of communication with different members of society.

Materials and methods of Research: Nosrat Pezeshkian, the father of Hamid Pezeshkian, a well-known doctor, scientist with a broad outlook, and a person of bright spirit, introduced a transcultural approach to science, as well as a synthesis of various approaches, emphasizing not the suffering and symptoms of illness, but the search for the patient's life resources. His research is based on the study of various character traits, deep empathy, and the rethinking of the patient's problems, which, according to the researcher, should be based on the body, soul, spirit, and the person's belief in recovery. In working with foreign medical students, modern theoretical methods of working with the presented material were used, aimed at clarifying, expanding, and systematizing scientific facts, explaining, analyzing, and synthesizing the acquired knowledge. Empirical methods, focused on obtaining data through the organization of practical activities, analysis of scientific and methodological literature, surveys, and testing, confirmed the significance of valuable conclusions.

Dr. Nosrat Peseschkian published more than 26 books on 'positive psychotherapy.' Verified practices and rational ideas were further developed in the works

of his son, Hamid Peseschkian. Numerous books, including Russian translations, are dedicated to the theory of positive psychotherapy developed by the scientists. These principles are based on intercultural research on understanding and treating people from different cultures. Studying scientific literature has allowed learners to compare the features of the national healthcare systems of India and Russia. The collection and accumulation of information takes place in the preparation of research materials and presentations at conferences. Students note that the Indian population, especially in the regions, speaks various local languages, which significantly complicates communication. The relationship between doctor and patient in India is shaped by cultural and religious traditions, socio-economic factors, and legal norms. Attention is drawn to family involvement in the treatment of the patient: often, decisions are made not only by the patient but also by the family.

Students Verma Pragya and Himansu Verma in her report, considers the following example: in the traditional interpretation, a myocardial infarction is described as a decrease in the activity of the heart muscle due to the blockage of the coronary arteries. In the positive interpretation, the negative aspect of the disease becomes secondary, but at the same time, the significance of the disease is brought to the forefront for the patient: “A myocardial infarction is the ability to take stress and risk factors seriously.” This approach does not imply that the negative aspects of the disease are unimportant. The goal of the positive interpretation is to change the patient’s perspective on their illness: it is important to start with the positive aspects and only then move on to the negative ones.

Young scientists note the specifics of doctor-patient communication in Indian culture: poverty and limited access to medical services (many patients cannot afford diagnostics and treatment), a shortage of doctors in rural areas, and the fairly common practice of doctors recommending unnecessary procedures to increase their own income. The country does not have a unified federal law regulating patients’ rights. However, positive trends have been observed: the digitalization of healthcare and an increase in the population’s legal literacy.

The doctor-patient relationship in India remains asymmetrical, with the doctor playing a dominant role. Modern medical practice, as recommended by students, is based on the following fundamental principles: strict adherence in communication, special respect for elders and the elderly, as well as the need to follow formal forms of address. In their surveys, students emphasized that patients tend to show a high degree of trust in a person wearing a white coat, and traditional medical systems (Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha) have a significant influence on patients’ positive expectations.

Ethical standards of medical culture bring medical approaches closer together. Professional competence, the principle of ‘do no harm,’ and the absence of conflicts of interest are enshrined in legislation (for example, in Article 73 of Federal Law No. 323 ‘On the Protection of Citizens’ Health’) and professional codes. Foreign

students compare the features of professional medical culture, which contributes to their professional development and the development of intercultural tolerance. The results of a survey conducted at the Northern State Medical University among foreign students showed the following results. The majority of respondents (67%) believe that the use of positive psychotherapy increases motivation and helps in their professional training as general practitioners. Fifth- and sixth-year students were twice as likely as third-year students to note that they had become more open, found it easier to communicate, and sought to maintain dialogue with Russian students on issues of professional ethics. 85% of students rate the accessibility of teachers as “good” or “excellent.” It should be emphasized that the application of positive psychotherapy principles as a tool that facilitates student integration contributes to their professional development and the growth of intercultural tolerance.

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IDIOMS IN ENGLISH: SEMANTIC AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. *The article examines theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of idioms in foreign linguistic. It analyzes existing interpretations of idioms as linguistic units and identifies the main problems of their definition and classification. Particular attention is paid to the correlation between structural – semantic and cognitive approaches, within which idioms are interpreted as a result of metaphorical conceptualization of reality.*

Based on English-language material, a classification of idioms according to the degree of semantic motivation is proposed, including semantically opaque, partially motivated, and transparent units. It is demonstrated that idioms constitute a gradable class of linguistic units characterized by varying degrees of idiomaticity. The findings contribute to clarifying the status of idioms within the language system and to identifying перспективные for further research within the cognitive-pragmatic framework.

Keywords: *idiom; phraseology; semantic motivation; idiomaticity; cognitive linguistics; conceptual metaphor; English language*

Scientific novelty

The scientific novelty of the study lies in the following:

1. A refined classification of English idioms is proposed based on a gradable principle of semantic motivation, which makes it possible to treat idiomaticity as a continuum rather than a discrete category.

2. The necessity of integrating structural-semantic and cognitive approaches to idiom analysis is substantiated, allowing their dual nature to be revealed – as both linguistic and conceptual units.

3. The status of semantically transparent idioms is уточнен; they are interpreted as a transitional type between free word combinations and fully idiomatized units.

Object and Subject of the Study

Object of the study – idioms of the English language.

Subject of the study – semantic and structural features of idioms in terms of their motivation.

Methodology

The study employs the following methods:

- semantic analysis
- structural analysis
- contextual analysis
- elements of cognitive modeling

Introduction

Phraseology, as a branch of linguistics that studies stable and reproducible combinations possessing semantic integrity, occupies an important place in the modern linguistic paradigm [1, p. 12]. Within this domain, idioms are of particular interest due to their high degree of semantic indivisibility and structural fixedness [2, p. 45].

Despite the considerable body of research, there is still no unified approach to defining idioms as linguistic units in foreign linguistics. This results in terminological variation and heterogeneity of existing classifications, which determines the relevance of the present study.

The aim of the research is to identify the theoretical and methodological foundations of idiom studies and to systematize their semantic and structural characteristics based on English-language material.

Theoretical Foundations of Idioms Studies

In the classical tradition, idioms are interpreted as stable word combinations whose meanings cannot be derived from the sum of their components, which allows them to be treated as units of secondary nomination [3, p. 67].

Early studies of idiomaticity, particularly those by L. P. Smith, are characterized by a broad understanding of this phenomenon: idioms are viewed as deviations from normative grammar and logic [4, p. 102]. This approach includes not only phraseological units but also syntactic patterns, which leads to a blurring of conceptual boundaries.

Smith's typology is eclectic in nature, as it combines structural, semantic, and etymological criteria [4, p. 110].

In contrast, Charles Bally considers phraseology as a systemic linguistic phenomenon determined by the functioning of language as a whole [5, p. 28]. Julio Casares proposes a classification based on morphological and syntactic principles, distinguishing nominal, verbal, and proverbial units [6, p. 89].

Henry Sweet differentiates between free and fixed combinations, limiting phraseology to semantically indivisible units [7, p. 54]. A similar view is expressed by

Otto Jespersen, who contrasts free syntactic constructions with formulaic expressions reproduced as ready-made units [8, p. 213].

At the same time, some scholars, such as W. J. Ball, adopt an expanded interpretation of idiomaticity, which leads to a loss of terminological precision [9, p. 76].

The contemporary stage of idiom studies is characterized by a shift from structural-semantic analysis to cognitive-pragmatic approaches. In the works of A. Makkai and J. Strässler, idioms are regarded as units reflecting culturally conditioned models of conceptualization [10, p. 134].

Particular importance is attached to the theory of conceptual metaphor developed by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, within which idioms are interpreted as linguistic representations of basic cognitive schemas (e. g., *ARGUMENT IS WAR*, *TIME IS MONEY*) [11, p. 5–7].

Thus, the analysis of existing approaches demonstrates the multidimensional nature of idioms and the absence of a universal classification model.

2. Practical Analysis of English Idioms.

2.1 Classification by Degree of Semantic Motivation

Based on existing theoretical models, three types of idioms can be distinguished according to their degree of semantic transparency.

Semantically Opaque Idioms

This type is characterized by complete semantic non-compositionality:

- *to kick the bucket* – to die
- *to spill the beans* – to reveal a secret
- *to let the cat out of the bag* – to disclose a secret
- *to bite the dust* – to fail or die

Such units exhibit the highest degree of idiomaticity and function as indivisible lexical-semantic complexes [2, p. 52].

2. Partially Motivated Idioms

- *to break the ice* – to initiate communication
- *to hit the nail on the head* – to express something precisely
- *to burn bridges* – to irreversibly sever ties
- *to keep someone at arm's length* – to maintain distance

These expressions retain metaphorical motivation [3, p. 71].

3. Semantically Transparent Idioms

- *to see the light* – to understand
- *to lose one's head* – to lose self-control
- *to make up one's mind* – to make a decision
- *to pay attention* – to focus

These units occupy an intermediate position between free combinations and idioms [1, p. 25].

2.2 Structural Characteristics of Idioms

The analysis reveals several patterns:

- predominance of verbal idioms;
- presence of stable binomial structures;
- high productivity of metaphor-based models reflecting cognitive schemas.

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These units occupy an intermediate position between free combinations and idioms [1, p. 252].

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These units occupy an intermediate position between free combinations and idioms [1, p. 252.2].

Structural Characteristics of Idioms

The analysis reveals several patterns:

- predominance of verbal idioms;
- presence of stable binomial structures;
- high productivity of metaphor-based models reflecting cognitive schemas.

Conclusion

The study has demonstrated that idioms constitute complex, multi-level linguistic units combining lexical, syntactic, and cognitive features.

The proposed classification based on semantic motivation makes it possible to clarify their status within the language system and to reveal the gradable nature of idiomaticity.

The scientific novelty lies in integrating structural-semantic and cognitive approaches, which provides a more comprehensive description of idioms.

Further research prospects are associated with the study of the pragmatic potential of idioms and their functioning in different types of discourse.

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“I WILL NEVER LEAVE THEE”: RELIGIOUS ETHICS AND FEMALE AGENCY IN ANNE BRONTË’S NOVELS

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Abstract. *This article examines the role of religion in Anne Brontë’s novels, primarily “The Tenant of Wildfell Hall”. Unlike her sisters Charlotte and Emily, Anne incorporates religious discourse with striking directness, making faith a structural and ethical backbone of her narratives. The study analyses how the heroine Helen Huntingdon turns to Christian precepts and prayer as a practical moral framework for decision-making, marriage, and motherhood, tracing her struggle against patriarchal authority and domestic abuse. The article argues that religion in Anne Brontë’s world functions as a source of inner strength, a justification for radical acts, and a lens for social critique of the Victorian gentry. The conclusion highlights that Anne Brontë offers a serious Christian vision that intertwines moral behaviour, religious faith, and personal salvation, while remaining engaged with secular questions of gender, power, and independence.*

Keywords: *Victorian literature, religion, Christianity, female agency, patriarchal authority.*

The work of the Brontë sisters – Charlotte (1816–1855), Emily (1818–1848), and Anne (1820–1849) – was a striking and significant phenomenon in 19th-century English literature. In December 1847, Anne Brontë’s first novel “Agnes Grey” was published, and in 1848, her second and final novel, “The Tenant of Wildfell Hall” appeared. Anne’s talent and place were considered more modest, remembered only as the “third Brontë”. A hundred years after her death, this assessment in the English-speaking world, and especially in Great Britain, is changing – interest in the works of the third Brontë is growing, so her work also demands close attention of literary scholars. The central social theme of Anne Brontë’s novels “Agnes Grey” and “The Tenant of Wildfell Hall” is the depiction of the decline of family relationships within the Victorian gentry. Exploring this taboo subject required a special courage, which the youngest Brontë was capable of.

Anne Brontë's first novel is a work with a linear plot and a small cast of characters. The narration in the novel is homodiegetic – the protagonist, Agnes Grey (whose character, as the novel itself, is based on rich autobiographical material) narrates the events of her life and her work as a governess in wealthy noble families. The novel reflected the trends of the time, when the expression “a governess novel” came into use. The appearance of such works testified to a certain social phenomenon: young educated women from the middle class needed income, which they could find at that time only by working as governesses or companions [4, p. 37–38].

Agnes Grey's independence when faced with reality leads to disappointment. It should be noted that the novel manifests the European theme of “lost illusions”. The conflict that underlies the plot of this work is the clash of dreams and reality, as in Emily's novel, but here it is depicted in a completely different – realistic tone. Agnes' dreams of a new independent life and financial support for her family are shattered while working in the homes of wealthy people, spiritually alien to her, where she has only to obey and please. Meeting priest Feston and falling in love with him changes her life, and accordingly, the author is able to end the novel with a happy romantic ending.

The second novel includes a larger number of characters, creating a broad background for the protagonists' actions. The plot lines in “The Tenant of Wildfell Hall” are more complex, their intersections allows more complete presentation of the novel's circumstances and situations, and the characters are characterized more vividly. They are recognized as typical representatives of their era. Anne Brontë realistically recreates the external and internal aspects of the existence of a man and a woman in the “Englishman's fortress”, and this immediacy sometimes gives the impression of documentary accuracy of description. From a formal point of view, “The Tenant of Wildfell Hall” resembles an epistolary novel.

Like Emily, Anne Brontë abandons the position of omniscient author, typical of classical realism, and introduces two narrators into the work. Each of them presents his own point of view, and this activates the critical consciousness of the reader. Mr. Markham is more masculinely restrained in describing the events and characters of ordinary life that “externally” surrounds the main characters. His story, which occupies the first 15 chapters and the last 8, is the implementation of the “external plot”. The “internal” plot is developed and dramatized in the confession of Helen Huntingdon, which occupies 30 chapters of the work and can be considered a “novel within a novel”. According to genre features, the “internal” novel is a novel of upbringing, in which the author tells her own life story from birth through years of trials – the “school of life” – to the moment when this life stabilizes, takes on its final form. These genre features connect Anne's novel with her eldest sister's novels “Jane Eyre” and *Villette*”.

Like the heroines of Charlotte Brontë's novels, in her thoughts, words, and behavior Helen is guided by God's teachings and commandments. In any difficult situation, Helen turns to a Higher Authority for help: "My burning, bursting heart strove to pour forth its agony to God, but it could not frame its anguish into prayer. <...>. Then, while I lifted up my soul in speechless, earnest supplication, some heavenly influence seemed to strengthen me within: I breathed more freely, my vision cleared; <...>; and then I saw the eternal stars twinkling down upon me; I knew their God was mine and He was strong to save and swift to hear. "I will never leave thee, nor forsake thee", seemed whispered from above their myriad orbs" [2].

Overall, religion occupies a significant place in the heroine's life – the novels are replete with prayers, spiritual reflections, Christian didactics, biblical metaphors, and direct quotations from Scripture. This is easily explained by the pious upbringing of the Brontë sisters, whose father was a country clergyman, as well as their natural inclination toward mysticism, reinforced by the early deaths of older family members. Charlotte and Anne identified themselves as adherents of the Church of England, Emily rarely attended church and their brother Branwell showed early rebellion against official church [3, p. 196].

Anne Brontë turns to the theme of religion not as a remedy for social intolerance, but as the primary and only true guide in human life. Having lost her mother at an early age, she was more influenced than her older sisters by her aunt Elizabeth, who encouraged her religious melancholy [3, p. 106]. In her work, Anne Brontë seems to fit most easily into conventional views on religion and the intersection of religion and art. She seems to have accepted the misfortune that befell her brother Branwell far more fully than her other relatives. She incorporates religion into her novels with greater directness than her sisters.

In the novel, the young, cheerful Helen rejects her aunt's wise and highly moral Christian advice in choosing a husband and, instead, following the dictates of nature, chooses a young and attractive, but extremely immoral, husband. Helen and her aunt argue about her fateful decision, exchanging quotations from Scripture. Over time, she finds herself increasingly estranged from the hostile, cruel, drunkard, and adulterer Arthur Huntingdon. As a result of her unhappy marriage, which led to disappointment, regret, and humility, Helen's image is radically transformed: she is transformed from a young woman entering life (the central character of Charlotte Brontë and many other works of nineteenth-century English literature) into a simulacrum of her religious aunt.

The world of the novel is also largely constrained by a religious vision. We probably have a much more realistic idea of the speech of the stern evangelical Protestants of the upper and middle classes of the Victorian era in this novel than in the much broader and more playful works of the other Brontës.

Solely in God Mrs. Huntingdon placed her hopes for improving her married life. Until his final hours, she tried to persuade Arthur Huntingdon to repent before God in the hope of His mercy, that is, to overcome evil through moral re-education. Helen was a person of integrity, who built her life on the principles of high and humane morality, formed on Christian precepts. Her husband, as well as some of his comrades, sensed this, comparing Helen to an angel: "... you are an angel from heaven, only don't be so harsh and don't forget that I am a mortal man and can make mistakes" [2].

The focus is on the important question of whether religion is a moral foundation for life. This question was quite typical of Puritan culture, both within and without the church in England in the first half of the 19th century. Arthur Huntingdon is portrayed as both "Mr. Worldly Wise" and Beelzebub. His lifestyle, his outrageous penchant for drunkenness and adultery, lead only down a slippery slope. Helen must separate from him while still diligently fulfilling her marital duties, and especially she must shield her son from his father's corrupting influence. She will suffer, but she suffers alongside the righteous, who clearly see the heavenly city coming after "this dark and wicked world". And she takes obvious satisfaction in observing Arthur's pitiful attempts during his illness to find protection from the curse. Helen cautiously suggests, even somewhat heretical for a Protestant, that he may ultimately be cleansed of his sins; but this hope seems dictated more by the rhetorical need to avoid appearing vindictive than by deep conviction.

The novel's central message is that moral behavior, linked to religious faith, saves in this life and the next. Helen finds little support in any version of official religion, and as a nominal member of the Church of England she is not overly concerned with the diversity of beliefs or any specific religious practice, as opposed to the practice of Christian life. She truly places her religious convictions, even when she commits the greatest mistake of her life, at the center of her lifestyle, which is largely in keeping with the evangelical tradition. Like a preacher who realizes the folly of his youthful actions, she is willing to dedicate her life, as her narrative effectively does, to the diary of a reformed sinner. She is not simply a wife whose kindness is valued more than jewels or gold; in her relationship with her husband, she was ready to become, like her aunt, a religious mentor.

Thus, religion is woven into a complex of other values, even in this most austere and traditional of Brontë's novels. The betrayed wife draws strength from religion, which compensates for her loss of power under the blatant patriarchal control of her husband, Arthur. And she is ultimately justified by religion, as many English rebels were when they took politically radical steps: here, in defiance of patriarchal law that grants a husband authority over his wife and children, she steals her own child to save his soul and goes into hiding – a decision we readily applaud as an act of liberation, but which she justifies with her religious convictions.

This somewhat stabilizes the heroine's life, gaining freedom. This was a defiant challenge to the general moral principles of English society during the time of

Queen Victoria. As one of Brontë's biographers, May Sinclair, aptly put it: "The slamming of Helen Huntingdon's bedroom door against her husband reverberated through Victorian England" [6]. But the novel also has a traditional epilogue, where the heroine's fate has taken final form: for many years she has been happily married to her second husband (after Arthur's death).

The depth of her own inner world holds more interest for Helen than the kaleidoscopic shimmer of the outer world, and intellectual development and creative pursuits seem more appealing than the empty distractions of society. Helen's outer story is indeed framed as a more traditional nineteenth-century novel about successful love and eternal happiness in this world. The frame novel about the ordinary world of love, money, and social status seems to initially shroud the inner religious story in potential conflict and a certain irony, and then asserts the dominant view of life: a view respectful of religious beliefs, yet deeply secular.

The main conflict underlying the plot of this novel is the conflict between an independent and original female personality and the traditional Victorian environment. This conflict can be considered as the quintessence of the novel, behind the adventurous plot and complex structure, a deep history of the inner spiritual formation of the individual in her relationships with other people, society, and – in her interpretation – with God.

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THE BASIC CONCEPT OF MEDIA JOURNALISM DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *The paper describes the trends that served as the main prerequisites for the development of the communicative trend in Russian stylistics, the theory of which is actively being developed on the basis of mass media. It is noted that the emergence of a new science, called media journalism, is largely due to the discursive orientation of journalism, as well as the use of the intentional method, which is based on the intention of the addressee. It is concluded that the intentional method, with the help of which the communicative, pragmatic and linguistic stylistic features of media texts are currently being actively studied, significantly expands the possibilities of modern stylistics.*

Keywords: *addressee, discourse, intentional method, integration, communicative, media stylistics, speech activity.*

At the turn of the century, a new direction of research was being formed in Russian stylistics, the appearance of which was due to many objective reasons. The intensive development of communicative stylistics, which is otherwise called media stylistics due to its orientation towards mass media material, was facilitated by global trends: the actualization of the principles of anthropocentrism and expansionism in Russian linguistics, as well as the turn of the research vector from immanent linguistics to functional and communicative linguistics.

However, internal reasons played an equally significant role, thanks to which the linguistic disciplines of the speech cycle became closer to the communicative sciences. First of all, the most important prerequisite for the formation of media stylistics was the active search for the signified discourse from the point of view

of the communicative activity approach, during which new original interpretations were introduced into scientific circulation, reflecting the author's view on the problem of differentiation of the concepts of "discourse" / "speech" / "speech activity".

Although discourse is somehow perceived as speech associated with activity, many scientists point out the ambiguity of these concepts and separate discourse from speech, speech activity, and its products, texts, thus following M. M. Bakhtin's concept of distinguishing the "actual reality of language-speech" from language as a system of forms, from text as a separate speech product and, finally, from the flow of speech itself. Based on L. V. Shcherba's triad "language – speech (speech activity) – language material" in its relation to the subject of activity, G. N. Manayenko considers discourse to be "a generally accepted type of speech behavior of a subject in any sphere of human activity, determined by socio-historical conditions, as well as established stereotypes of the organization and interpretation of texts as components that make up and reflect its specifics" [1:37].

Considering that the participants of the discourse are in the same cognitive space, sharing common cognitive content (knowledge, symbols, views, etc.), it should be noted the relevance of the cognitive approach to the interpretation of discourse, which is a process and at the same time its result. Based on the fact that discourse as a process has a cognitive basis, E. O. Menjeritskaya argues that "discourse is the transfer of cognitive content, put in by the addressee, to the addressee through the text in its linguistic embodiment and the specific strategies of information presentation embedded in it" [2:55]. Thus, in the modern generalized view, discourse is understood as a cognitive-communicative event, the participants of which adjust their speech behavior in accordance with the situation and conditions of communication.

The development of communicative-speech and cognitive aspects of discourse consideration has had a positive impact not only on discursology, but also on other disciplines that pay special attention to the verbal interaction of subjects in a social context. By bringing the concept of discourse to the center of scientific interest and including discursive factors in its subject area, Russian stylistics has thus taken a step towards science, which specializes in the study of various forms and types of discourse. "The dominance of the term "discourse" is a vivid indicator of the change of the scientific paradigm in modern linguistics: from a systematic approach to language learning (when language was considered as a system of systems) to the communicative study of linguistic phenomena" [3:26].

The convergence of these popular disciplines aimed at the study of speech activity did not happen by chance. Back in the first decade of the 21st century, M. N. Kozhina, predicting the future path of Russian stylistics, rightly noted that in the history of this science, the terms "style" and "discourse" went hand in hand. Functional stylistics, realizing the need to involve the socio-cultural context in the analysis of speech works, took into account external factors that are inherently

discursive when determining style: “Style is one of the essential properties of a text that is formed and expressed in its speech consistency, conditioned in a particular sphere and communication situation by a combination of extralinguistic style-forming factors” [4:511].

Due to the similarity of the theory of functional stylistics with the theory of discourse, a discursive-stylistic approach became possible, which opened up the prospects for studying the text as a product of purposeful communication from addressee to addressee. The development of the speech-activity aspect in the style was due to the predominance of a trend leading to integration and creative use of accumulated experience. Having made it its main task to consider texts in unity with communicative parameters, stylistics has risen to a new scientific and methodological level, which has opened up a new system of stylistic coordinates in front of the journalistic text. If in the functional style, the addressee/addressee communication block, the communicative intentions of the sender of the information and the expectations of its recipient remained outside the scope of the study., Conversely, in the communicative style, a large place is given to the participants of communication, the pragmatic nature of the message and – which is very important for mass media research – the translocative effect.

One of the most significant factors in the development of communicative stylistics was the use of the intentional method, first applied by N. I. Klushina in her doctoral dissertation in relation to the categories of journalistic text. “The basis of the method,” writes N. I. Klushina, – we have laid out the most extensive communication chain and deliberately complicated it by including the concept of intention, which has become central to the method (and gave it its name): Addressee – intention – text – communicative situation – addressee – decoding – impact (perlocutionary effect/ communicative failure)” [5].

The problem of intentional speech behavior attracts the attention of many domestic and foreign linguists: J. Austin, S. Fish, B. Fraser, D. Gordon, G. Lakoff, O. Pocheptsov, N. I. Formanovskaya, V. Z. Demyankov, I. M. Kobozeva, N. I. Klushina, L. R. Duskaeva, S. M. Mosheva and others. others. The intentionality of speech is one of the main aspects of linguistic pragmatics, which describes speech acts as ways of expressing communicative intentions. Based on the linguistic and philosophical traditions, the successors of the ideas of J. Austin’s intention was included in the illocutionary act, which J. Austin interpreted it as what “the speaker wanted to say, as his intention expressed verbally” [6].

When describing the problem of intentionality in the communicative and pragmatic aspect, the sociological model of the intentionality of action becomes in great demand, including the following components: “the desire to obtain a certain result; the belief about actions leading to this result; the intention to carry out this action; the ability, skills to carry out this action; awareness of the fulfillment of intention during the implementation of actions” [7].

In modern linguistic and pragmatic research, intentness is understood as “the most important component of speech activity that affects the success or failure of communication, the effective implementation of practical goals of communication participants” [8:3]. The problem of intentional speech behavior involves the description of a communicative intention in close connection with the linguistic means of its expression, which contribute to (or, conversely, hinder) the achievement of the goal. Thus, the linguistic aspect of intentionality turns out to be closely related to the effectiveness of speech impact.

In communicative stylistics, intention is considered not only a textual category that determines the construction of a speech work, but also a discourse-forming one, since the text is, firstly, part of the discourse, and, secondly, the communicative intention can have a global character, which determines the production of many speech works. An important achievement of communicative stylistics lies in the fact that intention is also considered here as a discourse-differentiating category, which makes it possible to solve the problem of the taxonomy of media discourse. According to the researchers, “the problem of distinguishing discursive varieties and establishing intra-systemic interactions between them remains relevant to the present time” [9:233]. From the standpoint of an intentional approach, media discourse is divided into several major varieties: news, analytical, and entertainment subdiscourses.

The advantage of the intentional method is due to the fact that in its content it is an integral method of research, involving the analysis of cognitive, pragmatic and communicative features of verbal communication. Considering that the intention is inextricably linked with the addressee/addressee communication block, the perlocative effect, communicative strategies and tactics that realize the author’s intention and contribute to achieving the goal of communication, it should be noted that the possibilities of media discourse research using the intentional method are significantly increasing.

The rapidly growing popularity of the intentional method in modern stylistics is largely explained by the effectiveness of its application in relation to media texts and media discourse, where both the sender of information and its recipient are of fundamental importance. The high importance of intentions in the organization of this type of discourse makes it possible to define journalistic activity as an intentional activity that determines the pragmatic orientation and linguistic properties of journalistic texts.

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MEDIA JOURNALISM AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF MEDIA LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *A new area of research is described, called media journalism based on the research material. In the process of comparative analysis of the concepts of two related fields, it is noted that media journalism, unlike media linguistics, relies on the category of media style and focuses on the typical and individual stylistic features of media texts. It is concluded that media journalism is a branch of media linguistics.*

Keywords: *concept, idiosyle, media linguistics, media stylistics, media style, media text, speech usage.*

According to scientists, at the turn of the century, a period of extensive study of the media language began, which “opens up new perspectives for stylistics and contributes to a deeper understanding of the specifics and nature of the media language” [1, p.14]. In response to the need for new knowledge about the peculiarities of language functioning and the mechanisms of its use in the media, media linguistics first emerged, and after a while, media journalism. Both sciences, named after the research material, are included in a number of “dual” disciplines (media rhetoric, media philosophy, media culture, media psychology, etc.) that relate to media studies (the Russian-language equivalent of the English phrase “MediaStudies”).

The purpose of our work is to describe the field of research of the young linguistic discipline, which is an important area of the anthropocentric scientific paradigm.

Media journalism has a lot in common with media linguistics, and therefore there is an urgent need to differentiate the subject areas of these sciences. Therefore, it is no coincidence that the idea of differentiating media studies and media linguistics, which put forward different concepts and different fundamental categories, has been brought up for discussion by the scientific community.

The concept of media stylistics is based on the following provisions: “1) style is the specificity of a type of language / speech (professional, genre, type of publication, separate publication, individual); 2) style is the fruit of creative speech activity of a person of one type or another, it is the manner of utterances (texts) created in them; 3) style and stylistic are intentional, because they are purposefully developed” [2, p. 40].

The lack of clearly defined boundaries between the above-mentioned disciplines is explained by the multidimensional nature of their research objects. Thus, the conceptual sphere is considered both as a subject of media linguistics (T. G. Dobrosklonskaya) and as a subject of media stylistics (L. R. Duskaeva). The scientific field of research on authorship (G. Ya. Solganik, T. V. Shmeleva), dialogicity (L. R. Duskaeva, T. V. Chernysheva), architectonics and composition of media text (L. G. Kaida), etc. is also ambiguously defined. The situation that has arisen forces us to look for answers to questions about “which term (media linguistics or media stylistics – Yu.K.) is more optimal and why? Or can both exist? And then how do they differ?” [3, p. 18].

Media linguistics studies a specific social field using discourse analysis and other methods. The object of media linguistics is various thematic spheres of mass media: political (A. P. Chudinov, T. V. Chernysheva); sports (E. G. Malysheva, K. V. Prokhorova); popular science (Yu. M. Konyaeva, M. R. Zheltukhina); cultural and educational (L. R. Duskaeva, N. S. Tsvetova), etc. Dealing with problems of applied importance, in particular, discursive practices, media technologies, media linguistics simultaneously solves general theoretical issues related to the status of media language, functional and stylistic differentiation of media discourse, typology of media language, etc.

Media linguistics is based on the concept of a media text, according to which much attention should be paid to its linguistic and format features. One of the main research problems of this science is the speech consistency of media texts devoted to various aspects of society, from politics to show business. “Mass communication has become one of the most intensive areas of speech use today. The total volume of texts distributed hourly through media channels is steadily growing, which in turn contributes to the growing interest in this rapidly developing field of speech use from academic science. <...> By the end of the 20th century, all the necessary conditions had been created to formalize the accumulated knowledge and experience in the field of media language learning into an independent scientific field” [4, p.18].

Media linguistics is able to cover almost all aspects of learning the language of the media, and therefore, in comparison with media journalism, it is a broader field. As O. B. Sirotinina writes, media journalism is a component of media linguistics, and, therefore, they can be distinguished as generic and specific concepts [3, p. 19].

At the same time, media stylistics retains a close connection with the subject area of traditional stylistics. Along with studying the typical linguistic and stylistic features of media texts, media journalism pays special attention to idioms, linguistic expression of a journalist's position, the use of tropes and stylistic figures, etc.

The difference between media linguistics and media stylistics is primarily manifested in the choice of central categories. Media linguistics puts forward the concept of media discourse as a central category. "We distinguish media discourse and media style as independent, not reducible to each other and not synonymous concepts" [5, p.74]. Unlike style, media discourse is characterized by its material essence (texts that are contained in periodicals, radio and television broadcasts, and electronic media).

Being a continuation of functional stylistics with its central category of functional style, media stylistics is based on the concept of media style, which is defined as a distinctive characteristic of texts produced within the framework of media discourse. The media style category unites media texts that are heterogeneous in terms of themes, genres, conceptual dominants and linguistic features, which relate to different channels of mass communication: print, radio, television, and the Internet. However, style is a part of discourse, and such relationships between the concepts under consideration indicate that media journalism should be considered as one of the areas of media linguistics.

If the linguistic and cultural context is of no small importance in media linguistics, then in media journalism special attention is paid to the addressee/addressee communication block, which increases the importance of participants in media discourse. Studying the phenomenon of media, taking into account the category of the author and other parameters of communication, media journalism develops as a science with a pronounced communicative orientation.

Thus, both sciences – media linguistics and media journalism – meet the challenge of the time by demonstrating innovative approaches and concepts. Integrating into the general system of the media research paradigm, media linguistics and media linguistics provide a deeper and more comprehensive analysis of media texts and media discourse.

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ARTISTIC LINKS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LITERARY WORKS

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Abstract. *This article explores the artistic connections between English and Russian literary works through the lens of comparative literary studies, with a particular focus on typological similarities rather than direct genetic or contact-based influences. Drawing on the theoretical framework of Dionýz Ďurišin, the study distinguishes between socio-typological, literary-typological, and psychological-typological similarities. The main objective is to examine the dialogue between the works of the prominent English postmodernist John Fowles and twentieth-century Russian prose, including writers such as Mikhail Bulgakov and Victor Pelevin. The analysis reveals unexpected yet fruitful parallels in philosophical foundations, poetics, character typology, and the use of mythologism and existentialism. Special attention is given to Pelevin's essay "John Fowles and the Tragedy of Russian Liberalism", where Fowles's characters are reinterpreted within the post-Soviet cultural context. The article also compares Fowles's "The Magus" and Bulgakov's "The Master and Margarita", highlighting shared motifs such as mystery, borderline situations, and the reworking of cultural archetypes. The study concludes that despite differences in national traditions, English and Russian literatures engage in a deep typological dialogue, creating new myths within the frameworks of postmodernism and existentialism.*

Keywords: *comparative literature, typological similarities, John Fowles, Russian literature, Mikhail Bulgakov, Victor Pelevin, postmodernism, existentialism, mythologism, intertextuality, dialogue of cultures.*

Each literary phenomenon, a writer or an artistic work are involved in the national literary process to the extent that they are connected with other phenomena of national literature. The goal of comparative literary studies or literary comparability is to study literary phenomena (a work or literary heritage of a writer, genre, and style) by going beyond the boundaries of national literature. By synthesizing materials from

individual national literatures, literary comparability seeks to understand the patterns of the world literary process. Comparative literary studies identify national features of literary works, compare any phenomena of various literatures, investigate the differences and similarities of artistic elements in works and highlight the relationship of literature with other arts. One of the conceptual provisions of comparative literary studies is the systematic study of the connections and mutual influences of national literatures in their diverse manifestations. Typological and imagological studies seem to become dominating components of the dialogue of cultures.

The transformation of literary themes is a direct impact of globalization on current English literature. Literature in the twentieth and twenty-first centuries has been nothing short of a mirror, showing how people are intertwined and dependent on one another all over the globe. Through exploring such thematic issues, one can see that they reflect cultural diversity among the societies and universal nature.

In many ways, globalization has eroded the spatial parameters that are used to delineate literature on a national basis. Due to this, modern writers usually deal with topics beyond the frontiers of their own countries. Universal themes like love, human rights, migration, environment, and identity are the central focus of modern literature. These themes have universal appeal and touch on basic human experiences, resonating with readers from different cultures around the globe. English literature has a rich history, transcending borders and embracing diverse traditions. But, on the other hand, the era of globalization is characterized by intercultural exchange that has transcended geographical boundaries, reshaped societies, and created a new literary landscape. This is evident in the works of authors such as Salman Rushdie, Kazuo Ishiguro, and Malcolm Bradbury, who combine features of Eastern tales and Western narratives.

In recent years, in literary comparative studies, the main attention of researchers has become not the problem of contact relations, as it was before, but typological similarities, so the center of gravity has shifted to the study of national literature in an international context, in a certain aesthetic system. Although comparative-typological approach as a research methodology seems to be rather young branch of literary studies, polemics and discussions aimed at comparing literary phenomena and trends of different national cultures have been going on since the time of Plutarch. In the twentieth and twenty first centuries the goal of the comparative method is to establish differences, the specificity of the objects and phenomena being compared. Without denying the importance of searching for sources, influence, reception, René Wellek and René Etiemble drew attention to the need to go beyond the boundaries of influence into the realm of broad comparison – parallels, analogies and contrasts. They involved literary phenomena for comparative studies that are not connected by direct genetic or contact ties and enriched comparative methodology with the experience of formalism, neo-criticism, structuralism.

The distinction between contact-genetic connections and typological similarities is a rather difficult task, because these two types of relationships are closely related and intertwined, but they can be applied to the study of one object within the framework of a single study.

Typological similarities can be caused by various factors. In the work “Theory of Comparative Literature Studies” (1975) Dionýz Ďurišin, an outstanding Slovak literary theorist and comparatist of world renown, distinguished the following: socio-typological, literary-typological and psychological-typological [8, p. 183–186].

The author derives socio-typological similarities from the similarity or recurrence of social phenomena and circumstances. As an example, the image of the “superfluous person” in the romanticism of the 19th century, which spread in many European literatures, is given. The emergence of this type of hero was born of similar social circumstances.

The artistic correspondences between the works of John Fowles and 20th-century Russian literature in the context of intercultural communication proves to be the goal of this study. The analysis of this literature reveals that Fowles, “the most interesting talent of the postwar period,” a renowned postmodernist, engages in an unexpectedly fruitful dialogue with 20th-century Russian prose on the level of philosophical foundations, poetics, and character typology.

1) If we take Ďurišin’s opinion about social and psychological typological similarities as the basis for a comparative analysis of characters in the works of Fowles and Pelevin, in this regard it’s necessary to pay attention to V. Pelevin’s essay “John Fowles and the Tragedy of Russian Liberalism” (1993). This work can be interpreted as the example of specific reception: in post-Soviet Russia Fowles’s heroes became symbols for understanding one’s own social and psychological crisis. Pelevin draws a bold analogy: Fowles’s heroine Miranda from “The Collector” is the prototype of the “sovok” – a somewhat dismissive definition of a citizen of the former USSR. For Pelevin, “ovok” isn’t an insult, but a designation for someone who “doesn’t accept the struggle for money or social status as the purpose of life” and possesses “an extra, dysfunctional mental layer”. Pelevin effectively uses Fowles’s conflict (the abduction of a “spiritual” girl by a “bourgeois” nouveau riche) to diagnose post-Soviet society, where the old intelligentsia world has found itself trapped in the basement of a new reality. This is a brilliant example of how an artistic image transcends the boundaries of national literature and begins to live an independent life in a different cultural context.

Pelevin himself provides the key to this comparison. His essay begins with a quote from Miranda’s diary, where he finds something painfully familiar: “Here, for example, is what Miranda writes in her diary: ‘I hate the uneducated and ignorant. I hate this entire class of new people. The new class with their cars, their money, their TV sets, with their dull vulgarity and dull, servile, lackey-like imitation of the bourgeoisie’ ...

‘New people’ are the same poor people. It’s just a new form of poverty. Those have no money, and these have no soul... Doctors, teachers, artists – it’s not that there aren’t scoundrels and apostates among them, but if there is any hope for a better world, it lies only with them” (Translated from Russian by E. Datsler) [2].

Pelevin redefines the concept of “sovok”, linking it to Miranda and the Russian intelligentsia – and this is the central thesis of his essay. From Pelevin’s essay: “Miranda and her friends from Fowles’ novel, the sovoks of Alexander Genis, <...> – are phenomena of the same nature, but of different quality. A sovok is not a Soviet or post-Soviet phenomenon at all. It is simply a person who does not accept the struggle for money or social status as the purpose of life. He looks with disgusted distrust at the bustle of the world outside the window, does not want to become part of it, and <...> lives in the spirit, though not necessarily in the truth” (Translation by E. D.) [2].

Besides that, Pelevin creates a central image for comparison – the metaphor of a broken aquarium, which directly refers to Miranda’s situation in the basement – intellectuals in the Soviet society are compared with goldfish in an aquarium, while Miranda stays locked in the closed place: “People who had been dreaming for years of a breath of fresh air suddenly felt like goldfish in a broken aquarium. Just like Miranda in Fowles’ novel, a dull and incomprehensible force had torn them from the world where all values and meaning were concentrated and thrown them into a cold void” (Translation by E. D.) [2].

In his essay Pelevin explains that Miranda calls her captor “Caliban”, adding, “in honor of one of Shakespeare’s heroes”. This alludes to Shakespeare’s “The Tempest”. Thus, a multilayered chain of intertextuality is constructed: Shakespeare → Fowles → Pelevin, where each subsequent author dialogues with the previous one on the themes of power, freedom, human nature, and civilization.

Pelevin “recognizes” Miranda as a Russian intellectual, appropriating her voice for his cultural diagnosis.

2) Then, from the point of view of literary-typological similarities, we may admit that some Russian and English novels of the second half of the 20th century can be compared through the prism of existentialism and mythologism. Both John Fowles and such diverse Russian authors as Mikhail Bulgakov and Victor Pelevin use myth not as embellishment, but as a structural element. They create “myth-novels” in which the personal story of the hero (Nicholas Urfe, the Master, Pelevin’s characters) becomes a metaphor for the universal laws of existence, and play, the labyrinth, and the search for truth are the main plot drivers.

The unexpected contexts of Fowles – Bulgakov, Fowles – Pelevin (almost in the spirit of postmodernism) may seem artificial and far-fetched, but often it is precisely when the distant things come together their typological connection is revealed.

The work of John Fowles, situated on the border between mythologism, existentialism, and postmodernism, represents a completely organic phenomenon in

European culture. Mythologism manifests itself in the author's desire to create a meaningful subtext – a novelistic level of classical archetypes. Existentialism manifests itself in the realization of the problem of personality development, tested by a “border situation” [7, p. 3]. Postmodernism in Fowles' prose does not lead to the destruction of plot, but the connection with contemporary artistic and philosophical worldviews is realized through the thoughtful creation of intertext. The author carefully creates playful models, characterizing the relationships between characters, and changes traditional meta-stories, which become the author's direct word [9].

Russian culture, gradually approaching an existentialist worldview in the prose of L. Andreev and A. Bely, and in the philosophy of L. Shestov and N. Berdyaev, did not develop a coherent system, which was variously realized in the works of A. Camus, J.-P. Sartre, K. Jaspers, and E. Husserl. The free development of the literary process did not show much interest in ancient Greek mythologism. Russian literature, even in the Soviet period of its development, accepted the principles of postmodern intertextuality closer to the end of the XXth century and maintained ties to the national spiritual tradition in the context of the Orthodox religion.

Dwelling on the literary-typological similarities between J. Fowles' novel “The Magus” and M. Bulgakov's “The Master and Margarita”, it's interesting to accentuate on the motifs, uniting these works – interpretation of the myth, dialogue with cultural archetypes, “borderline situations”, motif of mystery.

Characters of both novels happened to be involved in mysterious situations, but the difference is that in the English novel Nicholas willingly responds to the call to adventure and then leads the reader into the mystery he was led into. Mystery of villa Bournai and its owner Conchis dominated on the Greek island, while some Muscovites rather unwillingly felt mystery of supernatural forces which visited the Soviet capital.

On the Greek island Conchis plays his “Godgame”, during which Nicholas Urfe often turns out to be in “borderline situations”; in Moscow Woland, the antithesis of God, and his assistants play their specific game, where many characters also have to find themselves in “borderline situations”.

Finding himself in the mythical realm of the Villa Bournai, having undergone the trials administered by Conchis, Nicholas attains a higher level of consciousness, gains freedom of choice, and returns to the real world. The Master in Bulgakov's novel, while in the real world, is not free. Only by retreating to the land of myths with Woland's help can he find spiritual freedom.

The works of John Fowles and Russian writers testify that on the basis of old myths (biblical, ancient, literary) new myths in the context of postmodernism and existentialism are being created. This study also allowed to identify common themes, cultural archetypes and motifs.

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**COMPARATIVE LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF TRANSLATION
QUALITY OF NEURAL NETWORKS: YANDEXGPT, DEEPSEEK
AND CHATGPT BASED ON SCIENTIFIC-TECHNICAL
AND LEGAL TEXTS**

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Abstract. *The paper examines the quality of translation of scientific-technical and legal texts performed by three popular neural network models: YandexGPT, DeepSeek and ChatGPT. Using authentic texts on geodesy and law, the authors analyze criteria such as semantic accuracy, terminological correctness, compliance with academic style and grammatical norms. Special attention is paid to the problem of rendering non-equivalent vocabulary in legal discourse. The study also proposes an effective strategy for translator interaction with a neural network, including prompt preparation, draft generation and mandatory expert editing.*

Keywords: *neural network translation, YandexGPT, DeepSeek, ChatGPT, scientific-technical translation, legal translation, non-equivalent vocabulary, AI workflow strategy.*

Present days modern translators have access not only to electronic dictionaries and various online translators, but also to neural networks, which may be a cause of many contradictions. Can a translator use a neural network, and if so, how exactly should one use it to preserve the stylistics and semantic integrity of the target language? How can neural networks be applied in translation practices of scientific-technical and legal cross-regional interaction? Current realities force translators not only to study the principles of neural network operation to understand the mechanisms of translation generation, but also to be able to build an effective strategy for working with a neural network to minimize errors and optimize the process.

The aim of our research is to conduct a comparative analysis of the translation quality of scientific-technical and legal texts performed by the most popular neural

networks in Russia (ChatGPT, DeepSeek, YandexGPT) according to the criteria of semantic accuracy, terminological correctness, compliance with academic style and grammatical norms, as well as to develop an effective strategy for interacting with neural network models to improve the quality and speed of translation of specialized literature.

According to the ranking compiled by Medialogia company based on the number of mentions of neural networks in Russian online platforms, ChatGPT ranks first. This neural network handles the translation of complex literary and scientific texts well, as well as nuances, humor and idioms, and has a significant training base. In second place is DeepSeek, which is capable of adequately translating large general and technical texts while preserving their stylistics. In third place is YandexGPT, which better comprehends and correctly translates names of institutions, slang and bureaucratic vocabulary than its competitors, and can easily integrate into workflows (Search, Translator, Alice).

A neural network is not just a programmed model, but almost a copy of the human brain that uses strictly defined parameters. Therefore, the translation process performed by a neural network differs from that performed by a human translator. For example, the YandexGPT neural network builds translation using a multidimensional mathematical model of language, while the translation is formed from the analysis of a large number of texts in a language pair and determination of their linguistic norms, creation of a certain language model, as well as assessment of the quality of the resulting translation [1]. The newly introduced version of machine translation trained using YandexGPT understands context more accurately, recognizes phraseological units and navigates professional vocabulary. The NLU technology can recognize user intentions, identify and classify key fragments of information in a text according to predefined categories, and also determine the emotional tone of the text [2].

For conducting a comparative analysis of translation quality we selected a small authentic scientific-technical text containing geodetic terms and requiring background knowledge in this field:

Modern surveying basic control surveys

Geodetic surveys involve such extensive areas that allowance must be made for the Earth's curvature. Baseline measurements for classical triangulation are therefore reduced to sea-level length to start computations, and corrections are made for spherical excess in the angular determinations. Geodetic operations are classified into four "orders", according to accuracy, the first-order surveys having the smallest permissible error. Primary triangulation is performed under rigid specifications to assure first-order accuracy [3, pp. 7–8].

A prompt was written for the three neural networks YandexGPT, DeepSeek and ChatGPT [4] and the following query was created: «You are a professional translator

of scientific literature. Translate the provided text from English into Russian using the method of adequate translation. While maximally preserving the structure, rhythm and stylistics of the original».

YandexGPT translation:

«Geodetic surveys cover such vast territories that the curvature of the Earth must be taken into account. Therefore, baseline measurements for classical triangulation are reduced to length at sea level before calculations begin, and corrections for spherical excess are introduced in angular determinations. Geodetic works are classified into four “classes” depending on accuracy, with first-class surveys having the smallest permissible error. Primary triangulation is performed in accordance with strict technical requirements to ensure first-class accuracy».

DeepSeek translation:

«Geodetic surveys cover such vast territories that the curvature of the Earth must be taken into account. Therefore, measurements of baselines for classical triangulation are reduced to length at sea level to start calculations, and corrections for spherical excess are introduced in angular determinations. Geodetic works are classified into four “orders” depending on accuracy, with first-order surveys having the smallest permissible error. Primary triangulation is performed in accordance with strict standards to ensure first-order accuracy».

ChatGPT translation:

«Geodetic surveys cover such large territories that the curvature of the Earth must be taken into account. Measurements of base lines for classical triangulation are reduced to length corresponding to sea level to start calculations, and corrections for spherical excess are introduced when determining angles. Geodetic operations are classified into four “orders” depending on accuracy, with first-order surveys having the smallest permissible error. Primary triangulation is performed in strict accordance with technical requirements to ensure first-order accuracy».

Despite the fact that all neural networks generally coped with the translation, the most adequate version is the DeepSeek translation. It demonstrates a better balance between semantic accuracy, adherence to academic style and grammatical norms. DeepSeek correctly translates key terms such as «baseline measurements», «spherical excess», «orders», «rigid specifications», but excessively uses passive constructions and preserves the word order characteristic of English, which leads to a violation of such a translation quality assessment criterion as the norm of translator speech.

For a more complete assessment of the capabilities of neural networks in working with specialized vocabulary, we performed a similar experiment using an English legal text devoted to types of property rights (freehold estates). Unlike technical text with established terminology, legal discourse abounds in non-equivalent vocabulary, which poses a serious challenge for machine translation algorithms.

A fragment of an educational text describing types of property rights was selected as the material: fee simple, life estate, estate pur autre vie and the obsolete fee tail:

There are generally three types of freehold estate in English-speaking jurisdictions: the fee simple, the life estate and the estate pur autre vie. A fourth type of freehold estate, the fee tail, is now largely obsolete. The transfer of title in land from one person to another is known as the conveyance [5, p. 72].

The difficulty lay in the fact that in Russian there are no direct structural analogues of the English system of land rights. For adequate meaning transfer, the translator is forced to resort to descriptive translation – a technique in which, instead of a direct equivalent (calque or transliteration), a detailed explanation of the concept is given. This method is inevitable when there are no direct correlations between legal systems, and the translator's task is to make the English legal concept understandable to a Russian-speaking reader without distorting its essence. Below are the versions produced by neural networks using an identical prompt:

DeepSeek translation:

«In common law jurisdictions, three types of property rights in real estate are usually distinguished: unconditional ownership (freehold), life estate (life estate) and leasehold (leasehold). The fourth type – ownership of leased property that was in limited use – is now practically obsolete. The transfer of legal title to a land plot to another person is called alienation (conveyance)».

YandexGPT translation (repeated, with a different strategy):

«In English-speaking legal systems, three types of property rights in real estate with unlimited term of ownership (freehold) are usually distinguished: full unconditional ownership (fee simple), life ownership (life estate) and ownership for the life of a third party (estate pur autre vie). The fourth type of freehold – limited hereditary right (fee tail) – has now practically fallen out of use. The transfer of legal title to a land plot from one person to another is called alienation (conveyance)».

ChatGPT translation:

«As a rule, in English-speaking jurisdictions, three types of unconditional (free) land ownership (freehold estate) are distinguished: simple inheritable ownership (fee simple), life ownership (life estate) and ownership for the life of another person (estate pur autre vie). The fourth type of free ownership – hereditary ownership with inheritance restrictions (fee tail) – has now largely lost practical significance. The transfer of ownership of a land plot from one person to another is called conveyance (conveyance)».

The analysis of legal translation revealed significant differences in the quality of neural network performance. YandexGPT offers a significantly more successful translation, preserving the Latin term “pur autre vie” and providing an explanatory descriptive translation in brackets, which is important for identifying the concept in the original source. DeepSeek made a gross factual inaccuracy, replacing the concept

of estate *pur autre vie* with leasehold, which distorts the essence of this concept in English law. Despite this, DeepSeek and YandexGPT correctly conveyed the term “conveyance”, which means transfer of legal title to land, since two options are possible in this case: alienation and transfer of ownership of the land plot to another person. ChatGPT completely distorted the term and rendered it by transliteration.

The conducted analysis shows that to obtain an adequate translation, several stages of work on the text must be performed. First, correct formulating the neural network’s role (e.g., a professional translator specializing in scientific literature). Second, setting priorities and translation invariants (e.g., preserving the stylistics and structure of the original). Third, indicating the presence of special terminology and the importance of finding equivalents. The most significant is the fourth stage, at which the translator must check facts, the use of terminology, and also edit the text in accordance with the linguistic and genre-stylistic norms of the target language.

The case of legal translation is worthy of special attention, as it clearly illustrates the key role of translator: only a person with background knowledge in comparative law can notice the substitution of the concept “*pur autre vie*” with leasehold and edit the final text. Descriptive translation in this case became not just a technique, but a necessity dictated by the difference of legal systems, and the task of any competent translator is to ensure that the neural network does not simplify these complex concepts beyond recognition. Since this is a textbook, a more serious approach to translation is required, rather than a simple enumeration of terms, which makes the use of descriptive translation especially important for clearly expressing the author’s thought and ensuring understanding of complex legal concepts by the Russian-speaking reader.

Thus, a neural network can act as an adequate translation tool if the translator understands the mechanisms of effective interaction with AI in translation activity. Experience working with heterogeneous texts (technical and legal) shows that human-AI synergy is most effective when observing the following stages: preparation with clear formulation of the prompt and indication of the «professional translator» role and style requirements; draft generation, when the neural network creates a basic translation, freeing the translator from routine work; expertise and editing as a key stage, where the translator verifies facts (especially in legal texts, where the cost of error is high), corrects terminology and applies necessary transformations (such as descriptive translation or semantic development) to bring the text in line with the norms of the target language.

Modern translation is not a confrontation between human and machine, but their synergy, where the neural network acts not as a replacement, but as a powerful tool in the hands of a qualified specialist who bears responsibility for the final result.

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THE SOCIAL IDEAL AND THE WORLDVIEW OF A HUMAN BEING: A PHILOSOPHICAL AND TYPOLOGICAL ASPECT

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Abstract. *The article specifies the interrelation between a person's social ideal and their worldview within the philosophical and typological discourse on the cognition of reality. The conceptual potential of this interrelation as a factor in the development of moral-spiritual traits of a socialized personality is revealed. In the context of social ontology, attention is focused on the fundamental properties and functions of the social ideal of a human being, which influence the formation and perfection of their worldview position. The ontognoseological role of the ideal in the dialectical-typological comprehension of the diversity of objective and subjective reality is substantiated. The principles of reflection, comparison, universal connectedness and development, as well as the methods of progression from the abstract to the concrete and dialectical-typological reduction, are employed.*

Keywords: *human, society, worldview, social ideal, philosophy, typology*

That which is within a human being is undoubtedly more important than that which a human being possesses.

Arthur Schopenhauer

The problem of the human ideal occupies a central place in socio-philosophical studies. At various stages of personality development, society has formed specific conceptions of what a conscious human being should be like, what traits (qualities) they must possess, and which spiritual and moral values should guide them in realizing attainable goals, plans, and the destiny-shaping dreams of civilization. In the course of activity, these representations within the consciousness of a positively minded individual not only reflect the worldview content of socially recognized ideological orientations but also perform various functions within their conscious activity. Consequently, the ontognoseological interrelation of a person's social ideal and worldview

establishes reliable guidelines for personal and socio-cultural development, as well as for the individual's search for their place in society, grounded in a genuinely accurate understanding of socio-economic, cultural-political, and ideological realities.

The purpose of this study is a philosophical and typological analysis of the interrelation of a person's social ideal and worldview within the discourse on the cognition of objective and subjective reality.

In the socio-philosophical tradition, the concept of the ideal is interpreted in a non-univocal manner. The dialectical typology of its meaningful comprehension depends on the chosen scientific-theoretical research approach [10]. In the works of many authors, the ideal is primarily regarded in typical meanings such as: the highest goal of human activity; moral-ethical ideal of the ought; imaginary model of perfection; an adequate form of expressing spiritual and moral values; a regulative principle of social development; a prognostic dream (M. Yu. Bilaonova, V. P. Bransky, S. N. Bulgakov, G. I. Gerasimov, V. E. Davydovich, Yu. P. Ivonina, E. V. Kirpechenok [3], G. P. Kovaleva, A. I. Matveeva, L. D. Milkinen, E. N. Moschelkova, N. A. Novikov, E. V. Osichnyuk; I. I. Remezova, S. V. Timofeeva, T. A. Kharlamova, V. I. Filatov, O. P. Tselikova, E. L. Chertkova, A. I. Yatsenko).

Undoubtedly, the ideal does not exist outside the social context; it embodies a vast spiritual potential anchored in the ideological-social, moral-ethical, national-cultural values, as well as in the cognitive-intellectual ideas of the individual and society.

As the study has demonstrated, the ideal is formed within specific anthropo-historical conditions, develops within the realities of the socio-cultural environment, and reflects the structure of social ties and relationships within a particular social system. The ideal justifiably serves as the highest goal for a person on the path of moral and spiritual growth and intellectual refinement, including self-improvement, thus defining the sincerity of their thoughts and actions. This is the view of G. P. According to Kovaleva, a social ideal is understood as the concept of a person as the highest goal of development – a kind of socio-cultural model that shapes the thinking, behavior, and activity of an individual. The concept of an ideal state of society and the individual reflects the most significant values of a given culture, serving as a criterion for evaluating reality and as a guide for the actions of individuals, social groups, classes, and society as a whole. The social ideal is intended to serve as a criterion for evaluating both an individual's personal qualities and the development of a specific society, as well as humanity as a whole [4, p. 36].

Within the framework of socio-philosophical discourse, the ideal is understood as a meaning-constituting form reflecting the supreme values of the individual and society, embedded in culture and manifested through the multifarious process of their collaborative activity [6]. In contrast to empirical personality traits, the ideal does not describe the current state of the individual in terms of orientations, social status, or character traits, but primarily represents the overall direction of

cognitive-social development and sustainable individual self-improvement. This is why the social ideal is necessarily a product of social existence and social consciousness, thereby reflecting the culture-laden structure of worldview linkages and relations within a specific society. On this subject, the German philosopher Albert Schweitzer, addressing the socio-cultural foundations of an individual's worldview stance, emphasized that the ideal of a cultured person is nothing other than the ideal of one who preserves their authentic humanity under all circumstances.

It is characteristic that the concept of the ideal occupies a significant place within the system of philosophical categories, as it is connected with the dialectical-typological reflection on the relations between the normative and the real, the actual and the potential, the normative and the factual, the possible and the actual, the assumed and the attainable. In the most general sense, the ideal can be defined as the highest value of human existence, serving as a reliable guide for the individual's life activity, a personal instrument of intellectual development, and the comprehension of the laws of being.

From a philosophical perspective, it is methodologically important to distinguish the ideal from closely related concepts in meaning: idea, value, norm, goal, attitude, intention, and orientation. For instance, a value expresses the significance of a phenomenon for an individual or society, a norm establishes generally accepted behavioral rules, and a goal is directed toward achieving a specific practical outcome. Each of these definitions is typologically determined and therefore bears its own distinct meaning and function.

Communicativeness and the mentality of a person's social ideal are of significant importance. The intellectual potential of a conscious personality is actualized through interaction with others, as it is precisely in communication that the exchange of cultural experiences and the consolidation of social roles take place. The capacity for social dialogue, creative collaboration, and respectful mutual understanding constitutes essential conditions for the full participation of any individual in social life.

The social activity of an individual, imbued with their ideals and aspirations, is also among the essential characteristics of human nature. The essence of this type of activity lies in the individual's patriotic readiness to engage in social processes, the ability to exhibit social-political initiative, and the socio-cultural consciousness of their affiliation with collective forms of civilized existence. A person possessing clearly articulated social ideals is not confined solely to personal motives and needs but is oriented towards the public good and actively operates in the interests of society.

The worldview aspects of the social ideal include the axiological orientation of the individual toward resolving various contradictions within the vast domain of informational reality. From early childhood, each individual is guided by a spiritual and moral system of internalized ideological values that shape their behavior, life objectives, and socially recognized means of achieving them.

It should be emphasized that the social nature of the cognitive orientation of the ideal, along with its integrative character, encompasses the value-based, normative, organizational, anthropo-psychological, and goal-setting elements of its content. In this respect, the ideal functions as a meaning-determining image of the individual's creative consciousness, hypothetically indicating the path to achieving the goal and the realization of the intended. "The organizational aspect of the ideal, asserts Yu. M. Lustin, is a specifically important form of self-realization of human intentions. In this respect, the ideal serves as an integrator embodying the unity of goals, means, and results of the individual's activity" [9, p. 60].

The philosophical and typological approach demonstrates that the content of the ideal transforms according to the worldview foundations of the historical epoch, the politico-ideological and cultural-national traditions of society, as well as the ideological and patriotic positions of the constructive personality. Simultaneously, its orienting, integrative, and mobilizing character may remain relatively stable, thereby influencing its worldview manifestation, in particular the cognitive-existential functionality of the ideal. Thus, in actualizing the problem of the existential choice of Donbass within the context of the value-semantic universe of the Russian world, Professor N. N. Emelyanova emphasizes: «The values of the Russian world, as an integral part of the global axiological sphere, possess specific characteristics conditioned by the long history of formation and development of the nations and peoples comprising Russia. Unlike Western thought, predominantly oriented towards a rational-individualistic worldview, Russian consciousness initially accorded priority to spiritual-collectivist ideals» [2, p. 44].

One of the key socio-typological characteristics of the ideal is its capacity to inspire a person to seek effective means of conscious activity for the benefit of society. This quality forms the basis of moral choice and a high level of social responsibility, as a person is capable of setting goals, reflecting on the outcomes of their own actions, and aligning them with the societal norms governing their existence. As is well known, responsibility entails a genuine understanding by the individual of the consequences of their personal acts and a readiness to be accountable for them before the state, society, the law, and other people.

The socio-typological component of the ideal contributes to the formation in the individual of ideological and moral values, proper political views, socially approved type-defined behavioral models. In this respect, the ideal acts as a dynamic given, the worldview content of which determines the level of the individual's spiritual and moral stability [1].

In its ontological essence, the ideal reflects the aspiration of the individual and society toward perfection, thereby defining the socio-methodological guidelines for their dialectical-typological interaction. The author emphasizes that the essence of the social ideal consists in the harmonious integration of personal and societal

interests, directed towards the comprehensive development of the typology (type) of the individual and the type (typology) of society. It entails the cultivation in an individual of typologically defined qualities such as responsibility, justice, compassion, the pursuit of knowledge and constructive labor activity, as well as respect for others and the environment” [5, p. 39].

The dialectical-typological content of the social ideal is revealed through its functions. The primary functions are: methodological, orientational-axiological, cognitive-transformative, predictive, logical-constructive, reflective, creative-motivational, cognitive-managerial, historical-cultural, social-regulatory.

These functions fundamentally and predominantly play an important role in human activity, defining, first of all, the intellectual objectives of one’s personal, social (collective), and professional development. Secondly, the multivariate content of the identified functions possesses a worldview, and therefore dominant, character, which optimizes the spiritual and moral manifestation of human qualities, substantially elevating the ideological and moral level of their self-consciousness. Thirdly, in its worldview manifestation, the dialectical aggregate of these functions objectifies the ‘conceptuality of typological reflection’ [8], coordinating the reflexive process of the individual’s cognitive activity. Emphasizing these points, Yu. M. Lustin writes: “The reflexive component of typological constructivism is aimed at the sociocultural reconstruction of all the preceding human knowledge, which allows the updated content to be representable in the process of innovative development of personal intellect. This establishment primarily presupposes the dialectic of the transition of logical-gnoseological connections, formations, and dependencies of various modalities into stable elements of human-scale content,…” [7, p. 192].

Thus, the ideal is a complex, socially multifarious phenomenon associated with a system of worldview interests, socio-political values, and an individual’s intellectual aspirations.

Within the context of socio-philosophical issues, the ideal is linked to personality characteristics such as responsibility, activity, communicativeness, projective integrative capacity, moral-ideological steadfastness, and the capacity for creative activity. These qualities ensure the inclusion of a consciously aware individual in social processes, thereby making them a fully realized subject of anthropo-historical development.

The formative role and integrative orientation of the social ideal toward enhancing a person’s level of worldview maturity are conditioned by the realization of its functions, which reveal their essence in the concept of dialectical-typological development of humans and society [11]. Comprehending the essence of the social ideal enables an individual to master the scientific principles of organizing activity, which guide their engagement toward achieving objectives and fulfilling the tasks of social development.

A philosophical and typological analysis of the social nature of the ideal allows for a deeper understanding of the processes of modern human formation and helps to determine the prospects for the further development of civilization. The calling of each person in spiritual activity is the constant search for truth and the meaning of life, as the great Russian writer Anton Pavlovich Chekhov stated. The worldview meaning of this expression is today more relevant than ever.

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